
Accretion discs in T Tauri stars and interacting binaries

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Summary

This thesis explores aspects of the theory of accretion discs in two astrophysical environments; around young low-mass stars - T Tauri stars, and in mass transfer binaries. The importance of discs in our understanding of these systems is already well-established, and in this thesis I investigate extensions of the simplest theoretical disc models to incorporate the complexities suggested by recent observations. A particular aim is to consider the role that magnetic fields - including fields within the disc and those of the central star - may play in controlling the evolution of the star-disc system.

The first part of the thesis investigates the effects of stellar magnetic fields on T Tauri accretion discs. There is abundant observational evidence, some of it summarised in the Introduction, that both discs and stellar magnetic activity are essential elements in the understanding of T Tauri stars, and the theoretical implications of this are developed. In Chapter 2 the main assumptions of the model are set out, and the steady-state properties of discs around magnetic T Tauri stars are derived. Chapter 3 develops a time-dependent disc model, which is used to examine the effect of time-varying magnetic fields on the disc. Variable stellar fields might occur if T Tauri stars harbour magnetic activity cycles analagous to those seen on the Sun, and I show that some of the long-term photometric variability in T Tauri systems could be caused by the influence of magnetic cycles on the accretion disc. Chapter 4 then follows the evolution of the star-disc system on much longer timescales by combining pre-main-sequence stellar evolution models with those for the disc. The resulting model is used to examine the rotation rates of magnetically braked T Tauri stars, and the possible influence of close binary companions on those rotation rates.

The second part of the thesis considers accretion discs in interacting binary systems. In Chapter 5 I discuss some of the consequences of a magnetic dynamo operating within the disc, for the structure and evolution of discs in dwarf novae. A magnetic dynamo is a promising candidate mechanism for the origin of the viscosity in accretion discs, and this Chapter discusses the implications of an operating dynamo for observations of dwarf novae, which are among the best studied systems containing accretion discs. A simple model is presented in which the prominent outbursts seen in these systems have a direct origin in the physics of the underlying disc dynamo. Finally, Chapter 6 presents the results of three dimensional simulations of the interaction between the gas stream from the mass-donating star and the accretion disc. The hydrodynamic calculations show that a significant fraction of the stream gas can ricochet off the outer rim of the disc and overflow towards smaller radii. I discuss the implications of these results for models and observations of low-mass X-ray binaries and cataclysmic variables.

Declaration

I declare that this thesis is not substantially the same as any that I have submitted for a degree, diploma, or any other qualification at this or any other university. No part of this thesis has been or is being submitted for any such qualification. This thesis is the outcome of my own work, except where explicit reference has been made to the work of others, though it includes ideas discussed in the collaborative works listed below. This thesis is less than 60,000 words in length.

The thesis is based in part on work presented in the following papers, which have been published or submitted for publication:

'Magnetically modulated accretion in T Tauri stars', C. J. Clarke, P. J. Armitage, K. W. Smith and J. E. Pringle, 1995, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 273, 639

'Magnetic cycles and photometric variability of T Tauri stars', P. J. Armitage, 1995, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 274, 1242

'Magnetic braking of T Tauri stars', P. J. Armitage and C. J. Clarke, 1996, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 280, 458

'The ejection of T Tauri stars from molecular clouds and the fate of circumstellar discs', P. J. Armitage and C. J. Clarke, 1996, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, submitted

'Dynamo driven accretion discs and dwarf nova eruptions', P. J. Armitage, M. Livio and J. E. Pringle, 1996, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 457, 332

'Accretion discs in interacting binaries: Simulations of the stream-disc impact', P. J. Armitage and M. Livio, 1996, *The Astrophysical Journal*, in press

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Accretion discs are central to some of the most intriguing phenomena in astrophysics. Discs are observed in young stellar systems, in a range of interacting binaries, and at the heart of active galactic nuclei. They appear to be essential elements in forming planetary systems, and in generating the jets and outflows seen in disc systems.

This thesis investigates aspects of accretion disc theory in two environments; around young low-mass stars – T Tauri stars, and in close binary systems where mass transfer between the stars occurs via an accretion disc. The basic theoretical ideas governing the evolution of discs in these systems are by no means new, and this thesis relies heavily on the work done on thin, viscous, discs by Shakura & Sunyaev (1973) and Lynden-Bell & Pringle (1974). In turn the important ideas underlying this theory – that viscous processes in a flattened disc could lead to a redistribution of angular momentum and permit mass to flow inwards – were understood much earlier by authors considering the formation and evolution of the solar nebula (see Pringle, 1981, for selected references).

Observations of accretion discs in protostellar systems and Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) have recently improved dramatically, and this largely obviates the need to summarise the wealth of indirect evidence that existed previously. The Hubble Space Telescope (HST) has imaged a substantial population of discs around stars in the Orion Nebula (McCaughrean & O'Dell 1996), with inferred radii spanning the range between 50 and 1000 a.u. In one spectacular case, an HST image shows *both* a resolved disc seen in silhouette and a prominent jet emerging from the central regions (Figure 1.1; Stapelfeldt et al. 1994). In AGN, observations by *ASCA* of a broad and asymmetric iron K alpha line (Tanaka et al. 1995) can only be straightforwardly explained as the signature of a relativistic disc, while the technique of eclipse mapping has provided further detailed information on the properties of discs in interacting binary systems.

Despite these greatly improved observations, many aspects of accretion disc theory are unclear or simply unknown. The most basic question, of what physical mechanism acts to redistribute angular momentum in a disc and thereby permit mass to flow inwards, remains elusive (for a recent review of the possibilities, see Papaloizou & Lin 1995). It is obviously tempting to hope that one transport mechanism operates across all discs, and

Figure 1.1: HST image of a disc and jet in HH 30. The diameter of the disc is around 300 a.u. Image reproduced from NASA PRC95-24a; Burrows, Hester & Morse.

turbulence generated by magnetohydrodynamic instabilities has attracted great interest as a viable possibility. Some aspects of this mechanism are discussed in Chapter 5 in the context of models for outbursts in dwarf nova accretion discs.

In addition to such fundamental questions, a wealth of theoretical problems arise in the application of the theory to the wide variety of known disc systems, and it is these that are the main focus of this thesis. In protostellar discs around T Tauri stars, it is increasingly recognized that *stellar* magnetic fields may interact with the disc and play an important role in controlling the evolution of the star-disc system. The thesis develops a model for magnetically dominated accretion that draws on earlier investigations of the accretion flow in magnetic Cataclysmic Variables (CVs). The model is then used to investigate the angular momentum history, variability, and photometric properties of young low-mass stars. In interacting binaries, I consider the role that internally generated magnetic fields might play in the outbursting dwarf nova systems, and use hydrodynamic simulations to model the peculiarities caused by the impact of a gas stream with the disc in CVs and low-mass X-ray binaries.

The later Chapters of this thesis retain their own introductions to the problems discussed therein. In this introductory Chapter, I review first some relevant aspects of T Tauri stars, with the focus on the evidence for strong stellar magnetic fields in these young stars. This motivates the discussion of a magnetospheric model for these systems presented in Chapters 2 through 4. Chapters 5 and 6 concern discs in binary systems, and a brief account of some of the relevant properties of these objects is also given in this Introduction, along with an outline of the rest of the thesis.

1.1 T Tauri stars

T Tauri stars are a class of young low-mass stars, named after the prototype T Tau, that was first recognized by Joy (1945). They lie above the main-sequence in the Hertzsprung-Russell (HR) diagram, and have inferred ages that span a range between $\sim 10^5$ yr and a few $\times 10^7$ yr. They have masses below ~ 3 solar masses – more massive pre-main-sequence stars are referred to as Herbig Ae/Be stars – and are found in and around molecular clouds such as Taurus-Auriga and ρ Ophiuchus. Many of the basic properties of T Tauri stars are reviewed by Bertout (1989).

In the current understanding of the formation of low-mass stars, T Tauri stars represent the earliest evolutionary stages that are visible in the optical. They therefore occupy the intermediate ground between the very youngest protostellar objects, which are deeply embedded in gas and dust and only detectable at infrared and radio wavelengths, and solar-type stars on the main-sequence. The diverse range of properties displayed by T Tauri stars then reflects primarily the wide gap between these starting and ending evolutionary points.

In addition to the interest from the viewpoint of star formation, motivation for studying T Tauri stars derives from a number of other directions. These systems display many currently poorly understood phenomena, some of which (discs, jets, outbursts etc.) are also seen in other, less well-observed, types of object. The presumed similarity of T Tauri stars to the conditions prevailing in the early solar system provides further interest, and points towards future studies of the nature and formation of other planetary systems.

1.1.1 Classification

T Tauri stars can be classified into two groups, the Classical T Tauri stars (CTTS) and the Weak Line T Tauri stars (WTTS). The pre-main-sequence nature of stars in both groups is established observationally from the existence of Li I $\lambda 6707$ absorption with an equivalent width larger than $100 \text{ m}\text{\AA}$ (Bertout 1989). This quantity provides a good measure of youth since Li is rapidly depleted by nuclear burning as the star approaches the main-sequence. The CTTS are then distinguished by their high equivalent width of $H\alpha$ ($\gtrsim 10 \text{ \AA}$), while stars with lower $H\alpha$ equivalent width are classified as WTTS.

Both CTTS and WTTS share some common properties; for example, variability at optical wavelengths and, frequently, high levels of X-ray emission. The most important difference is that CTTS have spectra that show excesses above the stellar photospheric level at both infrared and ultraviolet wavelengths, while WTTS show no ultraviolet excess and little or no excess at infrared wavelengths. These characteristics make WTTS harder to identify than CTTS (most early catalogues were based on objective prism surveys), and only with systematic X-ray surveys is a true picture of the two populations emerging. A review of a number of wide-area *ROSAT* surveys by Montmerle & Casanova (1995) reports values for the ratio of the number of WTTS to CTTS as high as ~ 10 , with many

of the newly identified WTTS being situated much further from known sites of active star formation than previously known T Tauri stars.

Theoretically, it is now established that the cause of the differences between CTTS and WTTS lies in the presence of discs around CTTS, while WTTS are relatively devoid of circumstellar material. Active accretion through the disc (supplemented by passive reprocessing of the stellar radiation) produces the infrared excess, while the energy released as the accreting material reaches the stellar surface is emitted primarily at short wavelengths and provides the ultraviolet excess. The defining strong $H\alpha$ emission lines in CTTS (as well as other lines such as Ca II H and K) are also thought to originate in the accretion flow close to the star. The shared properties are then most probably a consequence of strong magnetic activity in both classes of object, some of the evidence for which is discussed below.

Given this picture, it is certainly tempting to interpret the differences between CTTS and WTTS in terms of a simple evolutionary sequence, in which CTTS (with discs) later lose their discs and evolve into WTTS. The available evidence, however, suggests a more complicated scenario, since WTTS and CTTS seem to be freely intermingled when placed on an HR diagram (except for a region near the main-sequence populated only by WTTS). Age determinations of pre-main-sequence stars are notoriously difficult (Ghez 1996 discusses the problem of multiplicity, and accretion is also a worry), but some WTTS do seem to be as young or younger than typical CTTS (Walter et al. 1988). Thus while the general trend for present-day CTTS to clear their discs and evolve into WTTS must occur, many currently observed WTTS may have spent short or non-existent periods as optically visible CTTS. Sensitive searches for remnant circumstellar material around WTTS should help to clarify these questions (Wolk & Walter 1996).

1.1.2 Binarity

Surveys for pre-main-sequence binaries reveal that most young low-mass stars possess companions, and so in this respect at least the Sun may not have resembled a typical T Tauri star (Ghez 1996). In the separation range of 1 to 150 a.u. that current surveys are sensitive to, the frequency of binary companions significantly exceeds that found for comparable stars on the main-sequence (Duquennoy & Mayor 1991). The mechanisms that lead to the formation of these binaries are the subject of considerable theoretical effort (see, e.g. Clarke 1996).

Once formed, by whatever means, the high frequency of binaries among T Tauri stars will certainly have the potential to affect the appearance and evolution of the system. Individual circumstellar discs around the stars will be tidally truncated by the presence of a companion, while a circumbinary disc may surround the whole system (Lubow & Artymowicz 1996). Some implications of this for the evolution of discs will be discussed in Chapter 4. It is also worth noting that the observed degree of small-scale clustering in star forming regions (Gomez et al. 1993) implies that interactions between unbound stars (some of them possessing discs), may also not be uncommon among T

Tauri systems.

1.1.3 Discs

Infrared excesses provide one of the principal diagnostics of the presence of circumstellar material around T Tauri stars. When coupled with determinations of the optical extinction towards the central star they provide clear evidence for disc-like structures, as a spherical distribution of the infrared emitting material would lead to much larger visual extinctions than are actually observed. More than half of a large sample of pre-main-sequence stars in Taurus-Auriga have infrared excesses (Kenyon & Hartmann 1995), and their presence correlates with other disc indicators including millimeter continuum emission, ultraviolet excesses, and $H\alpha$ flux. The inferred temperatures of CTTS discs are typically a few thousand K or less in the innermost regions, so that emission shortward of $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ originates primarily from a very small (~ 1 a.u.) inner area of the disc. At these wavelengths the disc is optically thick, and hence the form of the infrared spectral energy distribution (SED) provides information only on the temperature distribution and inner radius of the disc.

Comparison of the SEDs of CTTS with steady state models of accretion discs shows that they are broadly consistent with accretion in CTTS occurring at rates of around $\sim 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (e.g. Bertout, Basri & Bouvier 1988). However the spectra are often flatter than predicted by flat, steady state disc models, implying a slower decline of effective temperature with radius than the $T \propto R^{-3/4}$ produced by both active and passive accretion discs. Popular explanations include flaring or warping of the disc (so that the more distant annuli receive more stellar radiation than a corresponding flat disc), or accretion rates that increase with radius. Discrepancies with simple disc models are also found at the shorter wavelengths characteristic of the inner disc, in the form of systems where the disc emission seems to be significantly redder than predicted by the models (Bertout et al. 1988; Kenyon, Yi & Hartmann 1996). The observed colours can be matched if the disc has an inner radius that is larger than the stellar radius by factors of a few, so that the hottest parts of the disc are replaced by an inner hole. A possible way to create and sustain such a hole is if the star has a magnetic field that disrupts its inner disc (Königl 1991), and this explanation seems increasingly plausible given independent lines of argument favouring strong magnetic activity in T Tauri stars. Details of such a model are set out in Chapter 2.

At longer wavelengths, millimeter interferometric maps of CO emission have detected extended flattened structures around several T Tauri stars. These discs have radii of ~ 100 a.u., and in some cases measured velocity fields supporting the assertion that these are indeed rotationally supported discs (Koerner & Sargent 1995; a review is given by Sargent 1996). These radii are in agreement with the inferred sizes of the disc-like structures seen in HST images (McCaughrean & O'Dell 1996).

At millimeter wavelengths, the dust emission from T Tauri discs is optically thin and vastly stronger than the stellar component at this wavelength. Continuum surveys

for this emission thus provide a sensitive probe for the existence of circumstellar material, and yield a direct measure of its mass subject to uncertainties in the dust opacity. Estimates for the total disc mass derived in this way (including the gas) are in the range $10^{-3} M_{\odot}$ to $1 M_{\odot}$, with values between 0.001 and $0.1 M_{\odot}$ typical (Adams, Emerson & Fuller 1990; Beckwith et al. 1990; Osterloh & Beckwith 1995). These discs are thus generally of low mass compared to that of the central star, but are of comparable mass to that required for the formation of the solar system.

Observational signatures of the evolutionary history of T Tauri discs are of great interest – for the purposes of this work primarily because the disc lifetime limits the fraction of the pre-main-sequence for which discs can affect stellar properties such as rotation (Chapter 4). More generally, the mechanisms that cause T Tauri stars to lose their discs, and the possible influence of planet formation on that process, are the cause of ample speculation. Based on infrared photometry, Strom (1995) finds evidence for discs in close to 100% of low mass stars in embedded clusters with masses in the range $0.1 M_{\odot} < M_{*} < 1 M_{\odot}$. For stars of mass $\sim 2 M_{\odot}$, discs appear to be absent by $t \sim 1$ Myr, while in lower mass systems with $M_{*} \lesssim 0.5 M_{\odot}$ discs can persist for in excess of 10 Myr (Strom 1995).

1.1.4 Outflows

Classical T Tauri stars exhibit energetic winds, which can be detected via broad blueshifted forbidden emission lines (the weaker redshifted lines being attributed to the presence of obscuration by the disc). A recent survey of 42 T Tauri stars by Hartigan, Edwards & Ghandour (1995) derived estimates for the parameters of winds and accretion in CTTS. Forbidden line emission was found in *all* stars possessing optically thick discs and near-infrared colour excesses, with estimated mass loss rates between 10^{-8} and $10^{-10} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (with considerable uncertainties). Accretion rates were in the range between 10^{-6} and $10^{-8} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and were correlated with the mass outflow rate.

The observations thus support theoretical models in which the presence of disc accretion is a necessary ingredient for driving winds, with a rather low ratio of mass outflow rate to mass accretion rate of ~ 0.01 for CTTS. Stronger outflows are observed in FU Orionis systems (Kenyon 1995) where the inferred mass accretion rate is similarly enhanced above the normal CTTS values.

1.1.5 Optical variability

Optical variability of T Tauri stars was initially one of the defining characteristics of the class, and is now known to extend over a very wide range of timescales including hours (Gullbring 1994), days and weeks (Edwards et al. 1993; Bouvier et al. 1993, 1995), and years or longer (Herbst et al. 1994). Variations of a magnitude of more in the optical are not uncommon.

The intermediate timescale variability is currently the most studied, and is commonly attributed to the rotation of an asymmetric distribution of star spots on the stellar

surface, which may be cooler (primarily in WTTS) or hotter than the stellar photosphere (in CTTS). These observations are discussed in more detail in Chapter 4, but for now it suffices to note that they provide a straightforward way to measure the stellar rotation period independent of the unknown inclination of the rotation axis to the line of sight. The spin periods thus derived are found to be relatively long, with rotation rates typically an order of magnitude below the breakup speed (Bouvier 1991), and with CTTS rotating a factor of ~ 2 slower than WTTS.

The most dramatic variability on longer timescales is exhibited in the FU Orionis objects, pre-main-sequence sources that are observed to undergo large amplitude outbursts of 3–6 magnitudes in the optical (Hartmann 1991; Kenyon 1995). The spectra of FU Orionis objects in outburst are consistent with rapid disc accretion at $\sim 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (in particular, double peaked structure is observed in optical line profiles), and this suggests that what is being seen are periodic outbursts occurring in T Tauri discs. Theoretical models of thermal instabilities in CTTS discs (e.g. Bell & Lin 1994) are quite successful in reproducing the basic properties of the (very limited) observed sample of events. However the relation, if any exists, between large amplitude FU Orionis outbursts and the ubiquitous lesser variability in CTTS is unclear, and obviously depends on the unknown fraction of CTTS that are prone to FU Orionis-like episodes.

1.1.6 X-ray properties

Both classes of T Tauri stars are found to be strong X-ray sources, with luminosities in this waveband several orders of magnitude greater than main-sequence stars of similar spectral type (for a review, see Montmerle 1992). Since the optical signatures of WTTS are rather subtle, X-ray selection proves to be an efficient technique for finding these systems, and ROSAT observations have led to a large increase in the number of known WTTS (Alcála et al. 1996). The distribution of these new sources is more extended than previously known samples, and this is discussed further in Chapter 2.

Neuhäuser et al. (1995) find median luminosities for detected CTTS in Taurus of $\log(L_X/\text{ergs s}^{-1}) = 29.09 \pm 0.03$, as compared to $\log(L_X/\text{ergs s}^{-1}) = 29.70 \pm 0.05$ for WTTS. A correlation between L_X and the stellar rotation rate indicates that much of this difference is attributable to the faster rotation (on average) of WTTS, though other correlations are also found. The emission in both cases is consistent with thermal emission from a ~ 1 keV plasma, which corresponds to temperatures of $\sim 10^7$ K.

Flaring is also observed in X-ray observations, with powerful events displaying peak luminosities of several $\times 10^{31} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ (Montmerle 1992) and timescales of hours. The spectra and properties of these flares are analogous to very greatly scaled up versions of solar flares, and application of simple models of this nature permits estimation of the magnetic fields involved. From observations of a giant flare on the CTTS LkH α 92, Preibisch et al. (1993) derived a minimum value of the magnetic field of 210 G.

1.1.7 Radio properties

Radio observations offer a further probe of flaring and magnetic activity on T Tauri stars. Around 10% of WTTS surveyed at 5 GHz exhibit radio emission at levels of $10^{16} - 10^{17}$ ergs s^{-1} Hz^{-1} (O'Neal et al. 1990), which is 3 to 4 orders of magnitude stronger than powerful radio flares on the Sun. The most energetic flares on WTTS are an order of magnitude stronger still. The rise time for flares can be as short as hours, implying that these are events originating close to the star, though the constraints from this argument are not very strong.

Very long baseline interferometry (VLBI) observations have been reported for a number of radio bright WTTS (Phillips, Lonsdale & Feigelson 1991). In all cases the emission was found to originate from very close ($\sim 15 R_*$) to the star, and to be inconsistent with thermal emission processes. Both unresolved ($\lesssim 2 R_*$) and resolved components of the emission were detected, and these authors suggested that the latter provided evidence for large scale ordered magnetic structures in these systems.

A follow-up multiwavelength study of the T Tauri star HD 283447 (Feigelson et al. 1994) provides intriguing suggestions as to the magnetic field structure in radio bright T Tauri stars. The target star is apparently young, luminous, and possesses an infra-red disc excess, yet is classified as a WTTS on the basis of an equivalent width of $H\alpha$ of just 2-4 Å. The lack of signatures of accretion may well be due to the presence of a spectroscopic binary companion (Phillips et al. 1996), which would explain the rare mix of CTTS and WTTS characteristics in this star. During the observing campaign, the radio luminosity was found to vary by a factor of four, unaccompanied by changes in the optical spectral lines or X-ray emission. An interpretation for this is that part of the radio emission originates from large magnetic structures many stellar radii in extent, while the X-ray and flaring activity is generated closer to the star in extremely powerful versions of solar-like activity.

The conclusions that can be drawn from these observations concerning the magnetic field configuration in the majority of T Tauri stars are limited, since the fraction of stars detectable via VLBI is quite small. They may therefore be unrepresentative of most T Tauri stars, while the particularly well-studied system HD 283447 is itself probably unique (and extremely interesting for studies of binary-disc interactions). With these caveats, however, the VLBI observations do provide strong evidence that apparently symmetric, extended magnetic structures can exist in T Tauri stars.

1.1.8 Direct measurements of magnetic fields

The X-ray luminosities of T Tauri stars and the optical flares observed in WTTS are consistent with models in which these stars possess magnetic activity that is an enormously (10 – 100 times) scaled-up analogue of that seen on the Sun. This suggests magnetic fields of kG strength covering a large fraction of the stellar surface, and motivates consideration of models in which fields of comparable magnitude can interact with the accretion disc or drive stellar winds. Although encouraging, it is clear though that

Table 1.1: Reported measurements of TTS magnetic fields via Zeeman broadening

Star	Classification	fB / G
TAP 35	WTTS	1000^{+500}_{-500}
LkCa 16	WTTS	1700^{+600}_{-600}
LkCa 7	WTTS	2500^{+500}_{-2500}
HBC 427	WTTS	2500^{+300}_{-1000}
TAP 10	WTTS	< 1000
LkCa 15	CTTS	< 2000

much of the observational evidence for these fields rests on questionable comparisons with better understood magnetic stars, in which the physical conditions are very different. Most strikingly, CTTS display broad emission lines such as $H\alpha$, Ca II and Mg II that appear to be connected to the accretion process rather than to magnetic fields. This problem is absent in WTTS, but even in these systems the large jump in inferred magnetic activity suggests extrapolations from solar behaviour should be treated with caution.

For these reasons, attempts to measure directly magnetic fields in T Tauri stars are particularly valuable. To date, successful detections have been claimed by two groups (Basri, Marcy & Valenti 1992; Guenther & Emerson 1996) for a total sample of 4 WTTS. The technique in both instances is to search for the broadening of spectral lines due to the Zeeman effect, which has an advantage over other spectropolarimetric techniques (Johnstone & Penston 1987) in that it can yield a signal even when the field geometry leads to a net cancellation of flux along the line of sight. Since spectral lines in T Tauri stars are also broadened as a consequence of rotation and thermal broadening, a differential method is employed wherein the equivalent width of Zeeman sensitive lines is compared to that of Zeeman insensitive lines formed in similar regions of the stellar atmosphere. This approach works best for WTTS – in CTTS the presence of typically greater rotational broadening and veiling (filling-in) of the spectra tends to reduce the sensitivity of the observations to kG strength magnetic fields.

Table 1.1 reproduces the results reported by Basri et al. (1992) for TAP 35 and TAP 10; together with those of Guenther & Emerson (1996) for LkCa 7, LkCa 15, LkCa 16, and HBC 427. The quantity measured is the product of the stellar field B , and the filling factor f that the field occupies on the stellar surface. Much fuller discussions of the errors on these measurements (which for the Guenther & Emerson values are probably *overestimated* in the above table) are given in the original papers.

The sample of stars with measured fields is evidently still rather small, and thus it is not yet possible to begin attempting to correlate the field strengths with other stellar parameters such as the rotation rate. However on the basis of these reported

detections, it seems likely that stellar magnetic fields with $fB = 1 - 2$ kG are common in WTTS. Encouragingly, these values are consistent with those inferred from other, more indirect, measures of magnetic activity. Frustratingly, for the CTTS (where the indirect approaches are most suspect), the position is still unclear. There are no reported detections or upper limits stringent enough to strongly constrain models, and the case for magnetic fields in these systems remains strong but circumstantial at present.

1.1.9 Importance of stellar magnetospheres

The preceding Sections have summarised some of the evidence for the presence of both active accretion discs and strong stellar magnetic activity in Classical T Tauri stars. A number of observations also lend support to the idea that *interaction* of the stellar magnetosphere with the disc is an important process in CTTS. These include:

- The infrared colours of CTTS discs, which are often redder than expected if the disc extends to the stellar surface (1.1.3).
- The presence of hotspots in CTTS but not in WTTS, which could be caused by gas infalling along magnetospheric field lines onto the star (1.1.5).
- The slow rotation of T Tauri stars, especially CTTS, which can be explained via magnetic braking via interaction of the star with its disc (e.g. Königl 1991).
- Kinematic evidence for mass infall at free fall velocities in many CTTS spectra (e.g. Edwards et al. 1994). These are consistent with a magnetospheric model for accretion close to the star (Hartmann et al. 1994).

Recent reviews by Edwards (1995) and Hartmann (1994) concur that these observations suggest that magnetospheric accretion is most probably a common phenomena in Classical T Tauri stars.

1.2 Interacting binaries

The interacting binaries include a diverse variety of double star systems in which mass is transferred between the binary companions. Mass transfer may occur either via stellar winds, or as a result of one star overflowing its Roche lobe and losing mass to the companion through the inner Lagrange point, and it is this latter type of mass transfer that is exclusively of interest in this thesis (see e.g., Shore 1994; Livio 1994; van den Heuvel 1994, for reviews of these mechanisms). If the accreting star is small enough, then the angular momentum of the matter flowing through the inner Lagrange point, L_1 , ensures that it cannot fall directly onto the surface of the star, and will instead form a disc (e.g. Whitehurst 1988a, 1988b, for explicit numerical calculations of this process). This picture applies for non-magnetic or very weakly magnetised primaries - many complications are possible if, conversely, the accreting star possesses a magnetic field strong enough to partially or entirely inhibit the formation of a disc.

Amongst these systems, the first level of classification is provided by the nature of the accreting star, which may be an unevolved main-sequence star, a white dwarf, neutron star or possibly a black hole. As the gravitational potential well deepens greatly along this sequence, the potential accretion luminosity and inner disc temperature rise rapidly. For both cataclysmic variables (where the accreting object is a white dwarf) and low-mass X-ray binaries (where the donor is a star of mass $\lesssim 1.2 M_{\odot}$ and the accretor a neutron star) the accretion luminosity often dominates the emission from the system. Whereas cataclysmic variables (CVs) are relatively weak X-ray sources, the low-mass X-ray binaries (LMXBs) comprise many of the strongest galactic X-ray sources.

For the purpose of studying the behaviour of accretion discs, CVs and LMXBs offer a number of advantages, which include:

- Timescales. The dynamical timescale in the inner disc of a CV is \sim seconds, typical orbital timescales are \sim hours, and outbursts occur with durations and spacings measured in days and weeks. These are all relatively convenient observationally, and allow the time-dependent properties of the disc to be investigated. Theoretically this translates into the ability to probe the *viscosity* in the disc - one of the most mysterious aspects of accretion discs.
- Origin in binary systems, permitting accurate determination of many of the system parameters, and, in the most useful cases, observations of eclipses. These in turn permit the gathering of a limited amount of *spatial* information on the disc properties, via techniques such as eclipse mapping (e.g. Horne 1985).
- Dominant system emission originating from the accretion process, with strong emission frequently in the optical and near ultraviolet for CVs.

Below I discuss some of the properties of dwarf novae - a subset of the CVs that prove to be the most useful for investigating the evolution of discs. The large amplitude outbursts observed in these systems are the prototypical examples of time-dependent disc behaviour, and as such provide the most stringent constraints on theoretical models. The most successful model for the outbursts is based on a disc thermal instability, and I discuss the main ideas underlying this model.

1.2.1 Dwarf novae

Cataclysmic variable binaries typically consist of an unevolved main-sequence star and a white dwarf of mass $\sim 1 M_{\odot}$. The distribution of orbital periods ranges from ~ 80 minutes to ~ 12 hours, with a 'Period Gap' between 2 and 3 hours (e.g. van den Heuvel 1994). Variability is observed both on short timescales ('flickering' - see Bruch 1992), and in the form of nova and dwarf nova outbursts. The nova outbursts are modelled as thermonuclear events on the surface of the accreting star, whereas the dwarf nova outbursts are due to an increased rate of mass accretion through the disc.

The photometric properties of dwarf nova outbursts are highly diverse (see e.g. the lightcurves reproduced in Livio 1994). In the relatively well-behaved system VW

Hyi, normal outbursts have a visual amplitude of ~ 4 magnitudes, a duration of 4-5 days, and a recurrence time of 25-30 days. There is a large range in these parameters, for example recurrence times in the WZ Sge subclass extend to years. Typical outbursts attain disc effective temperatures of the order of 20000 K, and involve energies of a few $\times 10^{40}$ ergs. The average accretion rate over an outburst cycle implied by these numbers is a few $\times 10^{16}$ gs^{-1} .

The inferred increase in the accretion rate during a dwarf nova outburst could in principle be due either to a burst of enhanced mass transfer from the secondary, or to an instability that increases the viscosity (and hence accretion rate) in a disc replenished with gas at a constant rate from the companion (for references for these models see Livio 1994). Observations (especially of the outer disc radius, which is predicted to shrink during a enhanced burst of mass transfer, but to expand during outburst in the disc instability model) are more consistent with the disc instability model, which is based on the existence of a thermal instability in dwarf nova accretion discs (this is not to imply that *all* of the variety of dwarf nova behaviour can be explained without considering also variable mass transfer). Chapter 5 discusses a modified thermal instability mechanism for dwarf nova, for comparison below I outline the 'standard' picture for the origin of these events.

1.2.2 Outbursts as disc thermal instabilities

Dwarf novae are generally modelled using the geometrically thin α disc models of the type considered by Shakura & Sunyaev (1973), in which the kinematic viscosity ν is related to the disc sound speed c_s and scale height H via $\nu = \alpha c_s H$, with α a free parameter. For such discs, the thermal properties of an annulus are to a good approximation determined by a balance between local viscous heating and cooling via radiation from the top and bottom surfaces of the disc. This simple situation occurs because radial fluxes are small (since for a thin disc the gradients in the vertical direction are much greater), and the thermal timescale is much shorter than the viscous. As a consequence, it is possible to construct a local model for the vertical disc structure at a given radius, and with a value assumed for the free parameter α . Such a thermal equilibrium solution yields the effective temperature T_e of the annulus (or, equivalently, the mass accretion rate \dot{M} through the annulus), as a function of the local surface density Σ . This calculation requires as input the opacity, κ , which determines the relation between the central and effective temperatures of the annulus.

Detailed vertical structure calculations of this nature yield curves for $T_e(\Sigma)$ that are schematically of the form shown in Figure 1.2 (e.g. Faulkner, Lin & Papaloizou 1983). The important feature of these solutions is that in the temperature interval corresponding to the partial ionization of hydrogen (near 10^4 K), a branch is obtained on which $d \log T_e / d \log \Sigma < 0$. This means that there is a range of surface densities where solutions can be found in which the annulus is either hot and ionized (the hot branch) or relatively cool and predominantly neutral (the cold branch). Both of these

Figure 1.2: Illustrative results of disc vertical structure calculations plotted in the $\log \Sigma - \log T_e$ plane. The middle branch of solutions with $d \log T_e / d \log \Sigma < 0$ is thermally unstable. For intermediate mass fluxes into the disc (where if a steady state existed T_e would lie on the middle branch), the annulus can undergo limit cycle behaviour as shown by the arrowed path.

branches represent valid equilibria (since if Σ increases, the increased viscous dissipation is matched by an increased T_e). By the same argument, however, the middle branch must be thermally *unstable*, and does not represent a valid equilibrium state of the annulus.

Suppose now that the mass transfer rate from the secondary lies in the interval of \dot{M} for which the annulus has no stable solutions. Steady mass flow through the annulus at this externally imposed \dot{M} is then not possible, and a limit cycle occurs instead. If the annulus is at some initial time on the cold branch, then the rate of inflow through the annulus is less than the applied \dot{M} , and the surface density gradually increases. This continues until Σ exceeds Σ_{\max} , the maximum surface density on the cold branch, whereupon the annulus moves rapidly toward the hot branch. Once thermal equilibrium has been attained on the upper stable branch, however, the mass inflow rate exceeds \dot{M} , and Σ begins to fall towards Σ_{\min} , the minimum surface density on the hot branch. Cyclic behaviour as illustrated in the Figure then ensues.

What has been described thus far is a purely local analysis for a single annulus in the disc, and this indicates that *for that annulus* transitions between a hot and cold state should occur. This is some way from demonstrating that a thermal instability can produce a dwarf nova outburst, for which purpose the *entire disc* must alternate between the two thermally stable states. Detailed calculations (e.g. Cannizzo 1993) show that global outbursts can be produced from this mechanism, but only if the effective viscosity in the low state (parameterized by the value of α) is a factor of several less than that in the high state. Thus although thermal instability models provide an attractive

mechanism for dwarf nova outbursts, they are obviously incomplete in the absence of physical processes that might create the required variations in the viscosity during the course of the cycle. Chapter 5 will discuss a magnetic process that might achieve this goal.

1.3 Plan of the thesis

The first part of this thesis, comprising Chapters 2, 3 and 4; develops a magnetospheric model for accretion in T Tauri stars. There is abundant evidence, some of which has been touched on above, that both accretion discs and stellar magnetic activity are important elements in the understanding of T Tauri systems, and these Chapters explore some of the theoretical implications of these observations. In Chapter 2 I set out the main assumptions of the model, and look at the consequences for steady state properties of T Tauri accretion discs. A straightforward result is that a disc disrupted at small radii by a stellar magnetic field is much less conspicuous at near infrared wavelengths than an undisrupted disc, and I investigate whether this can explain some of the unusual properties of the outlying Weak-Lined systems discovered by ROSAT. Chapter 3 develops a time-dependent disc model, which is used to examine the possible influence of variable stellar magnetic fields on the disc. Variable fields might occur if T Tauri stars harbour magnetic dynamos and activity cycles analagous to those seen on the Sun, and I discuss in particular the photometric signature expected from such a scenario. Finally for this part of the thesis, in Chapter 4 the evolution of the star-disc system on much longer timescales is investigated by combining the model for a magnetically dominated disc with a pre-main-sequence stellar track. The rotation rates of Classical and Weak-Lined T Tauri stars, and the possible effects of close binaries on those rotation rates, are examined using the resulting model.

The second part of the thesis consists of two self-contained Chapters that deal with aspects of accretion disc theory in interacting binaries. Chapter 5 explores some of the consequences of a magnetic dynamo origin for the viscosity in dwarf novae, which are some of the best observed disc systems. I discuss both the qualitative observational predictions of a disc dynamo, and present an example model in which the prominent outbursts seen in these systems have a direct dynamo origin. Finally, in Chapter 6, I present the results of three dimensional simulations of the interaction between the stream and the accretion disc. Observations of low-mass X-ray binaries in particular have suggested that the impact of the stream induces marked non-axisymmetric structure in the disc, and this is found to be consistent with the results of the hydrodynamic simulations.

Chapter 2

Magnetospheric accretion in T Tauri stars

This Chapter develops a model for the evolution of viscous accretion discs around T Tauri stars possessing a strong stellar magnetic field. The ingredients required to construct the model are twofold; first an equation for the evolution of the disc surface density in response to viscous and magnetic torques and, second, a model for the interaction between the stellar magnetosphere and the disc. The derivation of the disc evolution equation is outlined below, and is a straightforward modification of the well-known equation for thin viscous accretion discs. The behaviour of the stellar magnetosphere in the presence of the disc is much less well understood, and many models have been put forward by various authors (a partial list includes Ghosh & Lamb 1979; Cameron & Campbell 1993; Yi 1994; Lynden-Bell & Boily 1994; Lovelace, Romanova & Bisnovatyi-Kogan 1995; Ostriker & Shu 1995; Pearson & King 1995; Wang 1995). This work uses a rather simple description of the magnetic field configuration that was previously employed by Livio & Pringle (1992) in modelling discs around magnetic white dwarfs, and the assumptions of this model (together with some of the differences as compared to the previously cited authors) are described below. I then derive some of the steady state properties of the discs, and suggest an application of the magnetospheric disc model to the population of Weak-Lined T Tauri stars recently identified via *ROSAT* X-ray surveys.

2.1 Equation for disc surface density evolution

The standard derivation for the time-dependent behaviour of accretion discs considers a gaseous accretion disc that is thin, flat and axisymmetric. If the mass of the disc is small enough relative to that of the central body, then the orbits of gas elements in such a disc are stable and circular with an angular frequency Ω . To obtain evolution and inflow of matter through the disc, it is then necessary to postulate that either internal viscous processes or external torques act to redistribute or remove angular momentum from the disc. Three timescales are then of particular interest: the dynamical timescale $t_{\text{dyn}} = \Omega^{-1}$, the thermal timescale t_{th} over which radiation would cool the disc if heating

processes were switched off, and the viscous timescale t_ν over which angular momentum transfer leads to order unity changes in the disc surface density.

For many discs, the hierarchy of these timescales is such that $t_\nu \gg t_{\text{th}} \geq t_{\text{dyn}}$, i.e. radiation from the disc is efficient enough to remove energy dissipated by viscous processes close to where it was generated, and viscous processes require many dynamical times to take effect. In cylindrical polar coordinates (R, ϕ, z) the radial inflow velocity v_R is then small compared to the orbital velocity v_ϕ .

Despite this seeming plethora of assumptions, the conditions listed above are likely to be valid in most of the inner part of T Tauri discs (at large radii, gravitational instability may induce departures from axisymmetry, while conditions in any boundary layer close to the stellar surface also demand more careful attention). The procedure for deriving the equation for the time-dependence of discs in this limit is now standard (see, e.g., Pringle 1981; Frank, King & Raine 1992; Shu 1992), and only the main steps are reproduced here. The equation representing conservation of mass is,

$$R \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (R \Sigma v_R) = 0, \quad (2.1)$$

where Σ is the disc surface density. Conservation of angular momentum yields the equation,

$$R \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Sigma R^2 \Omega) + \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (R \Sigma v_R \cdot R^2 \Omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\partial G}{\partial R} + \frac{G_B}{2\pi}, \quad (2.2)$$

where $G(R, t)$ is the viscous torque exerted by an annulus in the disc on its inner neighbour, and G_B the torque from (external) magnetic fields. Specifically,

$$G = 2\pi R \cdot \nu \Sigma R \frac{d\Omega}{dR} \cdot R = 2\pi \nu \Sigma R^3 \frac{d\Omega}{dR}, \quad (2.3)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity, and

$$G_B = -\frac{B_z B_\phi}{4\pi} \cdot 2 \cdot 2\pi R \cdot R = -B_z B_\phi R^2. \quad (2.4)$$

Here the sense of B_ϕ is defined such that $B_\phi > 0$ implies a magnetic torque opposing the disc rotation, and a factor of two is included as magnetic torques act on both upper and lower disc surfaces. To preserve the axisymmetry of the problem, it is assumed that the magnetic axis is aligned with the stellar rotation axis and perpendicular to the plane of the disc. This is unlikely to be the case in real systems (where observations of rotational modulation of the stellar light by hotspots suggest a non-axisymmetric magnetic structure), and some of the limitations of this assumption are discussed in the following Section.

For a Keplerian disc,

$$\Omega = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R^3}}, \quad (2.5)$$

where M is the mass of the central star. Eliminating v_R from equations (2.1) and (2.2) and using the specific forms for G , G_B and Ω then yields the following equation for the time-dependence of the disc surface density (Livio & Pringle 1992),

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} = \frac{3}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left[R^{1/2} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (\nu \Sigma R^{1/2}) \right] + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left[\frac{B_z B_\phi R^{5/2}}{\pi \sqrt{GM}} \right]. \quad (2.6)$$

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram of the assumed magnetic field configuration. Field lines with footpoints on the star and the disc are twisted due to differential rotation. Inside the corotation radius (dashed line), the angular velocity of the disc exceeds that of the star, and the field lines are dragged along with the flow to exert a braking torque on the disc. Outside corotation the field lines are swept in the opposite direction and tend to impart angular momentum to the disc.

The kinematic viscosity leads to a diffusive term on the right-hand side that will be non-linear in Σ if, as is normally the case, ν is itself a function of the local disc conditions. The magnetic torque adds a second term that falls off rapidly with radius for models in which the magnetic field originates in a stellar magnetosphere.

The time dependent solution of equation (2.6) evidently requires knowledge of the form of both ν and $B_z B_\phi$, neither of which is known with any great certainty. For some important *steady state* disc properties such as the temperature distribution, however, the important quantity is the combination $\nu \Sigma$, which can be found from (2.6) independent of the nature of the viscosity. Deferring discussion of the form of ν until Chapter 3, I therefore begin by considering the behaviour of the magnetic torque term and proceed to steady state solutions of equation (2.6).

2.2 Evaluating the magnetic torque

The physical picture of the disc–magnetosphere interaction is illustrated in Figure 2.1. The star possesses an ordered magnetic field, which for simplicity is assumed to be a dipole aligned with the rotation axis and perpendicular to the disc plane. Some evidence for large scale magnetic fields in T Tauri stars is provided by analysis of VLBI observations of HD 283447 (Feigelson et al. 1994), though close to the stellar surface the

field structure is doubtless much more complex. Following previous authors (e.g. Ghosh & Lamb 1979), it is assumed that despite the high electrical conductivity of the inner disc the stellar field is able to fully penetrate the disc gas, as a result of local instabilities that mix the magnetospheric field with the disc plasma. The stellar field lines then have footpoints that are anchored both to the star and to the rotating disc material.

The *corotation radius*, R_c , is defined as the radius in the disc where the angular velocity of the Keplerian disc material equals that of the star,

$$R_c = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{\Omega_*^3}}. \quad (2.7)$$

For radii in the disc $R < R_c$, the faster rotation of the disc relative to the star drags the field lines along with the flow. The field acts to remove angular momentum from the disc, and a corresponding spin-up torque is exerted on the star. For $R > R_c$, the opposite is the case, and the magnetic linkage in this region imparts angular momentum to the disc and exerts a spin-down torque on the star.

A quantitative estimate of the magnetic torque requires knowledge of the radial dependence of $B_z B_\phi$ as in equation (2.4). Following Campbell (1992) and Livio & Pringle (1992), B_z is taken as the unperturbed dipole field,

$$B_z = B_* \left(\frac{R}{R_*} \right)^{-3}, \quad (2.8)$$

where R_* is the stellar radius and $B_* R_*^3 = \mu$, the stellar dipole moment. From this poloidal field, a toroidal component B_ϕ is generated from the shearing of field lines anchored both to the star and to the disc. The growth in B_ϕ due to shearing may be limited either by processes in the disc, for example by magnetic buoyancy or turbulent diffusion (Campbell 1992; Lovelace et al. 1995), or by reconnection of field lines in the magnetosphere. Assuming that this latter mechanism provides the most stringent limit on the twist of the magnetic field, Livio & Pringle (1992) obtain for an equilibrium toroidal field,

$$B_\phi = B_z \frac{[\Omega(R) - \Omega_*]}{\Omega(R)}, \quad (2.9)$$

which assumes that the rate of reconnection is $\sim \Omega(R)$, the local Keplerian angular velocity. At corotation B_ϕ vanishes, as expected, and inside R_c the twist is limited such that $B_\phi \sim B_z$. Beyond corotation the detailed form of equation (2.9) is unlikely to be of great importance, as the radial dependence of the magnetic torque G_B will be dominated by the dipolar fall off of $B_z^2 \propto R^{-6}$. In particular, and following a suggestion by Wang (private communication), the sensitivity of the results presented later in this thesis to a specific modification of equation (2.9) was explicitly checked. The modification consisted of replacing Ω in the denominator of (2.9) with Ω_* for $R > R_c$, which ensures that $B_\phi \sim B_z$ for all radii in the disc. The results were not found to be seriously changed by this alternate prescription, although rather stronger stellar fields would then be required to compensate for the reduced torque as compared to that implied by equation (2.9).

Figure 2.2: Schematic diagram of the assumed accretion flow. Outside the magnetospheric radius R_m , accretion occurs via a thin disc with slow radial inflow. At R_m the disc is disrupted by the stellar magnetosphere, and interior to this radius material follows the field lines to impact the star at high latitude and with a velocity close to the free-fall speed.

Combining the magnetic torque formula (2.9) with equation (2.6) provides an equation for the time-dependence of the disc subject to the influence of the stellar magnetosphere,

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} = \frac{3}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left[R^{1/2} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (\nu \Sigma R^{1/2}) \right] + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left[\frac{\Omega - \Omega_*}{\Omega} \frac{B_z^2 R^{5/2}}{\pi \sqrt{GM_*}} \right]. \quad (2.10)$$

The picture of the accretion flow described by this equation is shown schematically in Figure 2.2. At large radii, well beyond corotation, the effect of the magnetic torques is negligible. The disc here is well described by the normal non-magnetic expressions. Closer to corotation, but still outside it, the field acts to inject angular momentum into the disc and hence inhibits inflow and accretion. Compared to a non-magnetic disc, higher surface densities will generally be required to sustain a given \dot{M} . Once inside corotation, the magnetic torque acts to remove angular momentum, and drives a rapidly increasing inflow velocity through the disc. Eventually, the magnetic field removes all the angular momentum from the gas, and by this stage the assumptions underlying the above derivation have obviously broken down. At smaller radii, the magnetosphere is likely to completely dominate the structure of the accretion flow, so that the gas falls in along the field lines to impact the star at high latitudes in an accretion column geometry. The hotspots inferred in Classical T Tauri stars are often interpreted as being formed at the bases of such columns.

The above analysis assumes that the field lines linking the disc outside corotation remain closed, and thus able to transmit a spin-down torque to the star. Alternative models have been proposed in which the field becomes twisted to an angle where it is prone to a catastrophic breakdown, in which the previously closed magnetic field configuration becomes open (Lynden-Bell & Boily 1994). The resulting magnetosphere has an inner part where the field lines are closed, and an outer region where the field lines threading the disc are open. Models with a magnetic field configuration of this general character have been proposed by several authors (Lovelace, Romanova & Bisnovatyi-Kogan 1995; Ostriker & Shu 1995), and it has been suggested that the open field lines may be able to power the outflows that are observed in some young stars. A full exploration of the properties of these models is not attempted here, but it is worth noting that the main benefits of magnetospheric accretion from an observational viewpoint (reduced near-IR excesses, infall at the free-fall velocity, and regulation of the stellar angular momentum), seem also to be possible within such models.

2.3 Steady state solutions

Steady state solutions of the disc evolution equation can be found straightforwardly by setting the time derivative in equation (2.10) to zero once appropriate boundary conditions are chosen. At the magnetospheric radius, the magnetic torques lead to rapid inflow and large (free-fall) radial velocities v_R . The surface density (and kinematic viscosity, assuming this to be an increasing function of Σ) then becomes very small, so that the appropriate boundary condition is to take $\nu\Sigma = 0$ at $R = R_m$. At large radii the magnetic field has negligible influence on the disc, such that $\nu\Sigma = \dot{M}/(3\pi)$ as $R \rightarrow \infty$ (the usual non-magnetic disc expression). Imposing these boundary conditions the solution is,

$$\nu\Sigma = \frac{\dot{M}}{3\pi} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{R_m}{R}} \right) - \beta R^{-7/2} \left[\left(\frac{R}{R_m} \right)^3 - 1 \right] + 2\beta R_c^{-3/2} R^{-2} \left[\left(\frac{R}{R_m} \right)^{3/2} - 1 \right], \quad (2.11)$$

with $\beta = (B_* R_*^3)^2 / (9\pi \sqrt{GM_*})$. The first term on the right-hand side of this expression is the same as for a non-magnetic disc with a $\Sigma = 0$ boundary condition at $R_{\text{inner}} = R_m$, while the remaining terms represent the modifications due to the magnetic field. These decline in importance at large radii.

The above equation does not specify the location of the magnetosphere relative to corotation. Previous work (Cameron & Campbell 1993; Clarke et al. 1995) suggests that the disc is disrupted by the field close to the radius where the magnetic torques first exceed the viscous. This yields an estimate for R_m that is independent of ν ,

$$R_m \simeq \left(\frac{2B_*^2 R_*^6}{\dot{M} \sqrt{GM_*}} \right)^{2/7} \quad (2.12)$$

and which scales as a weak function of \dot{M} .

Figure 2.3: steady state disc solutions for $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ (left panel) and $\dot{M} = 10^{-8} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ (right panel). Plotted is the quantity $3\pi\nu\Sigma$ which $\rightarrow \dot{M}$ at large radii. The dotted line shows a non-magnetic disc with $R_{\text{inner}} = R_*$, the dashed line a non-magnetic disc with $R_{\text{inner}} = R_c$, and the solid lines magnetic models disrupted at corotation with $B_* = 500, 1000,$ and 2000 G. The position of corotation (appropriate to $P_* = 6$ dy) is shown as the dashed vertical line.

This simple criterion for the location of R_m becomes more complicated if R_m becomes comparable to R_c . Beyond R_c , any magnetic linkage between the star and disc acts to impart angular momentum to the disc material rather than to remove it, and hinders accretion through the disc. This implies that if $R_m > R_c$ accretion onto the star will be cut off, and hence *no* steady solution for Σ exists in this regime. Time dependent models show that if the magnetosphere is pushed beyond corotation, for example in response to an impulsive increase in B_* , then accretion onto the star ceases and inflowing matter begins to pile up at small radii. Eventually the viscous torques are strengthened sufficiently to return R_m to corotation, and a steady state is established with $R_m \approx R_c$.

The same theoretical calculations (presented here as Chapter 4; see also Cameron & Campbell 1993; Cameron, Campbell & Quaintrell 1995; Ostriker & Shu 1995) show that for mass fluxes in the range between $\dot{M} = 10^{-8} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ and $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$, a good approximation is to take $R_m = R_c$. Fits to T Tauri photometry sometimes suggest that the magnetosphere lies further inward of corotation (Kenyon, Yi & Hartmann 1996), but for the purpose here of illustrating the behaviour of the magnetospheric model the differences are not substantial.

Figure 2.3 shows the radial dependence of $3\pi\nu\Sigma$ predicted by equation (2.11) for disc models with $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ and $\dot{M} = 10^{-8} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$. I show three magnetically truncated models with varying assumed values for B_* , and compare those to two non-magnetic models with inner radius either at the stellar surface or at corotation. The later

model is not physically reasonable, but serves to demonstrate the relative importance of the magnetic versus non-magnetic terms in equation (2.11).

For any magnetospheric accretion model, the main effect is obviously to produce a 'hole' in the inner disc and so remove the emission that would have originated from the relatively hot inner regions. Observations would thus be most sensitive to a single parameter, R_m . However, some sensitivity to B_* can arise from differences in the profile for $\nu\Sigma$ (which determines the disc temperature) outside R_m . From the figure, it is clear that the expected magnitude of such differences depends greatly on \dot{M} . For the higher value considered ($10^{-7} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$), the predicted profiles are all very similar, implying that the disc could be modelled well as a non-magnetic system with a large value for the inner disc radius. For the lower accretion rate, conversely, the magnetic effects could be comparable to the viscous outside corotation for plausible magnetic field strengths. The field acts to inhibit accretion for $R > R_c$, and so in the steady state a greater surface density is required to sustain a given \dot{M} . This will alter the disc temperature profile, and in principle may have observable effects on the infrared colours of the disc.

2.4 Temperature distributions

The temperature profiles and spectral energy distributions for the magnetic disc models are calculated assuming that annuli in the disc radiate as blackbodies with effective temperature T_e , where

$$T_e^4 = T_\nu^4 + T_p^4 + T_B^4, \quad (2.13)$$

and the terms on the right-hand side represent respectively the contributions from active accretion, reprocessing of the stellar luminosity, and work done on the disc by the magnetic field. For a disc in which the energy from viscous dissipation is radiated locally

$$2\sigma T_\nu^4 = \frac{9}{4}\nu\Sigma\Omega^2, \quad (2.14)$$

where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. The viscous heating of the disc as a consequence of active accretion can then be obtained by combining the solutions for $\nu\Sigma$ (2.11) with equation (2.14).

The component due to reprocessing of stellar radiation is calculated from the results of Kenyon & Hartmann (1987) and Adams & Shu (1986). These authors obtain

$$T_p^4 = \frac{T_*^4}{\pi} \left[\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{R_*}{R} \right) - \left(\frac{R_*}{R} \right) \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{R_*}{R} \right)^2} \right], \quad (2.15)$$

for the case assumed here of a flat reprocessing disc.

The magnetic torques arising from field lines linking the star and the disc will also do work on the disc material, and some fraction of this may be thermalized and heat the disc material. Assuming *all* the available energy goes into heating the disc,

$$2\sigma T_B^4 = (B_* R_*^3)^2 |\Omega - \Omega_*| R^{-5}. \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.4: Disc effective temperature T_e as a function of radius for models with $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$ (left panel) and $\dot{M} = 10^{-8} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$ (right panel). The dotted line shows a non-magnetic disc with $R_{\text{inner}} = R_*(2 R_{\odot})$, the dashed line a non-magnetic disc with $R_{\text{inner}} = R_c$, and the solid lines magnetic models with $B_* = 1000$ G in the reheating and no-reheating limits. The position of corotation for $P_* = 4$ dy is shown as the dashed vertical line.

The actual fraction of the available energy that goes into reheating the disc material is unknown, and so the calculations are repeated for the two limiting cases. In the *reheating* limit, it is assumed that all the energy goes into heating the disc, so that T_B is as given above, while in the *no-reheating* limit, T_B is taken to be zero.

Figure 2.4 shows model temperature profiles for discs with accretion rates of 10^{-7} and $10^{-8} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$. The stellar component assumes a central star with an effective temperature of 4400 K and a radius $R_* = 2 R_{\odot}$. With these parameters, the bulk of the disc luminosity arises from active accretion for the higher \dot{M} models, and from reprocessing of the stellar flux for the lower \dot{M} case. The remaining inputs to the model are the stellar rotation rate, $P_* = 4$ days, and a stellar dipole field of 1 kG. For the magnetic models, R_m is assumed to lie at corotation.

The presence of the inner hole in the disc, here of radius $\sim 5 R_*$, reduces the peak temperature from close to 4000 K to around 1000 K for models with either accretion rate. This severely curtails disc emission at wavelengths shortward of a few μm . Compared to this effect, the changes caused by adopting either the reheating or no-reheating limit are modest. However, the models computed with reheating are $\sim 10 - 20\%$ warmer at their inner edges than those calculated without this heating contribution, and for low accretion rates the resulting discs can be significantly hotter just outside corotation than comparable non-magnetic discs. Note that the field strength assumed for these models is roughly what is required to regulate the stellar spin period to the observed values (see Chapter 4 for details). However, the observations do not seem to rule out significantly stronger fields of several kG in at least some systems, and for such fields the contribution

Figure 2.5: The emission from annuli in the disc at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$, $5 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$, for a variety of disc models. The upper curve in each panel shows a model of an undisturbed, non-magnetic disc; the lower curves a magnetic disc disrupted at corotation with $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ or $\dot{M} = 10^{-8} M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$. For the magnetic models, $B_{*} = 1000 \text{ G}$, $P_{*} = 4 \text{ dy}$ and reheating is assumed.

from reheating would dominate other disc heating processes. Some implications of this possibility are discussed in Chapter 3.

2.5 Spectral energy distributions

Figure 2.5 shows the emission from annuli in the disc at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$, $5 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to the temperature profiles shown in Figure 2.4. The weighting factor for the increasing area of annuli at larger radii has been included, so that this plot shows the relative contribution to the total disc emission originating from each radius. For the undisturbed disc, the Figure illustrates the radial extent of significant disc emission at each wavelength. For the $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ ('K') flux, the greater part of the emission occurs within $10 R_{\odot} = 5 R_{*}$, while at $10 \mu\text{m}$ ('N') significant emission occurs from a region $\sim 0.5 \text{ a.u.}$ in radial extent.

For the magnetically disrupted discs, the emission is reduced by significantly more than would be predicted from simply removing all the flux of the undisturbed disc that arises at $R < R_{\text{m}}$. This is due to the rollover in $\nu\Sigma$ as the inner boundary is approached. At K there is a dramatic diminution in the predicted flux of the disrupted disc as

Figure 2.6: Model system spectra (solid lines) including the contribution from the star (dashed line) and disc (dotted lines). (a) A non-magnetic disc extending to the stellar surface at $2 R_{\odot}$ with $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$. (b) A passive disc (no accretion) extending to the stellar surface. (c) A magnetic disc model with $\dot{M} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$ disrupted at corotation ($P_* = 4$ dy, $B_* = 1000$ G). (d) A passive disc disrupted at corotation with the same parameters as (c). For magnetic models both reheating (upper curves) and non-reheating limits (lower curves) are considered.

compared to the undisrupted case, with a further significant drop as \dot{M} falls and the emission begins to be dominated by the reprocessing of stellar radiation. As expected, the longer wavelengths ($\lambda \gtrsim 5 \mu\text{m}$) are much less affected by the presence of the inner hole in the disc, which implies that the level of K and L flux is a good indicator of the location of the magnetosphere if $R_m \sim 10 R_{\odot}$.

Figure 2.6 shows continuum spectra calculated for these models, including a contribution from the central star. However no allowance is made for emission from a boundary layer or accretion column – flux from these regions is mainly likely to boost the short wavelength part of the spectrum. For the magnetic models both reheating and

non-reheating limits are shown.

The following characteristics of spectra from the magnetically disrupted discs are evident from the Figure. At the higher accretion rates ($10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, as shown in the Figure, and higher), the spectra are distinctively different from the non-magnetic discs, being heavily suppressed between 1 and 3 μm but retaining similar emission to the undisrupted discs at 5 μm and beyond. This implies a flatter spectrum between these wavelengths than the undisrupted disc, which is well known to be consistent with observations. Unfortunately a number of plausible models (for example those invoking flared discs or increasing \dot{M} with R) can produce the same effect, so this is in no way a unique explanation. Moreover the flatter spectrum has been achieved mainly by depleting the shorter wavelengths, while leaving the longer wavelengths untouched.

At lower accretion rates, the important difference between the undisrupted and disrupted discs lies in the contribution of the disc to the overall flux from the system. A flat undisrupted disc that merely passively reprocesses stellar radiation intercepts 1/4 of the luminosity of the central star (Kenyon & Hartmann 1987). Furthermore the temperature of such a disc close to the stellar surface is comparable to the stellar photospheric temperature. Together, this implies that a reprocessing disc that extends down to the stellar surface contributes significantly to the flux from the system at all wavelengths longward of the peak in the stellar blackbody spectrum, and so should be easily detectable in the near infrared.

In contrast, the magnetically disrupted discs are very weak at a few μm for low or negligible accretion rates. If the full reheating limit is appropriate, significant disc emission is only seen in such circumstances at 3 μm and beyond, and this figure is increased further if little reheating occurs. Moreover, many T Tauri stars have rotation periods substantially in excess of the 4 days assumed in these calculations, and the larger holes in such systems would reduce the disc fluxes further. Passive discs around magnetically active stars are thus expected to be hard to detect at short infrared wavelengths, but could possess relatively strong emission at longer infrared and mm wavebands.

2.6 An application to dispersed T Tauri stars

In the preceding Section it has been argued that the photometric consequences of a magnetospheric accretion model are most dramatic in systems with a low accretion rate, which would appear qualitatively different as a result of having large holes in their inner discs. A possible candidate for such systems are the dispersed Weak-Lined T Tauri stars recently discovered from *ROSAT* observations of nearby star forming clouds (Alcalá 1994; Neuhaüser et al. 1995; Sterzik et al. 1995). Spectroscopic follow-up of these candidates to measure their lithium abundance has confirmed many as bona fide WTTS (Alcalá et al. 1996), and suggests that X-ray selection is an efficient method for generating statistically well-defined samples of pre-main-sequence stars. The observation that many of these candidate WTTS are far removed from known sites of active star formation provides evidence that prior studies may have missed a substantial popula-

tion of pre-main-sequence stars, and raises questions as to the origins of this dispersed population. One possibility is that a larger fraction of low-mass stars form in small, previously unrecognized groups, as suggested by Feigelson (1996) on the basis of simple kinematic models for the distribution of the dispersed stars. A more conservative option is that the dispersed stars detected by *ROSAT* were formed within known regions of star formation activity, before being ejected by dynamical interactions. In this latter scenario the observed distribution of outliers implies that a reasonable fraction of the observed WTTS must have been ejected at relatively high velocity.

In either model, the inferred ages of the outlying WTTS pose a serious problem. Placing these stars on isochrones in a Hertzsprung-Russell (HR) diagram gives derived ages of around 2 Myr (Montmerle & Casanova 1995), at which epoch many stars *within* star-forming regions are still actively accreting and appear as Classical T Tauri stars (CTTS). There are uncertainties in pre-main-sequence isochrone ages due to both the influence of accretion and the often uncertain distance determinations, but these do not seem likely to resolve the problem. The effects of accretion are most problematic for CTTS, while the distance estimates for the outlying WTTS would need to be systematically too large to explain the young ages as solely an artifact of distance errors. The lack of ongoing accretion and circumstellar material in such young systems (evidenced by the absence of a K band excess) then requires explanation, as it is not obvious that the interactions leading to ejection should inevitably remove the circumstellar material and convert CTTS rapidly into solely Weak-Lined systems. Here I consider whether a magnetospheric accretion model for stars ejected from small clusters can explain the observed presence of stars that are simultaneously young, Weak-Lined, and far removed from the main areas of star formation activity.

2.6.1 infrared excesses of magnetically disrupted discs

The parameters and mechanisms that control the transition of a star from Classical to Weak-Line status are largely unknown, but it is natural to assume that the mass accretion rate through the disc \dot{M} plays an important role. With this assumption, three mass fluxes can be defined; the accretion rate for a typical CTTS, \dot{M}_{CTTS} , the accretion rate below which a star appears as a WTTS in a non-magnetic model, $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,noB}}$, and the corresponding quantity in a magnetospheric model, $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,B}}$. The dispersed WTTS stars are classified as Weak-Lined systems on the basis of their low $H\alpha$ equivalent width (Alcalá et al. 1996), and on the lack of excess flux in the K band at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$. These same conditions can be adopted for deciding when model systems have become WTTS, and hence to estimate the values of $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,noB}}$ and $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,B}}$. These quantities are then used to estimate the timescale for the CTTS to WTTS conversion in magnetic and non-magnetic systems that suffer an ejection interaction.

Figure 2.7 shows the excess flux ΔK at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ for a range of discs around a star of mass $1 M_{\odot}$ and radius $2 R_{\odot}$. These models are computed as in the preceding Section, except that in addition to considering the case where $R_{\text{m}} = R_{\text{c}}$, I also allow the

Figure 2.7: K excesses over the stellar photosphere for a variety of accretion disc models described in the text, as a function of the steady state accretion rate through the disc. (a) A non-magnetic disc extending to the stellar surface. (b) A magnetically disrupted disc around a star of period $P_* = 4$ dy with $R_m = R_c$ (lower curve) and $R_m = 0.7 \times R_c$ (upper curve). (c) A magnetically disrupted disc around a star of period $P_* = 8$ dy with $R_m = R_c$ (lower curve) and $R_m = 0.7 \times R_c$ (upper curve). The curves for magnetic discs with $R_m = 0.7 \times R_c$ do not extend to very low \dot{M} , since at low accretion rates the magnetosphere must lie at larger radii.

possibility that R_m may lie significantly inwards of corotation. Specifically, models are computed with $R_m \approx 0.7 \times R_c$, which has some observational support (Kenyon, Yi & Hartmann 1996).

For the non-magnetic disc model, reprocessing of the stellar luminosity ensures that an easily detectable K excess is found for all accretion rates, provided only that the disc remains optically thick at K. This will be the case down to very low accretion rates. To order of magnitude, an optical depth $\tau_K = 1$ requires a disc column density $\Sigma = 0.1$ g/cm², which is at least 4 orders of magnitude below the surface density seen in CTTS disc models accreting at $10^{-7} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The accretion rate corresponding to $\Sigma = 0.1$ depends on the disc viscosity ν via $\dot{M} \sim 3\pi\nu\Sigma$, where ν is typically an increasing function of Σ . This suggests that $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,noB}}$ is likely to be more than 4 orders of magnitude below \dot{M}_{CTTS} , and that a disc around a non-magnetic T Tauri star would remain visible via its K excess long after significant accretion (evidenced by high equivalent width of $H\alpha$) had ceased.

For the magnetic models, the behaviour of ΔK as a function of \dot{M} is very different.

If $R_m = 0.7 \times R_c$, then significant K excesses of ~ 1 mag are obtained at accretion rates of $10^{-7} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$ and above for $P_* = 4$ dy, with smaller but still readily detectable ΔK values for the longer rotation period. However, once the accretion rate has fallen sufficiently low that the magnetosphere lies at corotation, the models predict that ΔK should be low. Taking as observationally determined the result that $R_m \approx 0.7 \times R_c$ in the Classical T Tauri phase, equation (2.12) predicts that the magnetosphere should lie near corotation once $\dot{M} \lesssim 0.3 \times \dot{M}_{\text{CTTS}}$. From the Figure, it can then be concluded that T Tauri systems rotating at $P_* = 8$ dy would appear as WTTS on the basis of their K excess below an accretion rate of a few $\times 10^{-8} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$. For the shorter rotation period of 4 dy, ΔK falls below 0.1 magnitudes at approximately the same \dot{M} .

These results imply that judged by the near infrared excess, a magnetic CTTS would appear indistinguishable from a WTTS at an accretion rate of $\sim 10^{-8} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$ or below. The equivalent width of $H\alpha$ in the dispersed WTTS shows considerable scatter (Alcalá et al. 1996), so accretion at approximately this level probably cannot be excluded on the basis of the $H\alpha$ measurements either. The resulting estimate is that $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,B}} \sim 10^{-8} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$, so that $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,B}} \gg \dot{M}_{\text{weak,noB}}$. It remains to show that the interactions leading to ejection of a star from a cloud would reduce \dot{M} below $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,B}}$ within the available time, and thus convert it observationally to a WTTS.

2.6.2 Conversion of Classical T Tauri stars to Weak-Lined systems

Consider an outlier at a distance d from the cluster that it was ejected from, with an inferred age, as judged from its position in the HR diagram, t_{HR} . Since the velocities of the outliers must be substantially greater than the typical cluster velocity dispersion, the velocity of the runaway star, $v_{\text{run}} \sim d/t_{\text{HR}}$, is close to its ejection velocity v_{eject} . Making use of prior work on the scattering of single stars by binaries, v_{eject} can be related to the distance of closest approach in the encounter that led to the ejection, R_{peri} , (for details see, e.g. Davies 1995). The energy lost from the binary ΔE is related to the binding energy of the binary, E_{bin} , via

$$\Delta E \lesssim 0.4 \times E_{\text{bin}} = 0.4 \times \frac{GM^2}{2d_{\text{bin}}}, \quad (2.17)$$

where d_{bin} is the separation of the binary before the encounter. Making use of the further result that $d_{\text{bin}} \approx R_{\text{peri}}$ gives,

$$v_{\text{eject}} \approx 15 \text{ km/s} \times \left(\frac{R_{\text{peri}}}{1 \text{ a.u.}} \right)^{-1/2}, \quad (2.18)$$

for stars of solar mass. The observed distances and ages imply $v_{\text{run}} = 5 - 10$ km/s, so that $R_{\text{peri}} \sim 3 - 10$ a.u.. Star-disk encounters have been extensively modelled (Hall, Clarke & Pringle 1996; Clarke & Pringle 1993), and these simulations suggest that the accretion disc following the encounter has an outer edge at $\sim R_{\text{peri}}/2$. The ejected stars would thus be expected to harbour remnant discs with outer radii $R_{\text{out}} \lesssim 5$ a.u. immediately following the interaction.

The weakened disc will then evolve *faster* as a consequence of the reduced viscous timescale t_ν at R_{out} . The viscous timescale is given by (e.g. Pringle 1981),

$$t_\nu \sim \frac{1}{\alpha\Omega} \left(\frac{R}{H} \right)^2, \quad (2.19)$$

where α is the Shakura-Sunyaev viscosity parameter, H is the disc scale height, and all quantities are evaluated at radius R . At 5 a.u.,

$$t_\nu \sim 2 \times 10^5 \text{ yr} \left(\frac{\alpha}{10^{-3}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{(H/R)_{10\text{a.u.}}}{0.1} \right)^{-2}. \quad (2.20)$$

Thus provided that $\alpha_{R=5\text{a.u.}} \gtrsim 10^{-3}$ (as is likely since even $\alpha = 10^{-3}$ implies worryingly large disc masses at this radius) and $(H/R) \gtrsim 0.1$, $t_\nu \ll t_{\text{HR}}$. The same conclusion follows by noting that unless α or (H/R) are strongly increasing functions of R beyond 5 a.u., the radial dependence of t_ν scales approximately as $\Omega^{-1} \propto R^{3/2}$. A typical T Tauri disc has a lifetime of a few Myr, which implies $t_\nu \sim 1$ Myr. Reducing R_{out} by a modest factor of ~ 5 then ensures that for the weakened disc the same result, that $t_\nu < t_{\text{HR}}$, is obtained.

The viscous timescale can be regarded as a characteristic time for the decay of the disc surface density and accretion rate. As $\dot{M}_{\text{CTTS}} \approx 10^{-7} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$, only a few viscous times will be required before \dot{M} through the truncated disc falls below $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,B}}$. Thus within the available time t_{HR} , the initially Classical T Tauri star will lose the ΔK and $H\alpha$ signatures of a CTTS, and will appear as a Weak-Lined system. In this model circumstellar material will still exist around the star, but the low accretion rate and the hole created by the stellar magnetosphere renders it undetectable in the near infrared.

Note that the same conclusion does *not* follow for non-magnetic disc models. In this scenario, the interaction reduces t_ν exactly as for the magnetic case, but a large number of viscous times are still necessary before \dot{M} falls below $\dot{M}_{\text{weak,noB}}$. Before the accretion rate falls this low, the disc will have had time to re-expand to its original extent, restoring t_ν to a much larger value. At t_{HR} the disc close to the star would still be strong enough to generate noticeable K flux via reprocessing, and the system would not appear as a WTTS.

2.7 Summary

The observations summarised in Chapter 1 suggest that in many T Tauri stars the accretion disc does not extend down to the stellar surface, but rather is disrupted by a stellar magnetosphere at a few stellar radii. This Chapter has then aimed to outline a plausible theoretical model for describing such a magnetospheric accretion flow in pre-main-sequence stars. As I have sought to emphasise repeatedly, there are a number of uncertainties inherent in constructing such a model, especially in the treatment of the interaction of the stellar magnetic field with the accretion disc. The main assumption made here is that the stellar magnetosphere can be described to a reasonable approximation as closed and dipolar at a distance of a few stellar radii from the star. With

this assumption, simple physical arguments have been used to derive equations for the evolution of the disc subjected to both viscous and magnetic torques.

A number of the most interesting consequences of this picture follow from consideration of steady state disc models, which have the considerable merit of not requiring knowledge of the form of the kinematic viscosity in the disc. The disrupted discs are colder and very markedly weaker at wavelengths of a few μm than their undisrupted counterparts, and exhibit different continuum spectra. At low accretion rates, the injection of angular momentum into the disc beyond the corotation radius can lead to a substantial 'damming up' effect that enhances the surface density in this region and increases the disc temperature. This effect will be a recurring theme in the two following Chapters.

Finally, these models have been applied to the evolution of discs around Classical T Tauri stars which are subjected to disruptive encounters within the environment of small clusters. Such systems could be the progenitors of the young dispersed WTTS detected in the *ROSAT* All-Sky Survey. The models suggest that the encounter could act to convert a CTTS into an apparently Weak-Lined system within ~ 1 Myr, provided that the stars possess magnetic fields of ~ 1 kG. The encounter leads to a rapid diminution of the accretion rate through the disc, while the magnetic field creates a hole in the inner disc that reduces the fraction of the stellar luminosity reprocessed to near infrared wavelengths by the disc. As magnetic fields of the required strength are inferred from other observations, the conclusion is that the main properties of the outlying WTTS are consistent with a dynamical ejection model.

Chapter 3

Magnetic cycles and photometric variability

3.1 Introduction

The preceding Chapter describes a magnetospheric model for accretion in T Tauri stars, in which the inner regions of the accretion disc are disrupted by a stellar magnetic field. The observable consequences of such a model include radiation arising from the accretion of matter onto the star, (mainly in the visible and ultraviolet), and infrared flux from the disc. The strength of both of these components may be expected to change if the magnetic field varies with time, and this Chapter develops the implications of such time-varying stellar fields.

Observational motivation for studying the effects of variable stellar magnetic fields comes from the long timescale variability of T Tauri stars. T Tauri stars exhibit photometric variability over a wide range of timescales, including hours (Gullbring 1994), days and weeks (Edwards et al. 1993; Bouvier et al. 1993, 1995), and years to decades (Herbst et al. 1994). Of these, the variability on timescales of days to weeks is found to be roughly periodic in many sources, although the values quoted for the periods are often still doubtful (Osterloh, Thommes & Kania 1996). This periodicity is then commonly attributed to the presence of spots on the stellar surface, in which case the photometric period is a probe of the stellar surface rotation. This is discussed in more detail in the next Chapter.

The variability on shorter (hours) and much longer (years) timescales is much less well characterized, and the processes responsible for these variations are unclear. The shortest variability is often ascribed to the presence of flaring or unstable accretion phenomena, either of which would be plausible within a model of accretion onto magnetically highly active stars.

Figure 3.1 displays two illustrative V band light curves showing the long timescale variability of the CTTS T Tau and RY Tau (data for these plots is taken from the database compiled by Herbst et al. (1994)). The figure shows both the individual photometric measurements, and (since typically many observations were made during short

Figure 3.1: Photometry of the Classical T Tauri systems T Tau (top panels) and RY Tau (lower panels), from the compilation by Herbst et al. (1994). Left panels show the individual V band photometry, right panels show the mean magnitude at each epoch of observations.

monitoring campaigns) the same data averaged at each epoch of observation. Both stars display complex variations over the approximately 30 year period spanned by the observations, with an amplitude of 0.5 to 1 magnitude in V. It must be stressed that although the Herbst et al. catalogue list light curves for many (~ 100) TTS, the examples shown in Figure 3.1 are in no way typical – most TTS have only a handful of photometric points taken prior to the last few years. However, the *amplitude* of long timescale variability shown in the figure does not seem to be atypically large when compared to the other active CTTS in the Herbst et al. database.

Timescales of years and decades are short compared with those for variations in the stellar luminosity or disc flow at large radius. Outbursts in the disc caused by thermal instabilities (FU Orionis events and lower luminosity analogues) *do* have roughly the

correct duration, but it would be unexpected if discs in most T Tauri stars proved to be susceptible to such instabilities. The timescales for magnetic variability in pre-main-sequence stars are unknown, but cycle times of years to decades are common for the magnetic activity in cool main-sequence stars (Baliunas 1988).

The evidence supporting the existence of dynamically important magnetic fields in TTS has already been discussed, and appears to be strong. How likely is it that those fields are in fact dynamo generated and variable over these time periods? As yet there appears to be no observational evidence either way, while the theoretical expectations for the nature of magnetic dynamos in pre-main-sequence stars are also uncertain. A detection of variable magnetic effects via their influence on the disc could then provide a useful new probe of the activity in these stars.

As well as modulating the disc and accretion luminosity, a variable stellar field could also induce qualitative changes in the appearance of the system. A sudden increase in the field strength might push the magnetosphere temporarily beyond corotation, thereby cutting off the accretion flow onto the star in this model. This process could lead to the interconversion of stars between WTTS and CTTS status, and would imply the existence of a population of stars that were devoid of accretion onto the star but which did still possess disc material at larger radii.

The layout of this Chapter is as follows. Section 3.2 describes the numerical method used to solve the disc surface density equation, and the parameters assumed for the calculations. Section 3.3 presents results for the location of the magnetosphere, disc luminosity and accretion rate. The implications of the results are discussed in Section 3.4.

3.2 Numerical method

3.2.1 Disc surface density evolution

With the assumptions outlined in Chapter 2, the equation for the time evolution of the disc surface density Σ is,

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} = \frac{3}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left[R^{1/2} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (\nu \Sigma R^{1/2}) \right] + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left(\frac{\Omega - \Omega_*}{\Omega} \frac{B_z^2 R^{5/2}}{\pi \sqrt{GM_*}} \right), \quad (3.1)$$

where B_z has the usual dipolar radial dependence and ν is the normal kinematic viscosity. The effect of the magnetic field is to add a second, advective term to the evolution equation, representing a magnetic torque which falls off with increasing radius, and which causes inflow inward of corotation. Beyond corotation the field acts to inject angular momentum into the disc material. A sufficiently strong field can therefore cease inflow and accretion onto the star altogether.

In order to integrate equation (3.1), the form and magnitude of the kinematic viscosity ν needs to be specified, the usual choice being the ad hoc α prescription relating the viscosity to the local disc sound speed c_s and scale height H via $\nu = \alpha c_s H$, with α a poorly known parameter (Shakura & Sunyaev 1973). With such an assumption

it is possible to solve for the vertical thermal equilibrium structure of the disc, and hence to derive the viscosity as a function of the disc variables. Two recent independent calculations of this type for T Tauri discs by Kawazoe & Mineshige (1993) and Bell & Lin (1994) are in reasonable agreement. Earlier authors (Campbell 1992) have found that the disc is disrupted shortly inward of the radius where the magnetic torque exceeds the viscous torque. Thus at the inner edge the magnetic pressure is small compared to the thermal pressure (Clarke et al. 1994), and it should be a reasonable approximation to use the results of the non magnetic structure calculations even in the magnetic regime. For input mass fluxes in the region of ($\dot{M} \sim 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$), the equilibrium curves given in Bell & Lin (1994) are well fit by a single power law in α , R and Σ , corresponding to a viscosity given approximately by,

$$\nu = 0.3\alpha^{1.05}\Sigma^{0.3}R^{1.25}, \quad (3.2)$$

which is used in equation (3.1). The value of α is highly uncertain, though arguments based on the recurrence timescales of FU Orionis outbursts (assuming these to be due to thermal instabilities in T Tauri discs) suggest a low value (Clarke et al. 1990; Kawazoe & Mineshige 1993; Bell & Lin 1994). The 'best guess' runs therefore take $\alpha = 10^{-3}$, though I also consider $\alpha = 10^{-1}$, this higher value being typical of that deduced in dwarf novae systems (e.g. Cannizzo 1993 and references therein). Empirically, the differences caused by these two disparate values of α are much greater than the uncertainties due to only taking a crude fit to the Bell & Lin (1994) curves (note that the uncertainties in the vertical structure calculations themselves are unquantified and could be large).

3.2.2 Boundary conditions

Equation (3.1) is integrated on an Eulerian radial grid evenly spaced in $R^{1/2}$, using a simple first-order explicit scheme for the diffusive term and the Leleuvier method (Potter 1973) for the magnetic torque term. These choices are adequate to reproduce well the analytic solution for the spreading of a narrow ring (with no magnetic field and $\nu = \text{constant}$, see e.g. Pringle 1981; Frank, King & Raine 1992), and the steady solutions with an imposed magnetic torque given in the previous Chapter. For most of the calculations described here the outer boundary condition is imposed at $240 R_{\odot} \sim 1 \text{ a.u.}$, this being well beyond the region where the magnetic torque has a significant effect on the disc. The simulations use 1024 grid points, and give entirely consistent results when compared to earlier calculations (Armitage 1995) that were restricted to half this resolution.

If the disc is disrupted by the field the calculation must be cut off when the advective inflow velocity exceeds some limiting value v_{max} , thereby preventing the timestep becoming arbitrarily small at the disc inner edge. The value of the parameter v_{max} is unimportant provided that it exceeds the typical viscous inflow velocity, so that the magnetic torque dominates the viscous torque well before $v_R > v_{\text{max}}$. The calculations described here use $v_{\text{max}} = 5 \times 10^5 \text{ cms}^{-1}$, so that the calculation is cut off at a radius

where the inflow velocity is first becoming roughly supersonic. This radius is defined as the magnetospheric radius R_m . Although by this radius the assumptions used to derive equation (3.1) are breaking down, the steep radial dependence of the magnetic torque suggests that a more detailed treatment of the inner disc region would not change R_m substantially.

At the outer boundary a given mass flux \dot{M}_{outer} is imposed. At the inner boundary flow is allowed through the inner edge if $R_m \leq R_c$. If $R_m > R_c$, the inner boundary condition must be set so that there is no accretion onto the star. Integrating the magnetic part of equation (3.1) with respect to R gives,

$$\int_{R_{\text{in}}}^{R_{\text{out}}} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (2\pi R \Sigma) dR = 2\pi [f(R)]_{R_{\text{in}}}^{R_{\text{out}}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where

$$f(R) = \frac{\Omega - \Omega_*}{\Omega} \frac{B_z^2 R^{5/2}}{\pi \sqrt{GM_*}}. \quad (3.4)$$

The left-hand side of equation (5.1) is $\partial M_{\text{disc}}/\partial t$, which for $R_m > R_c$ and large R_{out} must be zero when only the magnetic term is considered. This ensures that the disc mass in the computational region is conserved (note that the diffusive part is solved using a mass conserving scheme and so does not alter this condition). The steep radial dependence of B_z means that $f(R)|_{R_{\text{out}}} = 0$, and hence the correct boundary condition is obtained by setting $f(R) = 0$ at the inner edge as well. As a consequence of cutting off the calculation, the innermost zone (where v_R may exceed v_{max}) will not generally be computed correctly, and the calculated surface density may become negative. When this occurs the surface density is restored to zero, and mass is removed from the first positive zone to compensate.

The stellar mass, radius and spin rate will vary with time as a consequence both of accretion and the coupling between the star and its disc. Even without such interaction, normal pre-main-sequence evolution will lead to changes in the stellar parameters. Clarke et al. (1995) estimated that for a T Tauri star accreting at $\sim 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$, the timescale for changes in the spin period was $\sim 10^5$ years, and this is shorter than the timescales for changes in either M_* or R_* . As the magnetic field variations considered here are on timescales $\ll 10^5$ years, it suffices for these purposes to regard the stellar parameters as fixed for the duration of the calculation. Discussion of the evolution of the system over such longer ($\geq 10^5$ yr) periods is deferred until the next Chapter.

3.2.3 Parameters adopted for the runs

The stellar parameters used are intended to be representative of typical accreting T Tauri stars. The runs assume a mass $M_* = 1 M_{\odot}$, radius $R_* = 3 R_{\odot}$, with an input mass flux into the outer edge of the disc $\dot{M}_{\text{outer}} = 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$. Stellar rotation periods are in the range 4-12 days, similar to the range seen in photometric surveys of CTTs (Bouvier et al. 1993; Edwards et al. 1993). As there is no real observational or

Table 3.1: Parameters adopted for the calculations

Run	α	P_* / days	B_{dc} / G	B_{ac} / G
1	10^{-1}	12	600	300
2	10^{-3}	12	600	300
3	10^{-1}	4	1500	750
4	10^{-3}	4	1500	750
5	10^{-1}	4	3000	1500
6	10^{-3}	4	3000	1500

theoretical guidance for the time dependence of the field, a simple form is used,

$$B_* = B_{dc} + B_{ac} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_{\text{cycle}}}\right) \quad (3.5)$$

envisaging both a ‘frozen-in’ component B_{dc} with no time dependence and an oscillatory dynamo component B_{ac} , with period τ_{cycle} . The cycle times of interest observationally will have $\tau_{\text{cycle}} \sim 10$ yr, activity on this timescale appears to be common in stars surveyed as part of the Mt Wilson monitoring programme (Baliunas 1988).

The values for the parameters used in the calculations are given in Table 3.1, below I discuss these runs in detail.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Accretion rate and location of the magnetosphere

Figure 3.2 shows the time-dependence of the accretion rate \dot{M} and magnetospheric radius R_m for runs 1 and 2. These runs have a relatively weak field compared to the stellar spin period, and as a consequence the magnetosphere remains well within the corotation radius throughout the cycle (for $P_* = 12$ days, $R_c = 22 R_\odot$, which is almost twice the magnetospheric radius for this field strength). The two calculations differ only in the assumed viscosity parameter α .

For both runs, the variation in the accretion rate is very close to being in phase with that of the applied stellar magnetic field. The main difference between the two values of α is in the magnitude of variation in R_m and hence \dot{M} . For $\alpha = 10^{-1}$ the magnetospheric radius varies by around $\pm 10\%$ over the course of the cycle, whereas the corresponding variation for $\alpha = 10^{-3}$ is only $\sim \pm 1\%$ (note that this level of variation corresponds to just a few grid points and hence cannot be accurately measured at this resolution). This almost negligible change in R_m during the cycle occurs because the amount of mass accreted during the strong-field phase of the cycle is small compared to the disc mass for a low value of α . The inner edge is then constrained to sweep back and forth by only a small amount. For an estimate, we ignore viscosity (which will anyway reduce the variations in R_m by replenishing material removed by the action of the field),

Figure 3.2: Time-dependence of the accretion rate and magnetospheric radius for magnetic cycles lying within corotation. The left panels also show the variation of the stellar magnetic field (dashed lines on an arbitrary scale) to illustrate the phase. Top panels show Run 1 ($\alpha = 10^{-1}$), lower panels Run 2 ($\alpha = 10^{-3}$).

and note that the amount of mass accreted in one magnetic field cycle is $\dot{M}_{\text{mean}}\tau_{\text{cycle}}$. This must be compared to the amount of mass ΔM that is swept up in displacing R_m to $R_m + \Delta R$. Near the inner edge,

$$\Sigma \approx \Sigma_0 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{R_m}{R}}\right) \approx \frac{\Sigma_0 \Delta R}{2 R_m}, \quad (3.6)$$

for small ΔR and taking the non-magnetic profile for definiteness. Then

$$\Delta M \sim 2\pi R_m \int \Sigma dR \sim \frac{\pi \Sigma_0}{2} \Delta R^2, \quad (3.7)$$

and using $\Sigma_0 \propto \alpha^{-1}$ gives

$$\Delta R \sim \alpha^{1/2} \tau_{\text{cycle}}^{1/2} \quad (3.8)$$

Figure 3.3: The solid line shows the variation of the ratio of maximum to minimum accretion rate $f = \dot{M}_{\text{max}}/\dot{M}_{\text{min}}$ as a function of cycle time τ_{cycle} , for $\alpha = 10^{-3}$. Dotted lines show the corresponding variation in the disc bolometric luminosity in the no-reheating and full reheating limits.

for fixed \dot{M} , in agreement with the numerical results.

The variation in the accretion rate onto the star is also shown in Figure 3.2. For $\alpha = 10^{-3}$ the range of maximum to minimum accretion rate, $f = \dot{M}_{\text{max}}/\dot{M}_{\text{min}}$, is approximately a factor of eight. This is as expected given the observation that R_m is nearly constant for this value of α , since in this limit the surface density profile changes little during the cycle. Near the magnetosphere the magnetic field dominates viscosity in transporting angular momentum, and hence the accretion rate scales as the magnetic torque which is proportional to B_*^2 . Hence,

$$\frac{\dot{M}_{\text{max}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{min}}} = \left(\frac{B_{\text{max}}}{B_{\text{min}}} \right)^2, \quad (3.9)$$

and the range for the parameters of run 2 is expected to be a factor $\lesssim 9$. For $\alpha = 10^{-1}$ the larger oscillations in R_m reduce the variation in \dot{M} , but even in this case the ratio of maximum to minimum \dot{M} is roughly a factor of four.

From equation (3.8) it is apparent that the cycle time is an important parameter in determining the behaviour. To investigate this, a variety of models were computed with τ_{cycle} between 10 and 10^4 years. Long cycle periods are expected to reduce the modulation of the accretion rate, as for a very slow cycle the disc has time to adjust via viscous processes to the changing field and remains close to a steady state with

Figure 3.4: Time-dependence of the accretion rate and magnetospheric radius for magnetic cycles crossing corotation. R_c is shown in the right panels as a dashed horizontal line. The left panels also show the variation of the stellar magnetic field (dashed lines on an arbitrary scale) to illustrate the phase. Top panels show Run 5 ($\alpha = 10^{-1}$), lower panels Run 6 ($\alpha = 10^{-3}$).

$\dot{M} \approx \dot{M}_{\text{mean}}$. Figure 3.3 shows the results of varying τ_{cycle} , keeping all other parameters fixed as before, for $\alpha = 10^{-3}$. The plot shows the magnitude of variation in the accretion rate $f = \dot{M}_{\text{max}}/\dot{M}_{\text{min}}$ as the solid line. As anticipated, the modulation of accretion drops off sharply as the cycle time approaches the viscous response time of the disc (here $\sim 10^4$ yr at the outside edge). For this low value of α it is apparent that all timescales of observational interest are ‘fast’ compared to the disc timescale, and will thus yield substantial modulation similar to that described above.

Figure 3.4 shows the results for magnetic cycles where the field is strong enough to displace the magnetosphere beyond corotation during the strong field phase of the cycle. In this case accretion occurs in a series of relatively narrow pulses as the magnetospheric

Figure 3.5: Evolution of the stellar model luminosity and effective temperature.

radius moves inside corotation. Hence the minimum \dot{M} occurs when the field is strongest, which is the opposite of the behaviour for cycles remaining within the corotation radius. For both values of the viscosity parameter, \dot{M}_{\min} is essentially zero.

For $\alpha = 10^{-1}$, the fraction of the cycle for which accretion occurs is ~ 0.4 , with a peak accretion rate $\dot{M}_{\max} \approx 4 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, i.e. four times the mean accretion rate averaged over a whole cycle. Similar results are obtained for the low α run; in this instance the peak accretion rate is $\dot{M}_{\max} \approx 3 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and the duty cycle is ~ 0.6 . In general for cycles crossing corotation the details of the cycle and the value assumed for α are much less important than when the magnetosphere remains within corotation. This is because for cycles crossing the corotation radius, the qualitative behaviour is determined by the switching on and off of accretion as R_m passes R_c . Hence similar variations in accretion rate are seen both for a range of values of α and for cycles with lower amplitude magnetic field variations.

3.3.2 Disc luminosity

The bolometric luminosity and infrared flux from the disc may also be modulated by the action of a magnetic cycle. There are two possible effects at work. First, the disc emission will be modified as a result of the changing location of the magnetosphere, such that when the field is strong – and R_m is larger – the disc luminosity will be at a minimum. The strength of this modulation will depend critically on α , for a low value of 10^{-3} the results show negligible variations in R_m . Second, the work done by the

magnetic field on the disc material may go directly into heating the disc (the 'reheating' limit discussed in Chapter 2), in which case a fraction of the disc luminosity will directly depend on the strength of the imposed magnetic field. For this effect maxima in the field strength correspond also to maxima in the disc luminosity and fluxes.

Below I show plots for the variation in the disc bolometric luminosity L_{bol} , and the monochromatic fluxes at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ ('K'), $5 \mu\text{m}$ ('M'), and $10 \mu\text{m}$ ('N'), for the runs listed in Table 3.1. The calculation of the fluxes included components for the disc and star only – no contribution from reprocessing of stellar luminosity by the disc or luminosity arising from accretion is included. For representative stellar parameters, the stellar model shown in Figure 3.5 is used. This pre-main-sequence model (kindly supplied by Chris Tout) is described in more depth in the next Chapter, for the calculation of system luminosity all that is required is the effective temperature, which is taken to be 4400 K. Together with the assumed radius of $3 R_{\odot}$, this implies a stellar luminosity of $3 L_{\odot}$.

Figure 3.6 shows the results for the $\alpha = 10^{-1}$ runs 1, 3 and 5. If there is no reheating (so that only changes in R_{m} modify the emission), then the disc is weak at K and there is little variability at this wavelength (only ~ 0.05 magnitudes for the strongest field model). In this limit, the variations at M and N are similar, and increase from ~ 0.02 magnitudes for the weakest field model to ~ 0.1 magnitudes for the strongest. The model with the strongest fields shows roughly colourless variations over this wavelength range in the infrared.

If reheating is assumed, then the variations are much larger and are in phase with the stellar field oscillations. The K flux is most sensitive to the temperature at the inner edge of the disc, and hence to the strength of the applied field. The peak to trough variation increases from ~ 0.01 magnitudes for run 1 to almost 0.5 magnitudes for run 5. Significant variability, ranging from 0.1 to 0.4 magnitudes, is predicted at M and N for all these models. The amplitude of the induced variations typically peaks at around K (for the stronger field models) or M (for those with weaker fields where the disc is cooler).

Figure 3.7 shows the results for the $\alpha = 10^{-3}$ runs 2, 4, and 6. This lower value of the viscosity parameter is generally thought to be more appropriate for the inner (< 1 a.u.) regions of protostellar accretion discs. For this α , the magnetosphere remains almost static during the course of a 10 yr magnetic cycle, as shown in figures 3.2 and 3.4. This translates into negligible variations in the disc bolometric luminosity and infrared fluxes in the no reheating limit, for all three models.

In the opposite limit, where it is assumed that all the work done by the magnetic torque on the disc goes into heating the disc and is re-radiated as blackbody radiation, variability comparable but somewhat larger than the $\alpha = 10^{-1}$ runs is seen. The higher amplitude is because the movement of R_{m} in the high α runs tends to cancel out some of the variations in disc fluxes caused by reheating, and this effect is not present in the low α calculations. As before, variability at K is the strongest indicator of the magnitude of variability of the magnetic field, with ΔK increasing from ~ 0.01 magnitudes for run 2 to 0.5 magnitudes for run 6. Significant variability is also predicted at M and N , and

Figure 3.6: Summary of results for Runs 1, 3 and 5 ($\alpha = 10^{-1}$). From top downwards the panels show the accretion rate, bolometric disc luminosity, and system luminosity (disc plus star) at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$, $5 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$. The dotted curves represent the limit of no-reheating, the solid curves are for full reheating.

again as previously the infrared colour of the variability changes with the strength of the imposed magnetic cycle. Stronger fields with larger variability induce photometric variations in these infrared colours that are markedly bluer. However, this is not a rapid change, and if CTTS possess magnetic fields similar to those measured in WTTS (i.e. $1 - 2 \text{ kG}$), then order unity variations of that field would lead to comparable photometric variability across the $2 - 10 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength range.

It is also worth noting that at least for variations in the stronger fields, the changes in the disc bolometric luminosity are large. Therefore if magnetic cycles are common in CTTS, one would expect that comparison of $2 - 10 \mu\text{m}$ fluxes with longer infrared fluxes would show that very few discs fit a steady-state accretion disc model. It is well

Figure 3.7: Summary of results for Runs 2, 4 and 6 ($\alpha = 10^{-3}$). From top downwards the panels show the accretion rate, bolometric disc luminosity, and system luminosity (disc plus star) at 2.2 μm , 5 μm and 10 μm . The dotted curves represent the limit of no-reheating, the solid curves are for full reheating.

known that many systems show spectra that are flatter than simple disc predictions at mid infrared wavelengths, and this is often interpreted as implying higher \dot{M} at radii of a few a.u. in the disc than close to the star. The result from this work – that significant variability in the magnetic field could enhance \dot{M} by a factor of several at small radii – then suggests that in some systems the opposite effect of apparently higher \dot{M} at small disc radii should be observed.

3.3.3 Accretion luminosity

The likelihood that variable stellar magnetic fields would lead to significant changes in the infrared disc flux is dependent on both the disc viscosity and on the details of

the interaction of the disc with the magnetosphere. As discussed above, both of these are somewhat uncertain. More robust is the prediction that time-varying fields should modulate the accretion rate onto the star, and this should also lead to variability both in the radiation emitted where the infalling gas strikes the star (a 'hotspot'), and in the spectral lines formed further out in the infalling accretion column.

The properties of the hotspots in CTTS are subject to considerable uncertainties. Ideally, it would be useful to know both the fraction of the stellar surface occupied by the bases of accretion columns and the properties of the radiation emitted by those regions. A theoretical calculation of this would require considering stellar fields that were not aligned with the rotation axis (as the observations suggest substantial departures from axisymmetry), and would probably be of limited applicability if the flow close to the stellar surface is controlled by smaller scale fields than the dipole. Observationally, modelling of spot properties from the available broad-band photometry is complicated by the presence of many important spectral lines (Bouvier et al. 1995), since these affect the amplitude of modulation at different wavelengths. With these caveats, various authors (e.g. Vrba et al. 1993; Bouvier et al. 1993, 1995) find that the observations suggest a range of spot properties, with effective temperatures from a few hundred to a few thousand K hotter than the stellar photosphere, and projected sizes between 0.5% and 40% of the stellar surface. These observational results then imply that the effects of varying \dot{M} should be most prominent at wavelengths somewhat shorter than the peak of the stellar emission, but with substantial variability also in the well-monitored V band.

The luminosity of the model star at ages of a few $\times 10^5$ yr to a few $\times 10^6$ yr is in the range of L_{\odot} to $3 L_{\odot}$. For comparison, the luminosity from an accretion flow of $10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ falling from $R \approx 10 R_{\odot}$ to $R_{*} = 3 R_{\odot}$ is $\approx 0.75 L_{\odot}$. The amplitude of variations in \dot{M} seen in these calculations depends on the model, but for cycles within corotation \dot{M} varied between close to nothing and $\sim 2 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (with a dependence on B_{*} as given in equation (3.9)). For cycles crossing the corotation radius the modulation was around twice as large, and less dependent on the amplitude of the field variations. These cycles would then produce order unity changes in the bolometric luminosity of the star, and variability of ~ 1 magnitude at V . Larger changes might be expected in the UV, dependent on the spot properties. These estimates then suggest that variable stellar magnetic fields could drive variability comparable to that seen in the long-term photometric records of CTTS, such as that shown in Figure 3.1.

Modelling of the profiles of spectral lines suggests that the strong emission lines of T Tauri stars are commonly produced in infalling gas (Hartmann, Hewett & Calvet 1994), though the presence of winds is also required to explain absorption features. Detailed calculations of the thermal structure of the infalling accretion flow in CTTS have recently been presented (Martin 1996), and so it should be possible to determine the predicted emission in the different lines for various accretion rates. Such an analysis is however, well beyond the scope of this discussion.

3.4 Discussion

This Chapter has investigated the effects of variable stellar magnetic fields on T Tauri accretion discs in the framework of a magnetospheric accretion model for those systems. The results indicate that cyclic stellar magnetic activity can lead to various patterns of variability for the star-disc system. The most robust prediction is that cycles with periods of years to decades should strongly modulate the rate of accretion onto the central star. This is found to be the case regardless of the location of the magnetosphere relative to corotation, and for all values of the α parameter considered plausible in T Tauri discs. Observationally this translates into variability in the continuum radiation emitted in the accretion shock, and in the spectral lines believed to be formed in the infalling accretion column. The model is unable to predict the details of this emission, which for a real system will depend on the structure of the field close to the photosphere and the inclination of the magnetic and spin axes. However, by appealing to the observationally derived effective temperatures of hotspots in Classical T Tauri stars, it is possible to get some idea of the amplitude of the predicted variability. Order unity changes in the stellar field seem likely to induce variations in the V and shorter wavelength fluxes of up to about a magnitude. Variability at this level is consistent with long term photometric records for active CTTS.

For the particular case where the magnetosphere crosses the corotation radius in the course of a cycle, the accretion onto the central star occurs in pulses, corresponding to the weak field phases of the cycle. Such an accretion event is characterised by a rapid rise or fall in the apparent accretion rate, with a peak rate that can be several times larger than that found by averaging over the cycle. During the period when accretion is switched off, the star would appear to be 'weak' in terms of indicators of accretion close to the photosphere, but would still possess a reservoir of material held up by the field at a few stellar radii (Clarke et al. 1995). Such a system could revert to 'classical' status when the field weakened. This is the most clearcut demonstration of the non-steady state nature of these models. In systems with high levels of magnetic activity, the true accretion rate onto the star will not normally equal the apparent \dot{M} derived from near IR measurements of the disk, and neither will coincide with the mass inflow rate at large radii derived from far IR and mm observations.

The variability of the disc flux during the cycle depends both on the value of α and on the (unknown) details of the interaction between the disc and the magnetosphere. For the low (10^{-3}) values of α that are derived from modelling the timescales of FU Orionis outbursts, the surface density in the inner regions of the disc is high and variations of the stellar field on observable timescales lead to small changes in the location of the magnetosphere. In this case, no significant variability in the IR fluxes from the disc is expected unless a reasonable fraction of the work done by the magnetic torque on the disc goes into heating of the disc material. If this is the case, then variations of up to ~ 0.5 magnitudes at K , ~ 0.4 magnitudes at M , and ~ 0.2 magnitudes at N may occur. Note that these are not hard limits, but rather represent the peak values obtained

from a selection of models computed with plausible T Tauri parameters. The infrared colour of the variability depends on the strength of the stellar magnetic field, such that stronger fields lead to greater variability at shorter wavelengths. For fields of 1 – 2 kG, the variability would probably be close to colourless between 2 and 5 μm , with smaller variations at longer wavelengths.

It has also been suggested that a stellar magnetic field that varies by order unity may cause further variability in the star-disc system by affecting the photospheric output of the star. During the strong field phases convection may be inhibited and the star should dim (Appenzeller & Dearborn 1984). Such an effect would be most significant in systems with relatively low accretion rates, where the photospheric component is consequently strong.

The models computed here have been restricted to consideration of strictly periodic stellar magnetic behaviour, whereas analogy with the Sun might suggest a much richer array of quasiperiodic changes. Certainly the available light curves of CTTS are not well represented as sinusoids. It is thus worth emphasising that the cause of the large modulation of accretion seen in the calculations is the mismatch between the magnetic cycle timescale and that of the viscous response of the disc, which is independent of the details of the magnetic variation. Hence in any model where the disc is disrupted by a stellar field, changes in that field that occur on observationally-accessible timescales can be expected to lead to variations in the accretion rate through the inner edge of the disc.

Improved characterization of the long term photometric variability of CTTS should assist in determining the causes of the variability. Particularly valuable would be multi-wavelength observations that include both the short (UV) wavelengths that probe the innermost accretion processes, and the 2 – 10 μm wavebands characteristic of the inner accretion disc. Comparison of the long term variations in these bands with the strength of the stellar magnetic field (or, more feasibly at present, with proxies for the strength of magnetic activity) would also provide a means of testing the models presented here.

As a result of the potentially large magnitude of variability, useful constraints could be placed on the amplitude of magnetic cycles from observations of pre-main sequence stars, even given the inevitable ‘noise’ caused by the short timescale variations in these objects. If the variability is shown to be due to changing magnetic activity, then the archival data available on T Tauri stars may constitute an indirect record of such behaviour stretching back many decades. Detection of such cycles would both provide an explanation for decade scale variability in T Tauri stars, and also extend greatly the range of stellar systems in which magnetic dynamo activity may be studied.

Chapter 4

Magnetic braking of T Tauri stars

4.1 Introduction

The rotation rates of T Tauri provide an important test of the star-disc magnetic linkage models outlined in the preceding two Chapters. It is well known observationally that young low-mass stars rotate slowly, with angular velocities typically an order of magnitude below the breakup speed (see e.g. Bouvier 1991 and references therein). This observation on its own implies that the spin of T Tauri stars is efficiently regulated, as in the absence of such angular momentum loss processes the rapid contraction of the stellar radius that occurs during pre-main-sequence evolution would rapidly spin-up the star to close to the breakup velocity. Powerful stellar winds or magnetic linkage to circumstellar material are then obvious candidates for the unknown angular momentum loss mechanism. Models for the angular momentum evolution based on these alternatives have been proposed by numerous authors, (for example, Tout & Pringle 1992; Königl 1991), and it appears that either candidate can provide a viable conduit for angular momentum loss.

To test the various models further requires observations that characterize the rotation rates of stars as a function of their age and other potentially significant system parameters. These might include the mass, the presence or absence of binary companions, and the existence of discs and ongoing accretion. An important step in that direction has now been made via photometric monitoring of relatively large samples of both WTTS and CTTS (Edwards et al. 1993; Bouvier et al. 1993, 1995). These surveys have discovered periodicity in the light curves of many TTS, and this is generally interpreted as arising from the rotation of hot or cold spots on the stellar surface (though for a dissenting view, see Smith, Lewis & Bonnell 1995; Smith, Bonnell & Lewis 1995). Provided that this interpretation is correct for at least the majority of the surveyed stars, the measured photometric periods provide a direct probe of the rotation periods that is free of the inclination effects that afflict the complementary $v \sin i$ measurements.

Figure 4.1 illustrates the distribution of photometric periods found in the COY-

Figure 4.1: Distributions of photometric periods (upper panel) and $v \sin(i)$ (lower panel) for CTTS (solid histogram) and WTTS (dashed histogram) from the COYOTES II sample of Bouvier et al.

OTES II compilation of T Tauri stars in Taurus-Auriga (data for this plot are taken from Table 3 of Bouvier et al. 1995). Although there is some overlap in the distributions, it is clear that the Classical T Tauri stars rotate *slower* as a class (mean period $\bar{P}_* = 7$ days) than the Weak-Lined systems ($\bar{P}_* = 4$ days). The same distinction is seen, albeit less clearly, in the corresponding $v \sin i$ distributions.

Before commenting on this result, it should be noted that what is being measured in these surveys is *not* the same for both WTTS and CTTS. In the former case, the photometric modulation appears to be due to cool spots analogous to sunspots, while for the CTTS there is strong evidence in at least some instances for the presence of spots hotter than the stellar photosphere. In a magnetospheric accretion model these hotspots could arise at the base of accretion columns. There is no reason to suppose that the cool spots in WTTS have the same distribution with latitude as the hotspots in CTTS, and thus it has been suggested that the apparent difference in rotation periods might be an artifact of stellar differential rotation (Smith M. D. 1994). Recent high resolution spectroscopic studies of 3 TTS have explored this possibility, and are consistent with solid body rotation (Johns-Krull 1996). In particular these observations rule out differential rotation at the level required in the Smith (1994) model, and thus suggest that the apparent distinction between WTTS and CTTS is real and requires explanation.

The presence of disc accretion in TTS is generally believed to lead to the accretion

of angular momentum and hence faster stellar rotation (the intriguing suggestion of Popham [1996], that this may not be true at the high accretion rates seen in FU Orionis outbursts is unlikely to affect this unless TTS are susceptible to outbursts for a much longer period than is normally assumed). The contrary observation that CTTS in fact spin slower than WTTS is then puzzling, and suggests that angular momentum loss in these systems is more efficient in those systems possessing discs. Since a model in which the star is linked magnetically to its disc directly associates angular momentum loss to the presence of disc accretion, it is an attractive possibility to investigate the rotational evolution of stars within magnetospheric accretion scenarios.

A number of authors have modelled the evolution of stellar rotation rates using such a model (Cameron & Campbell 1993; Yi 1994; Ghosh 1995; Cameron, Campbell & Quaintrell 1995). Although their assumed magnetic field configurations differ widely, these authors concur that a dipole magnetic field of a few $\times 100 - 1000$ G can regulate the stellar spin to the observed values. These results are promising but also preliminary, since in these studies it is assumed that the evolution of the disc can be treated as independent from that of the star. In particular, these authors assume that the accretion rate onto the star, \dot{M} , can be prescribed as a function of time, and have then calculated the steady state magnetospheric radius based on \dot{M} and the stellar parameters.

This Chapter relaxes that assumption, and presents models that use a time-dependent disc code to follow the evolution of the disc in response to the combined effects of internal viscous and stellar magnetic torques. This permits a consistent treatment of the regime where the magnetospheric radius lies beyond corotation – in this regime accretion is cut off and no steady state solution for R_m exists. The influence of close binary companions on the stellar spin is also investigated using the model. It is well known that in *very* close systems (with orbital periods of \sim a few days) tidal effects can induce synchronous rotation between the orbital and spin periods (Tassoul & Tassoul 1992). The resulting spin periods would be faster than average for CTTS and most WTTS. Recent X-ray studies of the Hyades cluster (in which the X-ray flux is believed to be an indicator of stellar rotation) demonstrate that stars in binaries have greater X-ray luminosities than similar single stars, with the strongest effect at the small separations where tidal synchronization would be expected to operate (Pye et al. 1994; Stern, Schmitt & Kahabka 1995). Here I explore whether wider binaries, with separations of a few a.u., can exert a less direct influence on stellar rotation via tidal truncation of the accretion disc. This may modify the disc lifetime and so change the efficacy of magnetic disc braking. Finally I investigate the influence that the epoch of disc dispersal (for example by stellar winds), has on the predicted rotation periods in this model.

The plan of the Chapter is as follows. In Section 4.2 I describe the modifications made to the time-dependent code used in Chapter 3 to follow the evolution of the stellar rotation. Section 4.3 summarises the initial conditions used, while Sections 4.4 and 4.5 describe the general evolution of the system in this model. Sections 4.6 and 4.7 show the results for single stars and binary systems respectively, and Section 4.8 summarizes the conclusions of this work.

Figure 4.2: Evolution of the stellar radius R_* and squared radius of gyration k^2 for the 0.9985 M_\odot stellar model.

4.2 Description of the model

The main assumptions leading to the derivation of the disc surface density evolution equation (2.10) have been discussed in the preceding Chapter. Here, I describe the stellar model used in the spin calculations, together with the boundary conditions and other modifications required to model single and binary systems. The procedure used to mimic the process of disc dispersal is also outlined.

4.2.1 Stellar model

The stellar model used is a 0.9985 M_\odot model calculated using the most recent version of the Eggleton code (Pols et al. 1995), as modified for pre-main-sequence evolution by Tout (private communication). The spin calculations require only the time-dependence of the stellar radius R_* and moment of inertia $I_* = k^2 M_* R_*^2$, where k is the dimensionless radius of gyration. The evolution of R_* and k^2 for the model star is shown in Figure 4.2. The star contracts from approximately $5 R_\odot$ to $1 R_\odot$ in the course of $\approx 3 \times 10^7$ yr, implying a decrease in I_* by a factor of ~ 25 as a result of contraction. A further factor of two decrease in I_* is due to the changing internal structure of the star. While the star is completely convective k^2 remains nearly constant at $k^2 \approx 0.2$, a value that declines between 10^7 yr and 3×10^7 yr to ≈ 0.1 as a radiative core develops. This change in structure may be important in understanding the rapid spin of older stars

approaching the main-sequence.

The magnetic torques that lead to spin-down are applied to the star at the surface and at high latitude. Differential rotation may then occur at varying depths and latitudes, depending on the efficiency of angular momentum transport within the star. The strong magnetic fields within these stars will assist in enforcing rigid rotation, and the observational evidence points to insignificant differential rotation at least in latitude (Johns-Krull 1996). Making the simple assumption of solid body rotation throughout the star at angular velocity Ω_* , the equation for the spin evolution is then

$$\frac{d\Omega_*}{dt} = \frac{1}{I_*} \left(T - \Omega_* \frac{dI_*}{dt} \right), \quad (4.1)$$

where T is the net external torque on the star, comprising both a magnetic linkage contribution T_{mag} and a torque due to accretion of disc matter T_{acc} . Integrating equation (2.4) from the inner edge of the disc at R_m to infinity gives an expression for the magnetic torque on the star due to linkage to the disc,

$$T_{\text{mag}} = \frac{\mu^2}{3} \left(R_m^{-3} - 2R_c^{-3/2} R_m^{-3/2} \right), \quad (4.2)$$

where R_c is the corotation radius $R_c = (GM_*/\Omega_*^2)^{1/3}$. The magnetic linkage will therefore lead to a spin-down torque on the star if the magnetospheric radius is large enough relative to the corotation radius,

$$\left(\frac{R_m}{R_c} \right) > 2^{-2/3} \approx 0.63. \quad (4.3)$$

The accretion torque T_{acc} is given by the product of the accretion rate onto the star and the specific angular momentum of disc material at the inner edge of the disc. Strictly, the inner edge of the disc will correspond to that radius where the magnetic torques have enforced corotation of disc matter with the star, so that the spin-up torque due to accretion is $\dot{M} R_m^2 \Omega_*$. Numerically, however, this form cannot be used, as the code assumes Keplerian disc rotation and does not resolve the narrow region of the disc where departures from Keplerian rotation occur. As an alternative, R_m is defined to be the radius of the first computational zone with non-zero surface density (where Keplerian rotation still exists), and the accretion torque is calculated from,

$$T_{\text{acc}} = \dot{M} R_m^2 \Omega, \quad (4.4)$$

using the Keplerian value for Ω at radius R_m . As the magnetic field drives strong inflow through R_m , essentially all the angular momentum of disc matter passing this radius will be transferred to the star. Hence, although the balance between T_{mag} and T_{acc} will be different, this method will give the correct net torque T exerted on the star.

The stellar dipole field is assumed to be generated via a dynamo mechanism, with a simple linear form for the scaling of the stellar surface field with rotation rate. Specifically I take

$$B_* = B_0 \left(\frac{P}{4 \text{ days}} \right)^{-1} \quad (4.5)$$

with B_0 the normalisation for a stellar spin period P of 4 days. This is the form expected for a dynamo that scales with the Rossby number, except that effects due to changes in the convective turnover time during the pre-main-sequence are not included (Gilliland 1986).

4.2.2 Numerical method and boundary conditions

The disc evolution equation (2.10) is integrated on an Eulerian radial grid as described in Chapter 3. To follow the spin evolution the net stellar torque T and dI_*/dt are calculated at each timestep. The latter is given by,

$$\frac{dI_*}{dt} = M_* \frac{d}{dt} (k^2 R_*^2) + \dot{M} k^2 R_*^2, \quad (4.6)$$

where the first term on the right-hand side is calculated using cubic spline interpolation from the tabulated stellar model output. The accretion rate is therefore incorporated into the calculation of dI_*/dt and used to update M_* , though in every other regard coupling between the accretion process and the stellar model is ignored. In particular, no allowance is made for adiabatic shrinkage of the star as a consequence of accretion, an effect that would be important at high accretion rates. Accordingly, the calculations commence at relatively low accretion rates, where the assumption that the stellar evolution proceeds independently from the accretion should be valid.

At the inner boundary free flow is allowed through the inner edge if $R_m < R_c$. If $R_m > R_c$ the boundary condition is set to enforce no accretion onto the star, as described previously. For the simulations of discs around single stars the surface density Σ is set to zero at the outer disc boundary R_{out} , this corresponds to a ‘no-torque’ boundary condition and allows free flow of mass across the outer edge.

For binaries, the systems that are of most interest have separations of a few a.u., these systems being comfortably wider than those in which tidal synchronization is important. On the main-sequence, binaries of this separation typically have low ($e \sim 0.3$ or less) eccentricity (Duquennoy & Mayor 1991). I assume that this is also broadly correct for the pre-main-sequence binaries that are considered here. The influence of the companion on the accretion disc will then be twofold. Firstly, the disc will be truncated (at a radius typically $\sim 0.4 \times$ the pericentre distance, R_{peri}), with further infall most probably accumulating in a circumbinary, rather than circumstellar, disc. Second, the companion acts to remove angular momentum from the outer regions of the disc, thereby preventing the disc swelling beyond the truncation radius.

To represent these effects, the binary runs are set up with a disc extending out only as far as $0.4 \times R_{peri}$. The tidal influence of the companion is modelled by setting the radial velocity at the outer disc edge to zero. This ‘brick-wall’ boundary condition is the same as that typically employed in dwarf nova disc modelling.

4.2.3 Disc evolution and dispersal

The physical processes that may lead to the dispersal of discs and circumstellar material are poorly understood. Stellar winds, outflows from the disc itself, and the action of a stellar magnetic field may all play a role in eventually removing the disc material. In a magnetic braking model that depends on the presence of a disc, however, it is clear that the lifetime of the disc is likely to be an important consideration. Discs that are destroyed at a relatively early stage will be unable to brake the stellar rotation – such systems will spin up at later times to become rapid rotators. Conversely, weak discs that are able to survive close to the star may exert a controlling influence on the stellar spin throughout the pre-main-sequence phase.

To investigate the importance of these effects, two sets of models have been run. In the first, it is assumed that the only process that leads to dispersal of the disc is magnetic linkage with the star. As is shown later, in some circumstances the magnetic torques act to inject sufficient angular momentum into the inner disc to expel the disc material from the vicinity of the star completely. These models typically exhibit quite long disc lifetimes, at the end of which the disc surface density is quite low. In the second set of models, it is assumed that some other (unspecified) process acts to disperse the disc once it becomes sufficiently weak. As a crude prescription for this, *all* disc material is removed once the disc mass falls below some critical value M_{\min} . A variety of values of M_{\min} are used, all of them lower than the typically inferred values for the disc mass in T Tauri systems.

4.3 Initial conditions

At the start of each run the model star has a radius $R = 5R_{\odot}$, and this time is taken as $t = 0$. As I have argued earlier, neither the regime where the accretion rate is so high that it influences the stellar evolution, nor that where the star accretes a substantial fraction of its mass during the course of the calculation, can be modelled correctly using this approach. The initial disc profile is therefore set up as a steady state non-magnetic disc, with a viscous accretion rate that is constant with radius and set at the relatively low level of $\dot{M} = 10^{-7}M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. To avoid a sudden burst of accretion as the magnetic field clears out the inner regions at the start of a run, the disc inner edge is initially set just beyond corotation. The disc surface density profile is extended outward until either the total disc mass equals a specified M_{disc} , or the outer boundary is reached. At larger radii there is initially no mass, and no mass infall onto the disc is assumed.

The disc parameters for a run are then the radius of the outer boundary (typically ~ 20 a.u.), the type of boundary condition to be imposed there, the initial disc mass M_{disc} , and the critical value for dispersal M_{\min} where appropriate. In addition there are the stellar parameters, namely the normalisation in the dynamo relation B_0 and the initial spin period P_{*}^{initial} . Table 4.1 list the values used for the calculations described below.

Table 4.1: Parameters adopted for the calculations

Run	$R_{\text{out}}/\text{a.u.}$	Boundary condition	$P_*^{\text{initial}}/\text{dy}$	B_0 / G	$M_{\text{disc}}/M_{\odot}$	M_{min}/M_{\odot}
A1	10	single	2	1500	0.1	n/a
A2	10	single	4	1500	0.1	n/a
A3	10	single	8	1500	0.1	n/a
A4	10	single	16	1500	0.1	n/a
A5	10	single	32	1500	0.1	n/a
B1	10	single	8	0	0.1	n/a
B2	10	single	8	600	0.1	n/a
B3	10	single	8	1200	0.1	n/a
B4	10	single	8	1800	0.1	n/a
C1	20	single	8	1500	0.1	n/a
C2	20	single	8	1500	3×10^{-2}	n/a
C3	20	single	8	1500	10^{-2}	n/a
C4	20	single	8	1500	3×10^{-3}	n/a
C5	20	single	8	1500	10^{-3}	n/a
D1	20	single	8	1500	0.1	10^{-3}
D2	20	single	8	1500	0.1	10^{-4}
D3	20	single	8	1500	0.1	10^{-5}
E1	0.4	binary	8	1500	9×10^{-4}	n/a
E2	0.8	binary	8	1500	3×10^{-3}	n/a
E3	1.6	binary	8	1500	7×10^{-3}	n/a
E4	3.2	binary	8	1500	1.5×10^{-2}	n/a
F1	0.4	binary	8	1500	9×10^{-4}	10^{-5}
F2	0.8	binary	8	1500	3×10^{-3}	10^{-5}
F3	1.6	binary	8	1500	7×10^{-3}	10^{-5}
F4	3.2	binary	8	1500	1.5×10^{-2}	10^{-5}

4.4 Convergence to a ‘zero-torque’ spin period

Previous authors have argued that magnetic braking acts to bring the star to a quasi-equilibrium spin period, in which the net torque from disc linkage and accretion is small. Runs A1–A5 investigate the timescale on which this quasi-equilibrium is achieved. Figure 4.3 shows the effect of magnetic linkage on models with differing initial rotation periods (2–32 days). The same disc surface density profile (with an inner edge set just beyond R_c for the slowest rotating model) was used for all the runs. The slow rotators have initially weak fields and hence spin-up rapidly, while conversely the rapid rotators experience immediate magnetic braking as a result of their strong fields. All models

Figure 4.3: The evolution of rotation period for models with differing initial rotation period, here taken in the range 2-32 dy.

are brought to a common rotation period (here 7-8 days) on a timescale of $\sim 10^5$ yr. This agrees well with analytic estimates of the magnetic braking timescale (Clarke et al. 1995).

This timescale is significant in two respects. Firstly, as the lifetime of CTTS is much greater than 10^5 yr, it implies that provided magnetic braking is operating the system rapidly loses any ‘memory’ of its initial angular momentum. The remaining runs can thus be computed assuming an arbitrary initial spin period (8 days), and this choice will not control the later evolution. Second, it is relatively *long* compared to, for example, the expected intervals between FU Orionis outbursts in some models (Bell & Lin 1994). In the absence of other spin-down mechanisms the earliest stages of disc accretion (where \dot{M} is high enough to overwhelm the stellar field) might well lead to rapid rotation. The timescale of 10^5 yr for magnetic braking then implies that we *would* expect to observe some rapidly rotating CTTS spinning down from that early phase. During interoutburst T Tauri stars susceptible to FU Orionis events would likewise be expected to spin relatively rapidly.

4.5 Disc clearing and the CTTS \rightarrow WTTS transition

The evolution of the disc surface density profile with time for model C1 is shown in Figure 4.4, with profiles plotted at equal time intervals of 2×10^6 yr. The qualitative

Figure 4.4: Evolution of the disc surface density profile for the model with $M_{\text{disc}} = 0.1M_{\odot}$, and outer boundary at 20 a.u. Curves are plotted at intervals of 2×10^6 yr, from $2 \times 10^6 - 3 \times 10^7$ yr.

behaviour displayed by this model is typical of all the models computed with the $\Sigma = 0$ outer boundary condition. The most striking result is that the magnetospheric radius remains approximately constant and close to the corotation radius for the first 8×10^6 yr. This is despite the fact that the accretion rate falls off rapidly, decreasing by an order of magnitude on a timescale of $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ yr. The magnetospheric radius remains at corotation even at low accretion rates because more matter can flow in from larger radii to ‘reinforce’ the disc and overcome the magnetic torques. This continues until the disc becomes globally weak, so that there is no longer sufficient mass at large radii. After this time, the field acts to expel the disc material, and pushes R_m rapidly outwards from corotation.

The parameter that controls the strength of the magnetic braking is B_0 , the normalisation constant in the dynamo relation. Ideally perhaps this could be fixed from the measured fields and rotation rates of WTTS (Basri, Marcy & Valenti 1992; Guenther & Emerson 1995, 1996). As the dynamo prescription employed here is undoubtedly oversimplified, B_0 is instead treated as a free parameter and adjusted so that the models match the observed rotation rates of CTTS. The results of such a calculation are shown as Figure 4.5, in which the stellar spin is plotted at various ages as a function of B_0 (models B1–B4). For completeness a $B_0 = 0$ model is also shown, although by the latest times shown in the figure this model had spun up to break-up velocity and so was not being modelled correctly. At the first three isochrones shown ($t \leq 3 \times 10^6$ yr) the models

Figure 4.5: Stellar spin period at different ages, calculated as a function of the parameter B_0 . From top to bottom, lines are plotted at 3×10^5 , 10^6 , 3×10^6 , 10^7 , and 3×10^7 yr. For the first three ages the model stars would appear as CTTS, the older models would appear as WTTS.

were all accreting, and so those systems would appear as CTTS. From the figure, it can be seen that to reproduce CTTS' rotation periods of ~ 7 days requires $B_0 \approx 1500$ G, and this value is adopted in all subsequent calculations. Pre-empting somewhat the later discussion, it can be noted immediately that with this choice of B_0 , the spin period at later times ($10^7 - 3 \times 10^7$ yr) lies in the 2-5 day range, similar to typical WTTS. At these epochs the models have indeed ceased accreting, and so would appear as weak-lined systems.

4.6 Spin evolution for single stars

4.6.1 Models without disc clearing

The time-dependence of the stellar rotation period is shown in Figure 4.6 for models C1-C5, which differ only in the initial disc mass. The highest mass disc has $M_{\text{disc}} = 0.1 M_{\odot}$, while the lowest mass disc has $M_{\text{disc}} = 10^{-3} M_{\odot}$. All four models with the highest disc masses display similar behaviour. While the magnetosphere is close to corotation the rotation period is regulated in the range between 6 and 10 days. During this period the model stars are accreting, and thus would appear to be CTTS (at least as regards IR excess – the accretion rate itself is very low in the latter half of this phase).

Figure 4.6: Time-dependence of the stellar spin period for models computed with different initial disc masses. In all cases the outer boundary was appropriate for a ‘single’ star and was set at 20 a.u. From top downwards at $t = 10^6$ yr the curves represent $M_{\text{disc}} = 3 \times 10^{-3}$, 10^{-2} , 3×10^{-2} , 10^{-1} and $10^{-3} M_{\odot}$ respectively.

Amongst these four models the systems with the more massive discs rotate faster while they are CTTS, this is because higher disc mass implies a larger \dot{M} and thus a larger accretion torque. These models all expel their discs shortly before 10^7 yr, after this they spin-up by approximately a factor of two due to their vestigial stellar evolution. In common with previous authors (Cameron, Campbell & Quaintrell 1995), the results show that the final stellar rotation period is independent of the initial disc mass provided that it is high enough for magnetic braking to operate. The systems with the highest disc masses initially spin up more due to accretion, but this is compensated by longer disc lifetime (and hence a prolonged time over which braking can occur).

For the lowest mass disc the behaviour is different. In this case the magnetic torques expel the disc material to large radii almost immediately, from where it is unable to brake the star effectively. The star then spins up as it evolves along its pre-main-sequence track. For such systems the assumed initial spin period is important, and indeed determines the spin at all later stages in the absence of any alternative braking mechanism. However, for any reasonable initial spin the large decrease in I_* (approximately a factor of 50 for this stellar model) will ensure that systems with such low disc masses will become rapid rotators. As very little matter is accreted, they would appear as WTTS from an early epoch. The critical disc mass for this to occur is obviously a

Figure 4.7: Time-dependence of the stellar spin period for models computed with differing values of the minimum disc mass M_{\min} . In all cases the outer boundary was appropriate for a ‘single’ star and was set at 20 a.u. From top downwards at the final epoch the curves represent $M_{\min} = 0, 10^{-5}, 10^{-4},$ and $10^{-3}M_{\odot}$ respectively.

function of α and the assumed viscosity in the disc – for the parameters assumed here it is $\sim 10^{-3}M_{\odot}$.

4.6.2 Models incorporating disc clearing

In the single star models discussed above, the magnetic torques act to push the magnetosphere beyond corotation only at a relatively late epoch (~ 10 Myr). This is significantly longer than most estimates of the disc lifetime in CTTS. The disc lifetime in the model could easily be shortened (for example by increasing the viscosity at large radii where observational constraints are weak), but this would simultaneously lead to an implausibly *short* decay timescale for the accretion rate. It is therefore worth investigating models in which the removal of circumstellar material close to the star occurs via other, non-magnetic, processes.

Figure 4.7 compares run C1 with three runs (D1–D3) in which the disc is dispersed when its mass falls below a critical threshold M_{\min} . M_{\min} is taken in the range between $10^{-5} M_{\odot}$ and $10^{-3} M_{\odot}$. Taking $M_{\min} = 10^{-3} M_{\odot}$ cuts-off the magnetic braking at $t \sim 2$ Myr, while assuming $M_{\min} = 10^{-4} M_{\odot}$ implies a disc lifetime with these initial conditions of around 6 Myr. The final spin periods of these models are close to 1

and 2 days respectively. The lowest value experimented with for M_{\min} is too small to significantly affect the evolution of the rotation period or disc lifetime.

4.6.3 Uncertainties in the models

The most important uncertainties in these calculations probably arise from the choice of viscosity prescription (3.2). This was derived for CTTS mass fluxes at small (< 1 a.u.) radii, and even if it is an accurate description there it will fail at large radii in the disc, where the temperatures and opacities are very different. To explore how sensitive the results are to the form of the viscosity, I have computed models in which the power-law form of equation (3.2) is modified beyond a given radius (typically 1 a.u.). The general behaviour shown in Figure 4.6 (i.e. the shape of the curves and the dichotomy between high and low disc masses) persists in these alternative models. However, the timescale for the disc to be expelled, and thus the final spin period, does vary substantially. Assuming a higher viscosity in the outer disc leads to higher accretion rates and shorter disc lifetime, both of which imply faster rotation. Conversely, lower viscosity at large radii produces more braking.

A weak observational constraint on the viscosity for the whole disc can be inferred from the apparent lifetime of the accreting CTT phase, often taken to be a few Myr. This is consistent with the ~ 1 Myr decay timescale for \dot{M} that arises in these simulations. However it is clear that with our current knowledge of disc viscosity it is not possible to predict in detail the CTTS and WTTS spin distribution. Nevertheless, the results show that magnetic braking via star-disc linkage is a robust mechanism in that it will produce distributions similar to those observed provided only that the disc lifetime in T Tauri stars is 5-10 Myr. In particular, it would operate successfully even if some other effect, perhaps stellar winds, dissipated the disc at the end of the CTTS phase.

4.7 Spin evolution for binary stars

4.7.1 Models without disc clearing

For the runs intended to mimic binary systems, the disc is again set up to produce an initial accretion rate of $10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with an inner hole just larger than R_c . In this case, though, the disc profile extends out only as far as $R_{\text{out}} = 0.4 \times R_{\text{peri}}$, the binary pericentre distance. This is the radius at which the disc is tidally truncated by the binary companion. The boundary condition at the outer edge is set to enforce zero radial velocity.

Figure 4.8 shows the results of models E1-E4, for binaries with pericentre separations in the range 1-8 a.u. As for single stars, magnetic braking is effective in maintaining the stellar rotation rate in the 7-10 day range for the few Myr duration of the CTT phase. The differences between the models are due to the larger disc masses in the wider binaries. The wider systems are able to maintain a relatively high accretion rate for longer than the close systems, and as a result they have shorter equilibrium spin periods.

Figure 4.8: Time-dependence of the stellar spin period for models computed with an outer boundary condition appropriate to a binary system. From top downwards the models assume $R_{\text{peri}} = 1, 2, 4,$ and 8 a.u.

Although there are detailed differences due to the boundary conditions, the general behaviour of the binary models is very similar to that of the single stars up to a time of $\sim 10^7$ yr. We would therefore expect similar rotation rates in CTTS, whether they were single or members of a binary system. After 10^7 yr, however, there is an obvious distinction between the binary and single star models. Whereas the single star models expel their inner discs and spin up, the binary models *retain* mass just outside corotation. This continues to provide magnetic braking, and as the accretion torque falls off with time the models actually begin to spin down. They never achieve WTTS rotation periods, although the accretion rate is negligible in these models after the first few Myr.

The continuing spin down of the binary models is evidently due to these stars being unable to expel their inner discs, and this in turn is a consequence of the tidal effects of the companion. The companion is able to extract an arbitrary amount of angular momentum from the disc material, which can therefore remain at small radii despite the continual injection of angular momentum from the action of magnetic torques. The disc is effectively an intermediary in a continuing transfer of angular momentum from the spin of the primary, via the disc, to the orbit of the secondary.

Figure 4.9: The effect of imposing a minimum disc mass on the time-dependence of the stellar spin period in the binary case. The solid curves reproduce the results for $R_{\text{peri}} = 2$ and 8 a.u. with no disc clearing, the dashed curves show the effect of imposing a minimum disc mass of $10^{-5} M_{\odot}$.

4.7.2 Models incorporating disc clearing

Figure 4.9 compares the results of runs E2 and E4 (already described) with the corresponding runs F2 and F4 in which a critical minimum disc mass is imposed. The value of M_{min} in both cases is set to be $10^{-5} M_{\odot}$. As for the single star runs, this leads to a divergence in the predicted evolution at late times, and a disc lifetime that depends on the initial disc properties.

With the very simple prescription for disc clearing that is used here, the results suggest that setting $M_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5} M_{\odot}$ would reduce the disc lifetime to ~ 6 Myr for the closer (2 a.u.) binary. This leads to substantially faster spin of the model star at the end of the calculation. For the wider (8 a.u.) binary the effects are much more modest, because in this case the disc remains above the critical mass until late in the calculation (note however that M_{min} is here defined globally – a criterion for disc clearing based on Σ at small radii would reduce the differences between the models).

4.7.3 Summary of predictions for binary stars

As will be obvious by now, determination of the predicted final rotation rates of magnetically braked binaries is by no means straightforward. Commencing with the

shortest period systems, binaries with periods of a few days are expected to be synchronized by direct star-star tidal interaction. These will appear as rapid rotators compared to the mean CTT or WTT spin periods. Somewhat wider systems, where the *entire* disc is able to be cleared by the magnetic torques, should also lose their braking mechanism and spin up to be rapid rotators. The condition for this is that the binary disc truncation radius lies inside corotation, so that the magnetic torques drive rapid inflow across the whole surface of the disc. For a typical CTT rotation period of 8 days, this effect will persist up to pericentre distances of ≈ 0.2 a.u.

For wider binaries of separation up to a few a.u., the rotational evolution is highly dependent on the lifetime of the disc. During the first few Myr, while accretion is occurring at observationally detectable levels, all the models display slow rotation periods that are similar to those found in the single star models. There is a marginal effect favouring slower rotation during the CTTS phase for these binaries, because the truncated disc leads to lower \dot{M} and hence a smaller contribution from the accretion torque.

Differences between single and binary stars are however predicted at later epochs. For the single stars, a consistent model is possible in which the disc material is eventually expelled to large radius by the action of the magnetic torques alone. No such model is possible for close binaries. Rather a trapped ring of material between R_m and R_{out} continues to pass angular momentum from the star, via the disc, to the binary companion. The predicted spin during the WTTS phase then depends on when this trapped material is dispersed, after which time magnetic braking by this mechanism ceases. If the residual disc material can survive for $\sim 10^7$ yr, then binaries could be found with spin periods much greater than typical WTTS.

Finally, for sufficiently wide binaries, rotation rates comparable to single stars are expected, as a result of the outer disc's characteristic timescale being so long that the inner disc is effectively unaware of the outer boundary at all. For a very crude estimate of the radius where this final transition occurs, note that the disc thermal timescale ($\alpha^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$) reaches 1 Myr at around 100 a.u. The viscous timescale, which can safely be taken to exceed the thermal by a substantial factor, is thus likely to be greater than any other timescale in the system by this radius in the disc. This suggests that binaries of separation $\sim 10^2$ a.u. or greater should have rotation rates similar to single stars.

4.8 Summary and observational tests of the models

This Chapter has presented models for the braking of T Tauri stars in which the accretion disc is disrupted by an ordered stellar magnetic field. These models differ from those of previous authors in that they do not assume a steady state configuration for the disc, but instead allow it to evolve in response to viscous and magnetic torques. Compared to earlier work the magnetospheric radius remains close to corotation for longer, because as the accretion rate drops matter flows in from a large radius to reinforce the inner disc and maintain the inner edge at corotation. This implies that magnetic braking might continue in some systems where the diagnostics of accretion (such as UV

Figure 4.10: Summary of the final (at $t = 3 \times 10^7$ yr spin periods for all the models discussed. (a) P_{final} as a function of initial disc mass, assuming no disc clearing and an outer boundary appropriate to single stars. (b) P_{final} as a function of the minimum disc mass, for single star models computed with an initial disc mass of $0.1 M_{\odot}$. (c) P_{final} as a function of binary pericentre distance for the binary runs without disc clearing. (d) P_{final} as a function of binary pericentre distance, here assuming a minimum disc mass of $10^{-5} M_{\odot}$.

excess) were too weak to be observed. Such systems would still possess weak IR excesses and emission at mm wavelengths, though as remarked by Bouvier (1991) the discs in such systems would be optically thin at relatively small radii. The prediction that (at least in the absence of other angular momentum loss mechanisms) $R_m \approx R_c$ for many low accretion rate systems also implies that *changes* in the stellar field could readily displace the magnetosphere temporarily beyond corotation. These evolutionary calculations then offer some theoretical support for the variability models discussed in Chapter 3.

These models require the parameter B_0 to be around 1500 G in order to reproduce

the observed spin periods of T Tauri stars. This implies that the relatively slowly (~ 7 days) rotating CTTS should possess surface magnetic field strengths of 500-1000 G. This estimate must be regarded as uncertain as a result of the approximate treatment of the twisted magnetic field, however it does not appear unreasonably high given the measured kG strength fields in WTTS. More troubling is the fact that efficient star-disc braking of CTTS requires a field that generates significant torque beyond the corotation radius, at radii $R \gtrsim 10R_{\odot}$. In practice this necessitates a magnetic field that has a strong dipolar component. Some support for the existence of such fields is provided by VLBI observations of HD 283447 (Feigelson et al. 1994), which indicate the presence of large-scale, ordered magnetic fields in that source.

The mechanism described here appears to operate successfully in braking stars with a wide range of disc masses, provided that the mass exceeds some critical value. Lower mass discs in single stars are rapidly expelled by the magnetic torques, producing a runaway effect and rapid stellar spin. A population of rapid rotators is observed in young clusters such as α Persei (Keppens, MacGregor & Charbonneau 1995), these stars could therefore have been produced from systems in which disc braking was ineffective.

In terms of the distinction between Classical and Weak-lined T Tauri stars, this work supports a twin-track model of their evolution. In this picture, some WTTS are old CTTS that have expelled their discs and are spinning up as a result of their stellar evolution—in particular the reduction in the moment of inertia when a radiative core develops. Such stars would have undergone a prolonged (5-10 Myr) disc phase. The remaining WTTS would not be simply post-CTTS, but would instead be systems which had weak discs either initially or as consequence of disruptive collisions at an early epoch. These WTTS could be young, as is suggested by the intermingling of the classes on the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram. As they spun up, they would form the rapidly rotating tail of the WTTS spin distribution.

The observational correlation of stellar rotation rates with binarity offers the prospect of further testing the magnetic disc braking model. Two distinct regimes are predicted. Short period binaries (separations up to a few tenths of an a.u.) should clear away their discs entirely and spin up to rapid rotation rates. This may already have been seen indirectly in the X-ray observations of Stern, Schmitt & Kahabka (1995). In wider binaries, with separations of a few a.u., the theoretical expectation is less clear. In these systems, the disc cannot be expelled via the action of magnetic torques, which raises the intriguing possibility of a ring of gas and dust trapped between the corotation and binary truncation radii. The material in the ring would be unable to flow inwards due to the magnetic torques near corotation, while the tidal torques from the binary companion would prevent outflow. Ongoing braking would then lead to slow stellar rotation in the WTTS phase (see Figure 4.10, which plots the final stellar spin period for all the models discussed here). If, conversely, such residual discs are rapidly destroyed, for example by stellar winds, then the simulations suggest spin periods more typical of WTTS, but with a strong dependence on binary separation.

This work suggests a number of observational routes towards testing the ideas out-

lined in this Chapter. Clearly direct investigations of the correlations between rotation rates and stellar ages, binarity, and disc strength are the most valuable, and this will become possible as photometric periods for larger samples of stars are determined. Less direct measures of the rotation period from X-ray flux measurements or $v \sin i$ determinations are observationally easier, and should also be valuable, especially in intermediate age clusters and where binarity of the stars is known.

Chapter 5

A dynamo model for dwarf nova outbursts

5.1 Introduction

The dwarf novae, a subset of the cataclysmic variables, offer the best conditions in which to study the uncertain physics of accretion discs. This is a consequence both of their origin in binary systems (allowing determination of many of the important parameters of the system, and, in fortuitous examples, observation of eclipses), and the fact that most of the disc luminosity is radiated at accessible wavelengths. Equally importantly, the repeated outbursts seen in these systems, which typically last a few days, permit the exploration of the disc's time-dependent behaviour.

The disc instability model is able to account for many, but not all, of the properties of dwarf nova outbursts. In particular, the X-ray fluxes of the quiescent disc and the observed delay of the UV flux relative to the optical on the rise to outburst remain problematic (Livio 1994). A more fundamental worry is that such models require that the Shakura-Sunyaev α viscosity parameter be different in outburst and in quiescence, typically by a factor of three or more. Although there is no reason why α should *not* take this (or, indeed, any other) functional form, the *ad hoc* nature of the requirement illustrates clearly the limitations imposed by our ignorance of the mechanism that gives rise to the disc viscosity.

The possibility that small-scale magnetic fields might provide a mechanism for angular momentum transfer in discs was recognized by Shakura & Sunyaev (1973). More recently, mechanisms that might generate and sustain such fields by the action of a magnetic dynamo in the disc have been proposed by various authors (e.g. Balbus & Hawley 1991, 1992; Tout & Pringle 1992; Brandenburg et al. 1995). In the Tout & Pringle scenario, dynamo action occurs as a consequence of shear, reconnection, and the Balbus-Hawley and Parker instabilities. A merit of such a model is that it relies only on physical processes that are well-established, although much further study is required to clarify their detailed combined operation in the context of accretion discs. This, together with the fact that the model does not require any pre-existing turbulence in the disc for

its operation, suggests that such a dynamo is a promising candidate for the origin of the elusive viscosity.

In this Chapter the consequences of a magnetic dynamo origin for the viscosity in dwarf nova discs are explored. A time-dependent disc code is described and used to demonstrate that a modified disc instability model can reproduce the basic properties of dwarf nova outbursts. In the model, rapid cooling at the end of an outburst acts to inhibit the Balbus-Hawley instability and quenches dynamo action. The disc remains in a quiescent state, with strong fields (relative to the thermal energy) and very low viscosity until sufficient mass has been added to restart the dynamo at the outer disc edge. The observational consequences of this model are described, along with more generic predictions of a dynamo origin for the disc viscosity.

The plan of this Chapter is as follows. Section 5.2 outlines the aspects of the dynamo model that are relevant for this work, and how periodic outbursts can be generated within the model. Section 5.3 describes the time-dependent disc code, and in Section 5.4 model outburst calculations are presented. Section 5.5 discusses further observational consequences of the model.

5.2 The dynamo model

The ingredients required to sustain a magnetic dynamo in a disc are differential rotation (to generate azimuthal field from radial), and some mechanism that regenerates radial field from azimuthal, thereby closing the feedback loop. The first step is straightforward—in a disc rotating with Keplerian angular velocity, shear creates azimuthal field from radial on a dynamical timescale—but the second is more problematic. Stellar type dynamos that rely on convective motions to close the cycle are unattractive, as many astrophysical discs are expected to be stable against convection. Mechanisms that rely on pre-existing turbulent disc flows are similarly unappealing, as no purely hydrodynamic instability has been shown to exist in accretion discs.

In the Tout & Pringle (1992) dynamo cycle, the crucial step of regenerating radial field is accomplished by the Balbus-Hawley instability. This is a linear, local instability that exists in rotating flows threaded by an arbitrarily weak vertical field, for which $d\Omega^2/dR < 0$, conditions satisfied in discs (Balbus & Hawley 1991, 1992; Hawley & Balbus 1991, 1992). The dynamo cycle then involves shear (to create azimuthal field from radial); the Parker instability (to turn azimuthal field into vertical); and the Balbus-Hawley instability (to create radial field from vertical). Reconnection of opposite sign patches of vertical field near the disc surface provides a dissipative mechanism, and limits the growth of B_z . More recently it has been proposed that instabilities in the azimuthal field might lead directly to regeneration of the radial field, without requiring the intermediate action of the Parker instability (Ogilvie & Pringle 1996; Terquem & Papaloizou 1996). In either scenario, essentially magnetic instabilities in the vertical or azimuthal field seem to offer great promise for constructing a viable, dynamo driven, accretion disc model.

Numerical simulations show, unsurprisingly, that the magnetic fields generated by the interplay of these processes are extremely complex, both spatially and temporally (Hawley, Gammie & Balbus 1995; Stone & Norman 1994; Brandenburg et al. 1995). However, working in terms of local quantities B_R , B_ϕ and B_Z (which one hopes can be regarded as appropriate spatial averages of the actual fields), it is possible to make estimates of the rates of the various instabilities and so to investigate semi-quantitatively the dynamo action (Tout & Pringle 1992). Such models are undoubtedly oversimplified. However, the results do imply that a magnetic dynamo of this type could produce a Shakura-Sunyaev 'alpha' parameter in the 0.1–1 range typically inferred to exist in dwarf nova disc. The fields, and hence also the equivalent Shakura-Sunyaev 'alpha' parameter, $\alpha_{SS} = (B_R B_\phi / 4\pi \rho C_s^2)$, where ρ is the density and C_s the sound speed, exhibit periodic oscillations. The timescale for these is $\sim 10\Omega^{-1}$, i.e. an order of magnitude slower than the dynamical timescale of the disc and comparable to the thermal timescale $t_{th} \sim \alpha^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$. This motivates consideration of a model in which the cooling at the end of an outburst may be sufficiently rapid that the dynamo is thrown out of equilibrium. The sound speed and disc scale height drop rapidly, leaving behind a strong vertical field that is unable to decay as promptly. The growth rate of the Balbus-Hawley instability is *zero* if,

$$B_Z^2 > \frac{24}{\pi} \rho C_s^2. \quad (5.1)$$

Thus, rapid cooling can shut off the instability, and the turbulent motions generated by it, entirely. Although the vertical field exterior to the disc may now pinch off and escape, the reconnection and decay of the field actually threading the disc material is liable to be slow, because there is no longer dynamo generated turbulence to stir up the disc and push field regions of opposite sign together. The disc may then enter into a prolonged quiescent state, with strong but stable vertical fields and very low viscosity. This phase is ended only when sufficient mass (and energy) has been added at the outer edge to violate the inequality of equation (5.1) and allow the Balbus-Hawley instability to restart. There is then the potential for a global limit cycle in which the disc switches between active (high viscosity), and quiescent dynamo states. If the active dynamo is able to generate an effective $\alpha \sim 0.1-0.3$, as suggested by the results of Tout & Pringle (1992), then such a limit cycle leads to outbursts of the type seen in dwarf nova systems.

It is worth noting at this stage that in addition to the poorly understood physics of the functioning dynamo, the structure of the quiescent, strongly magnetised disc is also highly uncertain. A disc in which the Balbus-Hawley instability is inhibited will cool during inter-outburst to a state where the thermal contribution to the energy and pressure is small compared to the magnetic contribution. It has been suggested that such a disc might break-up into separate magnetised blobs (Pringle 1981) whose collisions would be cushioned by the strong fields. Such a disc, like the continuous fluid disc envisaged above, would have a low apparent α , but in other observable aspects (eg cooling time) would differ considerably. Speculating further, one can imagine that during the long period of quiescence, the dynamo fields, which when generated will be small

scale (of order the disc scale height), might reconnect in the disc corona to produce a more ordered global field (Tout & Pringle 1996). The disc could then drive a magnetic wind that would both carry material out of the disc plane and remove angular momentum from the inner disc. Accretion of 'cold' disc material could then occur even in the absence of any significant viscosity, leaving an almost evacuated hole in the inner disc. It is not clear how to model these processes quantitatively, and so for the models presented here the quiescent disc is treated as continuous and devoid of a wind. However, as discussed in section 5.5, more radical ideas of this type do show promise in explaining some of the puzzles thrown up by observations of dwarf novae.

5.3 The disc model

The global evolution of the disc is followed using a one-dimensional vertically averaged disc code. The evolution of the surface density Σ is described by the combined equation for mass and angular momentum conservation,

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} = \frac{3}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left[R^{1/2} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (\nu \Sigma R^{1/2}) \right], \quad (5.2)$$

where the kinematic viscosity $\nu = \alpha C_S^2 / \Omega$. The disc central temperature T is described via an energy equation in the form,

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{2(Q_+ - Q_-)}{C_V \Sigma} - v_R \frac{\partial T}{\partial R} + (\Gamma_3 - 1) \frac{T}{\Sigma} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} + (\Gamma_3 - 1) \frac{T}{\Sigma} v_R \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial R}. \quad (5.3)$$

Here C_V is the specific heat capacity at constant volume and Γ_3 is the third adiabatic exponent. In the first term on the right hand side, Q_+ and Q_- represent the effects of viscous heating and radiative cooling from the disc surfaces, given by

$$Q_+ = \beta \nu \Sigma \Omega^2 + \sigma T_{\text{floor}}^4, \quad (5.4)$$

$$Q_- = \sigma T_e^4, \quad (5.5)$$

where T_e is the effective temperature of the disc surface and σ the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. The parameter $\beta = (9/8)$ if all the energy dissipated goes into local heating of the disc. For simplicity this value is assumed in the calculations, though β could take a lower value as a consequence of energy being injected into a disc corona or as kinetic energy in a wind. The term $\sigma T_{\text{floor}}^4$ is included to prevent the disc from ever cooling below some background temperature, and represents crudely external heating of the disc from the white dwarf and secondary star. The second term represents advection of heat due to the radial flow at velocity

$$v_R = -\frac{3}{\Sigma R^{1/2}} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} (\nu \Sigma R^{1/2}), \quad (5.6)$$

while the remaining two terms account for the energy change from PdV work. This equation does not include terms for radial radiative diffusion or non-local transport of energy from the turbulence associated with the viscosity, as have been incorporated

in some other studies (e.g. Cannizzo 1993; Faulkner, Lin & Papaloizou 1983). The omission of these terms alters the outburst behaviour, but is not likely to change the general characteristics of the outbursts (Cannizzo 1993).

Previous studies (Mineshige 1988) have found that the sharp increase in C_V associated with the ionization of hydrogen (at $T \sim 10^4 K$) makes a significant difference in dwarf nova models, by slowing the transition to the upper state. This effect is included, using the analytic expression for the heat capacity at constant pressure, C_P , given in Cannizzo (1993),

$$\frac{C_P(\rho, T)}{\mathcal{R}/\mu} = 2.7 + Ae^{-(\log T - \log T_0)^2/w^2}, \quad (5.7)$$

where μ is the mean molecular weight, \mathcal{R} is the gas constant, $A = 26 - 7(\log \rho + 7)$, $\log T_0 = 4.1 + 0.07(\log \rho + 7)$, and $w = 0.115 + 0.015(\log \rho + 7)$. This gives a good fit over the relevant density range to numerical calculations. The specific heat capacity at constant volume is then given by $C_V = C_P - \mathcal{R}$.

For the hot state, the effective temperature T_e is related to the central temperature T by utilising the expressions given by Cannizzo (1993), which are based on vertically averaged Shakura-Sunyaev type scalings. For a disc around a star of mass $M_1 = M_*/M_\odot$,

$$T_e = 3.5 \times 10^4 M_1^{-1/8} R_{10}^{3/8} \Sigma_2^{-1/2} \mu^{-1/8} T_5^2 K, \quad (5.8)$$

where $R_{10} = R/10^{10} \text{cm}$, $\Sigma_2 = \Sigma/100 \text{gcm}^{-2}$, and $T_5 = T/10^5 \text{K}$. A hot state as defined by this power law (equation 8) exists down to a minimum surface density

$$\Sigma_{\min} = 8.25 R_{10}^{1.05} M_1^{-0.35} \alpha^{-0.8} \text{gcm}^{-2}, \quad (5.9)$$

where α is the value appropriate to the high state of the disc.

When a zone in the disc is *not* in outburst, equation (5.8) will certainly fail to provide an accurate representation of the T - T_e scaling. Many authors have of course made detailed calculations of the low state vertical structure, but these are equally unsatisfactory, because the quiescent state envisaged here is entirely different from that normally assumed, being out of thermal equilibrium and dominated by strong magnetic fields. In the absence of a consistent model for this regime, the simplest choice is then to use equation (5.8) throughout the cycle, thereby effectively ignoring the complexities of the low state altogether. This is wrong for two distinct reasons. First, it means that the cooling of the quiescent disc is modelled inaccurately, and therefore it is appropriate to treat details of the T_e profiles in the low state with caution. The robust prediction—that in the absence of viscosity T_e will rapidly cool below the temperatures seen in standard models—is however preserved by using this prescription. Second, it ignores the possible existence of a low branch that would provide a stable low state when the dynamo is first restarted. This would provide an additional delay to the transition back to the hot state, over and above that provided by the requirement that inequality (5.1) be violated. As shown later, the models do not *require* such an additional delay to produce well separated outbursts. If it were present, however, limit cycle behaviour would persist, albeit with

differences in the recurrence time and accretion rate of outbursts from those presented here.

Mass is added to the outer edge of the disc at a rate \dot{M}_{outer} , and with specific angular momentum corresponding to a Keplerian orbit at radius R_h . Following the method used by Cannizzo (1993), the mass flux from the secondary is added in a Gaussian distribution centred at R_h , with width ΔR_h . The mass added is assumed to have zero magnetic flux and the same temperature as the material at the outer edge of the disc. It may be noted, however, that in this model any variations in the magnetic flux of the stream material (e.g. due to magnetic cycles on the secondary) could directly influence the triggering of outbursts by altering the flux in the outermost regions of the disc. As has been discussed by other authors (e.g. Meyer-Hofmeister, Vogt & Meyer 1996), the field of the secondary may also play a role in dwarf novae by threading the disc and removing angular momentum.

For the magnetic field evolution a straightforward approach is adopted. When averaged azimuthally, it is assumed that the dynamo produces a viscosity that can be represented by a constant value of α . The vertical magnetic field is then given approximately by the value at which the growth of the Balbus-Hawley instability is curtailed,

$$B_Z^2 = \frac{24}{\pi} \rho C_s^2. \quad (5.10)$$

When the dynamo is operating in a given zone, the value of B_Z in that zone is set to this value at each timestep according to the local values of the density and sound speed. The dynamo is switched off in a zone when the surface density Σ falls below the minimum value for the hot branch Σ_{min} as given by equation (5.9). When this occurs, the value of B_Z is ‘frozen’ and α is set to an arbitrary low value (typically 10^{-4} , which for numerical reasons is preferable to actually taking zero). The dynamo is restarted when the density and sound speed have increased to the level where inequality (5.1) is violated, and α is reset to its high value.

The numerical method is as described by Pringle, Verbunt & Wade (1986). The disc between R_{in} and R_{out} is divided into N zones evenly spaced in \sqrt{R} . The boundary condition at the inner edge is that $\Sigma(R_{\text{in}}) = 0$, and at the outer edge that $v_R = 0$. The disc evolution equations (5.2) and (5.3) are integrated using an explicit first-order scheme, with the advective terms being treated using Lelevier (‘upwind’) differencing (Potter 1973). The calculations described here use $N = 100$. Previous authors have argued that this should be sufficient to resolve the transition front adequately (Cannizzo 1993; Lin, Papaloizou & Faulkner 1985).

5.4 Model outburst calculation

Given the present uncertainties in the model set out in Sections 5.2 and 5.3, it would be premature to attempt to match observations of a specific system. The aim of this work is rather to demonstrate that with a plausible choice of parameters, outbursts similar to

Figure 5.1: Log of the accretion rate (gs^{-1}) through the inner edge of the disc plotted as a function of time (days), obtained after a long run.

those observed can be generated, and to discuss the general differences from the standard picture expected in a magnetic dynamo driven model. The calculations use as system parameters a white dwarf of radius (equal to the inner disc radius) $R_{\text{in}} = 10^9 \text{cm}$, with a mass $M_* = 0.8M_{\odot}$. The outer edge of the disc is at $R_{\text{out}} = 3 \times 10^{10} \text{cm}$, $R_h = 2.6 \times 10^{10} \text{cm}$, and $\Delta R_h = 4 \times 10^9 \text{cm}$. Mass is added to the disc at a constant rate $\dot{M} = 10^{16} \text{gs}^{-1}$. The model is run until quasi-steady limit cycle behaviour is obtained.

For the internal model parameters, the Shakura-Sunyaev viscosity parameter in the high state is assumed to be $\alpha = 0.25$. The high state α controls the duration of outbursts in the usual manner. Additionally $T_{\text{floor}} = 10^2 \text{K}$ (though in practice the disc remains well above this temperature throughout the cycle), $\mu = 0.615$, and $\Gamma_3 = 5/3$.

5.4.1 Properties of Model Outbursts

Figures 5.1 and 5.2 show the accretion rate onto the white dwarf and the luminosity of the system as a function of time for a calculation with the above parameters. As can be seen from the Figures, the system undergoes outbursts, with a variable recurrence time of 5–10 days. Each individual outburst lasts for 3–5 days, with a rise to maximum of approximately 1 day. The strongest outbursts have a maximum accretion rate of approximately 10^{17}gs^{-1} , with a decay from maximum that is faster than exponential. The accretion rate during the quiescent phase is $\dot{M} \approx 10^{11} \text{gs}^{-1}$, and is determined

Figure 5.2: Plot of log disc luminosity (ergs^{-1}) as a function of time (days), corresponding to the outbursts shown in Figure 5.1. The disc luminosity is calculated from integrating the local luminosity across the disc surface, plus the contribution from the bright spot. The boundary layer luminosity is not included.

entirely by the arbitrary value of α in the low phase. The accretion rate onto the central object can be taken as a measure of the boundary layer luminosity. Also shown is the bolometric luminosity of the disc, which includes a contribution from the bright spot where the incoming stream strikes the outer edge of the disc. This permits an estimate of the magnitude of the outbursts from an observational point of view (cf. Pringle, Verbunt & Wade 1986). For the parameters of this run the bright spot luminosity is estimated at $\sim 10^{31} \text{ergs}^{-1}$. During interoutburst, the luminosity from passive cooling in the disc is typically at least an order of magnitude below this, so that the quiescent disc luminosity is dominated by the bright spot. The general appearance of these outbursts is very similar to those obtained from standard non-magnetic models (e.g. Cannizzo 1993; Ichikawa & Osaki 1992).

To illustrate the principal difference of this model from the standard ones, *viz.* the lack of a lower branch to the 'S-curve', Figure 5.3 plots the path traced out in the $\log(\Sigma/\text{gcm}^{-2})$ - $\log(T_e/\text{K})$ plane by a single annulus in the disc, here at a radius $R = 2 \times 10^9 \text{cm}$. Points are plotted over the course of two outburst cycles. The cycle begins with a cold quiescent disc cooling at constant surface density below 1000K (labelled as 1 in Figure 5.3). As the outburst commences dynamo action resumes in the next zone out (2). Mass and energy are then advected into the annulus, increasing Σ and heating it

Figure 5.3: Path traced out in the $\log(\Sigma/\text{gcm}^{-2}) - \log(T_e/\text{K})$ plane by an annulus at $R = 2 \times 10^9 \text{cm}$. Points are plotted at 50s intervals during the rise to the hot branch, and at $5 \times 10^3 \text{s}$ intervals subsequently. The numeric labels refer to significant points in the cycle described in the text.

up until inequality (1) is violated and dynamo action is restarted (3). The annulus then climbs rapidly to join the hot branch (4), after which it continues to heat up, reaching a peak temperature (5) that depends on the strength of the outburst (shown in the Figure are two fairly small outbursts). The annulus then remains on the hot branch until Σ falls below Σ_{\min} (6), at which point the outburst for this zone comes to an end. The dynamo switches off and the annulus resumes cooling, though until the neighbouring zone on the inside also becomes quiescent, mass and energy continue to be advected in. This can cause the dynamo to switch on again briefly until the neighbouring zones have also become quiescent; after which the zone whose evolution is being tracked just cools at constant Σ . The value of Σ in quiescence is then approximately Σ_{\min} at the radius of that zone, though the presence of advection into a zone after the dynamo there has switched off means it can be somewhat higher. This is shown in the Figure, where it can be seen that the second outburst cycle has a higher frozen value of the surface density than the first.

Figure 5.4: The evolution of the disc surface density profile. (a) On the rise to outburst and (b) on the decline. Curves show (Σ/gcm^{-2}) snapshots taken at 2×10^4 s intervals on the rise, and at 10^5 s intervals on the decline. The numeric labels identify curves according to the position of the inner disc zones in the $\log(\Sigma/\text{gcm}^{-2}) - \log(T_e/\text{K})$ plane (Figure 5.3).

5.4.2 The Disc in Quiescence and in Outburst

Figures 5.4–5.6 show the radial variations of the surface density, the vertical magnetic field and the effective temperature during the rise to outburst and during the return to quiescence. Curves which correspond to significant points in the cycle for a zone in the inner disc are labelled to correspond with Figure 5.3; (1) the quiescent disc, (2) when the heating wave reaches the inner disc, (5) the peak of the outburst, and (6) when the dynamo is about to switch off in the innermost zones. In quiescence the lack of viscosity means that the surface density profile is strongly weighted to large radii. The fraction of the disc mass accreted during outburst is $\sim 2\%$ for the small outbursts and $\sim 10\%$ for the larger events. Throughout the cycle most of the mass in the disc remains at large radii (Figure 5.4).

During quiescence the frozen magnetic field B_z reaches a few $\times 10^3$ G at all radii in the disc. Substantially stronger fields are obtained during outburst, with a maximum value of ~ 30 kG being attained near the white dwarf at the peak of the outburst (Figure 5.5). The fields in quiescence are lower because the disc cools substantially below its peak values before the dynamo ceases operation. Note that as the surface density in the inner disc remains essentially fixed in quiescence, outbursts are forced to

Figure 5.5: The evolution of the vertical component of the magnetic field. (a) On the rise to outburst and (b) on the decline. Curves show (B_z/G) snapshots taken at 2×10^4 s intervals on the rise, and at 10^5 s intervals on the decline. The numeric labels identify curves according to the position of the inner disc zones in the $\log(\Sigma/g\text{cm}^{-2}) - \log(T_e/K)$ plane (Figure 5.3).

start from the outer edge and propagate in. This is in contrast to the standard model where either inside-out or outside-in outbursts may occur, depending primarily on the mass addition rate (Ichikawa & Osaki 1993).

Figure 5.6 shows the run of the disc effective temperature as a function of time. During outburst the values of a few $\times 10^4$ K are similar to those obtained by other authors (eg Cannizzo 1993) for the inner disc regions. This is not surprising since here the parameters have been chosen to give similar accretion rates, principally by using the same upper (hot) branch of the S-curve. During quiescence the temperatures are a factor of 2–3 lower, due to the lack of internal heating. Indeed in quiescence in these models the temperature profile is essentially flat with radius. This appears to be a consequence of two competing effects—the higher surface density at large radii leads to a longer cooling time, but this is compensated by the fact that during outburst the inner regions of the disc are heated to a much higher temperature. This result should be treated with caution however, since the cooling properties of the quiescent disc have only been modelled in an approximate manner (Section 5.3).

Figure 5.6: The evolution of the disc effective temperature. (a) On the rise to outburst and (b) on the decline. Curves show $\log(T_e/K)$ snapshots taken at 2×10^4 s intervals on the rise, and at 10^5 s intervals on the decline. The numeric labels identify curves according to the position of the inner disc zones in the $\log(\Sigma/\text{gcm}^{-2}) - \log(T_e/K)$ plane (Figure 5.3).

5.5 Observational consequences of a disc dynamo

The previous sections have outlined a model for dwarf nova outbursts based on a magnetic dynamo origin for the disc viscosity. In this model, the low viscosity at quiescence is a direct consequence of the quenching of dynamo action in a rapidly cooling disc. This, in turn, is due to the fact that as the sound speed drops, while the magnetic field does not decay (or does not do so as rapidly), the disc becomes stable to the Balbus-Hawley instability, which is a crucial ingredient to field generation in the dynamo. The resultant model is able to reproduce the periodic outbursts that are the most distinctive feature of these systems. This section seeks to point out further observational consequences of the model, with particular reference to the fact that in this model the transport of angular momentum in the disc is dynamo dominated.

An immediate consequence of the model is that, at least in the absence of a disc wind, which is in principle capable of giving rise to angular momentum loss, the accretion rate during quiescence should be very low and emission from a boundary layer largely absent. Regardless of whether a wind exists or not, the inner parts of the disc are expected to be much cooler than in the standard case, leading to a much reduced UV flux from the central regions of the accretion disc. This deficit of UV emission from the

central areas is consistent with HST observations of IP Peg discussed by Horne (1994). A further prediction of the models (Figure 5.6) is that during quiescence the effective temperature of the disc is essentially constant with radius (although with the caveat that the input physics for this part of the calculation is rather approximate). Even so, it is worth noting that observations of the dwarf novae OY Car and Z Cha in quiescence (Wood et al. 1986; 1989), show flat radial temperature profiles. It is also found that in quiescence the mass transfer rate in OY Car appears to be two orders of magnitude smaller in the inner disc than near the disc edge, suggesting a very low viscosity in the quiescent state.

During outburst, the accretion rate and other properties are similar to those predicted by the standard models. However, one might expect to observe flickering in the UV emission as a result of the fluctuating nature of the dynamo process, at least in those systems where the disc reaches the white dwarf surface. To estimate this effect, note that the typical scale of dynamo generated fields is $\sim 2H$, the disc thickness. At the inner edge of the disc during outburst, the ratio of the disc scale height to the radius (H/R) is a few $\times 10^{-2}$, and so there will be $\sim 10 - 10^2$ separate dynamo 'cells' at the inner edge of the disc. In each cell the effective viscosity fluctuates on a timescale that is longer than the local thermal timescale, implying that luminosity changes at the $\leq 10\%$ level, arising from Poisson fluctuations in average dynamo activity and accretion rate, may be observable during outburst.

When the dynamo is operating, the potential energy of the disc material is being dissipated via expulsion of flux loops from the disc, followed by reconnection in the more tenuous atmosphere above the disc surface. The field strengths involved are of order 10kG, and cover the entire disc surface. This suggests observational consequences such as chromospheric lines of species such as Ca II and Mg II that are being powered non-radiatively by Alfvén waves and reconnection events, together with an extensive disc corona at temperatures of $10^{6-7} K$ that emits in the X-ray region of the spectrum. Recent ASCA observations of SS Cygni in an anomalous outburst (Nousek et al. 1994) do seem to detect emission that cannot be explained by simple boundary layer models, and this could be due to a coronal X-ray component at intermediate temperatures. Similarly, it should be noted that recent models for AGN discs also suggest that most of the energy dissipation occurs in a corona at low optical depth, and that this corona in turn irradiates the disc (Zycki et al. 1994, and references therein). The general prospects of detecting the kind of anisotropic turbulence one would associate with a dynamo model of this sort, through observing changes in the profiles of double peaked emission lines, were discussed recently by Horne (1994).

During quiescence, the magnetic field actually threading the disc matter is frozen. However, the strong fields 'left behind' when the disc scale height collapses at the end of an outburst can still power a lower level of coronal activity, and perhaps drive a wind. For the magnetic field strengths and disc volumes of the model presented earlier, the total magnetic energy available in these fields is approximately 10^{35-36} erg. During quiescence this energy may be released in the form of X-ray flares as large loops of flux are formed

and interact in the coronal regions. The relevant velocity in such a corona is the Alfvén speed, and so one might expect to see spectral lines broadened to velocities much greater than expected on the basis of the sound speed. The prominent Fe absorption lines seen in OY Car (Horne 1994) show turbulent broadening characteristic of a Mach number of order 10.

The possibility of a magnetic wind in at least some systems is a further attractive speculation. Such a wind would both carry disc matter through the line of sight far from the disc plane, and act to remove angular momentum from the inner disc and deplete the surface density. Most theoretical attempts to reproduce the observed delay of the UV flux relative to the optical on the rise to outburst are based on creating just such a ‘hole’ in the inner disc, typically either by white dwarf magnetic fields or the action of a ‘siphon flow’ that clears the inner disc (e.g. Livio & Pringle 1992; Meyer & Meyer-Hofmeister 1994). A magnetic wind that predominantly depleted the innermost disc region of matter would act in a similar, but potentially more dramatic way to these mechanisms.

To conclude, dynamo driven accretion discs appear to offer for the first time a physical model for angular momentum transport. The present work opens up the possibility that dwarf nova eruptions, one of the most dramatic manifestations of disc instabilities, can be incorporated into the context of dynamo driven discs.

Chapter 6

The stream-disc impact in interacting binaries

6.1 Introduction

Accretion discs in interacting binaries are unlikely to have simple axisymmetric structures. In these systems, the accretion disc is fed with material from a companion star via an accretion stream that originates at the inner Lagrange point. In this picture, both the gravitational influence of the companion and the impact of the stream with the disc provide mechanisms that may distort the shape and vertical structure of the accretion disc. Modeling of these deviations from axial symmetry requires the use of two and three dimensional hydrodynamic models, and is necessary in order to interpret a variety of observations of cataclysmic variables (CVs), low-mass X-ray binaries (LMXBs) and supersoft x-ray sources (SSS).

The X-ray light curves of nearly edge-on LMXBs provide one observational clue to the existence of non-axisymmetric disc structures. The eclipses are typically broad, with a gradual ingress that commences well before the phase of first contact (e.g. White et al. 1994). In some sources ('dipping' sources), most notably X1822-371, there is an actual dip in the flux at an orbital phase near 0.8. This absorption has been interpreted as arising from a bulge in the height of the disc rim at that phase (White & Holt 1982; Mason 1989 and references therein), which is suggestively similar to the location at which the accretion stream would impact the disc edge. X-ray observations of GK Persei (Hellier & Livio 1994) and EUVE observations of CVs (Warren, Sirk & Vallergera 1995; Long et al. 1996) provide further evidence for observational signatures of the accretion stream and its interaction with the disc.

Two dimensional calculations of accretion disc structure have primarily been used to investigate the formation of the disc and its response to the tidal field of the companion (Lin & Pringle 1976; Whitehurst 1988a,b; Lubow 1991; Murray 1996). Using a variety of particle-based numerical schemes, these studies show that for systems with a low mass ratio of secondary to primary ($q \lesssim 0.25$), the accretion disc is tidally unstable, leading to the formation of an eccentric precessing disc. Proper consideration of the effect of the

accretion stream on the disc (which acts to add low specific angular momentum material at the outer edge and so tends to reduce the disc radius) shows that this modifies the phenomenon but does not alter the general behaviour (Murray 1996).

Hirose, Osaki & Minishige (1991) carried out simplified three dimensional calculations in an attempt to examine whether variations in disc scale height caused by the stream impact could explain the dipping X-ray sources. They found thickenings of the disc at around the phases expected, if these were the causes of modulation in the X-ray light curves. However, the difficulties of modeling the entire disc for many dynamical times meant that the resolution of the stream-disc impact region in this calculation was poor, and the authors commented that an improved treatment of the hydrodynamics beyond their 'sticky particle' scheme was desirable. Much better resolution of the impact region was achieved in calculations by Livio, Soker & Dgani (1986) and Dgani, Livio & Soker (1989), but this was achieved at the expense of considering only a small region surrounding the point where the stream met the disc. Thus, while these calculations demonstrated clearly the flow pattern in the collision region, there remained the possibility that the hydrostatic vertical structure assumed for the disc gas might not be realistic, if the response of the entire disc to the stream was included. With this caveat, however, the calculations did demonstrate that stream material could overflow the disc rim, as suggested by the work of Lubow & Shu (1975, 1976), Lubow (1989) and Frank, King & Lasota (1987).

In the current investigation, these studies are extended by performing three dimensional Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations of the response of the disc to the accretion stream. These simulations focus on the dynamical effects of the stream-disc collision – for which the SPH method is well-suited – and aim for the highest practicable resolution of the interaction region. The current calculations do not attempt to model the thermal or long-term viscous evolution of the disc, for which purpose other numerical techniques would be preferable. Ignoring these aspects permits improved resolution of the stream-disc impact region when compared, for example, to prior 3D simulations by Lanzafame, Belvedere & Molteni (1994a, 1994b), who were interested primarily in modeling outburst behaviour over longer timescales than those considered here.

The layout of this Chapter is as follows. In Section 6.2 I describe the computational methods and binary system parameters that are adopted for the simulations. Section 6.3 presents and interprets the results of the calculations, while Section 6.4 summarizes the conclusions and suggests further observational tests of the models.

6.2 Computational Approach

6.2.1 Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics

The simulations described in this paper were performed using a three dimensional SPH code minimally modified from that described by Benz (1990). SPH is a fully lagrangian, particle-based hydrodynamics method, that has been applied to a wide variety

of problems in astrophysics (see, e.g. Monaghan 1992), and has been shown to give closely comparable results to hydrodynamics codes based on alternative numerical techniques (e.g. PPM—Davies et al. 1993).

For the simulation of accretion discs, SPH has a number of advantages. A Keplerian disc exhibits a rapid variation of dynamical timescale with radius, which is computationally expensive if the problem demands that a significant range of radii be modelled. This difficulty can be partially alleviated in an SPH calculation by assigning each particle its own timestep satisfying the Courant stability criterion, so that the bulk of the disc material at relatively large radii can be integrated on a longer timestep. SPH has further merits in facilitating easy tracing of the flow, and in not wasting resources following the void regions outside and above the accretion disc.

Disadvantages of this method include the variable resolution of an SPH calculation, which is worst in the low density parts of the flow where the particle density is small. As these regions—well above the mid-plane of the disc—are precisely those that are most important for determining the X-ray and EUV absorption, this is a potentially serious problem. Its effect can be mitigated by exploiting the freedom that SPH allows in setting particle masses, so that the stream particles (which on collision with the disc will form the majority of the material high above the disc plane) have lower masses than those in the disc. More problematic is the fact that the code neglects the effects of radiation transport and cooling of the gas, so that the only control over the thermal properties arises via the choice of the equation of state. In this work an isothermal equation of state is adopted, which corresponds to assuming that the energy generated from viscous and shock heating is radiated away instantaneously. For a standard α accretion disc (Shakura & Sunyaev 1973), the thermal timescale, $t_{\text{th}} \sim \alpha^{-1} \Omega^{-1}$, is comparable to the dynamical timescale, $t_{\text{dyn}} \sim \Omega^{-1}$, if the Shakura-Sunyaev viscosity parameter α is of order unity (Pringle 1981). Arguments based on the timescales involved in the outbursts in these systems suggest that for CVs and LMXBs α is typically in the range 0.1–1, so that the isothermal equation of state provides a reasonable approximation to the much more complicated physics that is actually involved. Caution is nevertheless required in interpreting the results close to where shocks—and hence strong and rapid heating of the gas—occur in the simulations.

6.2.2 System Parameters

Having ignored both thermal and viscous effects, the important system parameters that remain are the mass ratio $q = M_2/M_1$, the disc mass M_{disc} , and the accretion rate \dot{M} . For low mass ratios $q \lesssim 0.25$, prior calculations show the formation of an eccentric, tidally unstable disc, which precesses in the rotating frame of the binary (Whitehurst 1988a,b; Lubow 1991). Such mass ratios are likely to be relevant both to subclasses of dwarf novae (the SU UMa systems), and to many LMXBs with low-mass (a few tenths M_{\odot}) companions. Conversely, higher mass ratios lead only to a modestly-distorted disc which remains fixed in the Roche frame of the binary.

The disc mass and accretion rate are expected to be significant mainly via the combination $f = \dot{M}P/M_{\text{disc}}$, where P is the period of the binary. f is then the fraction of the disc mass that is replenished per orbit, and it measures how strong a perturbation the stream can exert on the disc. To estimate sensible values for f , consider a Shakura-Sunyaev disc in which the viscosity is given by $\nu = \alpha c_s H$, where c_s is the sound speed and $H \approx c_s/\Omega$ is the disc scale height. For such a disc, the surface density Σ in the steady state is given by,

$$\nu\Sigma = \frac{\dot{M}}{3\pi}, \quad (6.1)$$

for radii much larger than the inner disc radius. Taking $M_{\text{disc}} \sim \pi R^2 \Sigma$, the resulting estimate for f becomes,

$$f = \frac{\dot{M}P}{M_{\text{disc}}} \sim 6\pi\alpha \left(\frac{c_s}{v_K}\right)^2, \quad (6.2)$$

where v_K is the Keplerian velocity in the disc and all quantities are evaluated at the disc edge. For a thin disc $c_s/v_K \ll 1$ (≈ 0.03 for the specific parameters adopted for the simulations), so that f is small, typically of order 10^{-2} , even for α of order unity. This is also consistent with the timescales of outbursts (in which mass accumulated in the disc over an extended time rapidly drains onto the central star), which generally last $\sim 10^2 P$.

In previous calculations the most dramatic effects of the companion on the accretion disc were found to occur for low mass ratios. I therefore adopt $q = 0.2$, as appropriate for a $0.3 M_\odot$ companion to a $1.4 M_\odot$ primary, and $f = 0.025$. For the particular value of M_{disc} in the calculations, this corresponds to a mass transfer rate of $\dot{M} = 2 \times 10^{17} \text{ gs}^{-1}$, or $3 \times 10^{-9} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (run LMXB2). To assist in disentangling the effects of the Roche potential from those caused solely by the impact of the stream, a second simulation was run with a very low mass secondary (q effectively zero), and otherwise similar values of disc mass and accretion rate (run LMXB1).

6.2.3 Disc and Stream Initial Conditions

As already remarked, simulating the innermost regions of the disc is computationally prohibitive. Fortunately it is also unnecessary, since on a dynamical timescale the stream is unable to influence the disc interior to the stream circularization radius. The disc can therefore be set up as an annulus with an inner edge at approximately the circularization radius and an outer edge at the tidal truncation radius as given by Papaloizou & Pringle (1977) and Paczyński (1977). To prevent a small fraction of particles from bringing the simulation to a halt by moving too far inward under the action of viscosity, angular momentum is added to any disc particle straying inside a radius R_{bound} from the primary. For the runs described here, R_{bound} is set at half the inner radius of the annulus. Over the relatively short timescale of the runs, no effect of this inner boundary condition on the disc annulus farther out is observed.

Although the effects of *physical* viscosity are unimportant for these calculations, it is important that the artificial viscosity in the code, parameterized by α_{SPH} and β_{SPH}

Figure 6.1: (a) Distribution of particles in z for a thin annulus in a quiescent (no stream) disc. The dashed line shows a gaussian distribution with width $\Delta z = 2 \times 10^9$ cm. (b) The disc scale height evaluated in cells for the same quiescent disc, plotted as a function of radius. The dashed line represents $H \propto R^{3/2}$.

(Benz 1990), is sufficient to prevent particle interpenetration in the shocks that occur when the stream strikes the disc edge. An isothermal equation of state provides the least resistance to particle interpenetration (as there is no shock heating to generate additional pressure gradients), and so rather high values for $\alpha_{\text{SPH}} = 2$ and $\beta_{\text{SPH}} = 4$ need to be adopted. Previous work (Bate 1995) has shown that this should be adequate to stop particles streaming past each other, and indeed no such behaviour is discernible in the runs. The internal SPH viscosities can be converted into a physical Shakura-Sunyaev α parameter via the formula (e.g. Bate 1996),

$$\alpha \approx \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{SPH}}}{20} \right) \left(\frac{h}{H} \right), \quad (6.3)$$

where h is the particle smoothing length in the simulation (3D). The β -viscosity will also have some effect, but for a disc that is resolved in the vertical direction, the contribution to the kinematic viscosity from the second-order β_{SPH} term will be smaller than that from α_{SPH} (Bate 1996). Using this expression it can be seen that for simulations that are resolved vertically ($h < H$, as in these calculations), typical SPH viscosity parameters lead to values of α that are smaller than those believed to pertain to CV and LMXB accretion discs, and there should be no problems arising from unreasonably large artificial viscosity in the simulations.

The disc gas is modelled using 30000 equal mass particles that are initially distributed on a close-packed lattice within 2.5° of the disc plane, and which have Keplerian velocities about the primary. The sound speed is set such that $c_s/v_K = 0.03$ at the outer edge of the disc—this gives a somewhat thicker disc than is usually assumed, but has the advantage that better resolution is attained in the vertical direction. The disc reaches a stable hydrostatic equilibrium structure quickly (in less than one orbit), after which the distribution of particles with z (perpendicular to the disc) for a narrow annulus of disc is as shown in Figure 6.1(a). The particles follow a gaussian distribution, as expected for an isothermal accretion disc, and track the density profile well, up to the height where the particle number density becomes very low. Calculating the disc scale height (defined as $H = \Sigma/\rho_{z=0}$, where Σ and $\rho_{z=0}$ are evaluated from the SPH calculation) as a function of radius yields the results shown in Figure 6.1(b). For an isothermal disc, $H \propto c_s/\Omega \propto R^{3/2}$, and this scaling is shown in the Figure as the dashed line. Over the range ($-0.3 < \log(R) < 0$) where the disc is resolved vertically this relation is found to be obeyed, with discrepancies at the inner and outer edges where the particle density is dropping off rapidly.

For run LMXB2 the presence of the companion means that the disc is not being set up with velocities that are consistent with disc orbits in the binary potential. To allow time for these initial conditions to be smoothed out, the disc is first evolved for ~ 10 orbits of the binary before the stream flow is switched on. During this relaxation period the disc develops a stable but distorted shape, with a smooth variation of surface density. For the purposes of the present work this represents well enough the ‘background’ disc structure onto which the stream flows, though if, for example, one wished to follow the disc precession in a 3D calculation, a more elaborate disc set up would certainly be desirable.

For the initial conditions of the stream, I utilise the results of Lubow & Shu (1975, 1976), see also review by Livio (1994). These authors show that the width of the stream, W , in both the azimuthal and vertical directions, is given approximately by,

$$W \sim \frac{c_s}{\Omega_{\text{binary}}}, \quad (6.4)$$

where c_s is here the sound speed at the surface of the mass-losing star and Ω_{binary} is the binary angular velocity. This is essentially the same relation as for the disc scale height, and implies that the stream is much thicker than the pressure scale height of the mass-donating star H_* (indeed, $W \sim \sqrt{H_* R_*}$).

Numerically, the stream is modelled as a tube of particles stretching outward from the inner Lagrange point, L_1 , with radial velocities set to be c_s towards the primary. When a particle passes inward of L_1 (towards the primary) it is added to the simulation and evolved under the influence of gravity and all hydrodynamic forces, while particles outside L_1 are simply rotated to follow the binary orbit. Initially the stream particles are strongly compressed in the radial direction (by a factor ~ 10). This ensures that when the stream reaches the disc edge the separations are comparable in R and in z , as required to model the impact hydrodynamics. It is assumed that the stream leaves

Figure 6.2: Particle distribution in the $x - y$ and $x - z$ planes for simulation LMXB2 (mass ratio of secondary to primary $q = 0.2$).

L_1 in hydrostatic equilibrium, and at this point the vertical density profile is set to be a gaussian with width W . This is truncated at 1 scale height, where the scale height is estimated by extrapolating the numerical results obtained from the disc (Figure 6.1), and allowing, where necessary, for the gravity of the secondary. The compression required in R near L_1 means that the stream there is not in numerical hydrostatic equilibrium, but this is of no consequence, since the stream flow toward the disc is ballistic. The simulations follow the stream-disc interaction for around 2-3 orbits of the outer disc, requiring 20000-30000 particles to achieve adequate resolution of the accretion stream.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Stream Overflow

Figure 6.2 shows a snapshot of particle positions during the latter stages of run LMXB2: For both simulations, a quasi-steady state appearance in the Roche frame is rapidly attained, so that although the disc mass is slowly increasing throughout,

Figure 6.3: Logarithmic density contours (dashed lines) in a vertical plane aligned with the direction of stream flow at the location where the stream strikes the disc. Vectors represent the velocity in this plane of stream material. The z -component of the velocity vectors has been enhanced by a factor of two for clarity.

successive snapshots look very similar. Where the stream reaches the disc, the Figure shows that the oblique collision both shears the stream and compresses the disc edge. Some stream material is transferring its momentum to the disc gas and becoming buried in the disc rim. This is similar to the behaviour seen in previous calculations (e.g. Livio et al. 1986; Rozyczka & Schwarzberg-Czerny 1987). However, from the $x-z$ projection it is also clear that some stream gas is overflowing the disc rim as a result of the collision. This material is being thrown to larger distances above the midplane than the original stream, and is many scale heights above the disc itself.

To clarify the origin of this overflowing gas, Figure 6.3 plots density contours in a vertical plane, aligned along the direction of the accretion stream flow where it reaches the disc edge. Also shown are velocity vectors in this plane for the stream gas, calculated

Figure 6.4: Density from simulation LMXB1 (secondary of zero mass) in the $x - y$ plane at (a) $z = 0$, and (b) $z = 0.15$.

by simple averaging of particle velocities in spheres of radius $2h$. Although the disc in general flares towards large radius ($H \propto R^{3/2}$), it can be seen that in the outermost regions of the disc where the surface density is dropping, the density contours form a wedge-like structure. The stream strikes this supersonically, and the outer parts ricochet off to greater distances from the disc midplane. This behaviour has been predicted by the analytic Sedov Solution obtained by Livio et al. (1986). The vertical velocities away from the $z = 0$ plane that are achieved in this manner are typically several times c_s , so this gas reaches a maximum $|z|$ that is many times the disc scale height. Further downstream the overflowing gas falls back to the disc, achieving higher velocities than on impact, because now it is closer to the primary where the vertical component of gravity is greater. While the central core of the stream tends to blunt the wedge, it is continually restored by fresh disc material that possesses a higher angular velocity than that of the binary.

6.3.2 Density Slices from the Simulations

Figs. 6.4 and 6.5 show the density calculated using the SPH smoothing algorithm for both simulations. The plots show the midplane density, panel (a), and the density at a few scale heights above the midplane, panel (b). In the latter plot, 4 independent time-slices have been co-added in order to reduce the Poisson noise due to limited particle number, though the behaviour described here is clearly seen also in individual snapshots. For both simulations the compression of the disc rim due to the momentum of the stream impact is evident (the oscillations in radius of the disc, downstream of the impact, are probably due to remaining anisotropies in particle distribution on impact, and are not

Figure 6.5: Density from simulation LMXB2 (full Roche potential, $q = 0.2$) in the $x - y$ plane at (a) $z = 0$, and (b) $z = 0.12$.

physical). However, except for this, the midplane density plots show little structure beyond what would be expected given the initial set up of these discs.

At high $|z|$, strong signatures of the stream impact are visible. For LMXB1 a single region of relatively high density is obtained, beginning at the point where the stream reaches the disc and persisting until around phase 0.75 (here phases are measured with respect to the phase at which an eclipse would occur, and increase clockwise in the plots). This peak lies well inside the outer edge of the disc, and arises from the overflowing stream material discussed earlier. Although the resolution at this z is limited by relatively small particle numbers, it appears that the overflowing gas does *not* form a well-collimated continuation of the accretion stream. Rather the impact leads to a broad fan of material ejected to high $|z|$ as a consequence of the collision.

For the simulation with the full Roche potential, a similar structure generated by the stream-disc interaction is seen in the density plots. In this instance however, a second broad and comparatively high density region is seen at phase 0.2, which originates from the eccentricity of the accretion disc in this simulation. The disc is flared, and so for a given high z slice, the greatest density contribution is expected to come from material at the largest radius. This leads to a peak roughly in the direction along which the disc is most extended, though from the simulation the peak is seen at a somewhat earlier phase, probably as a consequence of the disc gas not reaching hydrostatic equilibrium and hence lagging in adjusting to the changing vertical gravity. The magnitude of the second peak is probably overestimated by the simulation, as the SPH particles at the outer edge of the disc have no neighbours at greater radii and so adopt larger smoothing lengths to maintain a roughly constant number of neighbours. These larger smoothing lengths will enhance the density contribution at high $|z|$. When this numerical effect is

borne in mind, both simulations demonstrate that material directly thrown above the midplane by the stream-disc impact is likely to dominate the absorption column at high $|z|$.

6.3.3 Column Densities Towards the Primary

In order to quantify the observable effects of the material thrown out of the plane the column density σ has been calculated along various lines of sight toward the primary from the simulations. The column density,

$$\sigma(\phi, \theta) = \int \rho dl \quad (6.5)$$

is calculated from integration of the SPH density estimator along lines of sight toward the primary at phase ϕ and at angle θ above the disc midplane. ϕ values are chosen so that neighbouring lines of sight are calculated from different sets of particles and hence are independent. As the innermost particles have overly large smoothing lengths for the reasons already discussed, these are removed before column densities are calculated. This cut affects only $\sim 1\%$ of the particles.

Figure 6.6 shows the results for both simulations, for angles of elevation $\theta = 0, 6, 12^\circ$. For comparison, the dipping source X1822-371 is believed to be viewed at an inclination angle of 82° – 87° (Mason 1989). For LMXB1 there is no variation evident above the noise at $\theta = 0^\circ$. By $\theta = 6^\circ$ the overflowing stream material, seen in Figure 6.4 at high $|z|$, is producing a significant contribution to the column density, leading to a peak in σ at phase $\phi \sim 0.8$. There is marginal evidence for a broad feature also at $\phi \sim 0.2$, caused by the compressed disc rim expanding outwards downstream of the stream impact point. However, at the highest angle of elevation, $\theta = 12^\circ$, the overflowing stream gas provides the *only* source of absorbing column, and there is a single strong peak centred on $\phi = 0.85$ and extending from phase 0.7 through to eclipse. For an opacity generated solely by Thomson scattering a column density of order unity is required to produce an optical depth of 1, and hence for this accretion rate ($3 \times 10^{-9} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$) the overflowing gas would be sufficient to create significant absorption even at angles to the midplane $\theta \gtrsim 10^\circ$.

For run LMXB2 the situation is more complicated. At $\theta = 12^\circ$ there is a single strong peak in column density at phase 0.8, which as before is associated with the stream-disc interaction. There may be a hint of a very small peak at $\phi \sim 0.1$ – 0.2 . However in this simulation there is significant variation in σ with phase even at $\theta = 0^\circ$, as a result of the marked distortion of the disc shape under the gravitational influence of the companion. Of course viewed directly edge-on, the optical depth to the central object is enormous, and so the variation in this regime would not be observable. These variations suggest, however, that at intermediate viewing angles both effects should be important, and this is seen in the plot for $\theta = 6^\circ$, where two clear peaks are produced—one arising from the stream overflow and one from the disc structure. Since the disc precesses in the frame of the binary (for low q systems), the absorption feature arising solely from the eccentric

Figure 6.6: Column density σ towards the primary as a function of phase for varying angles of elevation above the disc plane $\theta = 0, 6, 12$ degrees. Left panels are for simulation LMXB1, right panels for LMXB2. Units are g cm^{-2} . Error bars are calculated from 4 independent time-slices of the simulations.

disc structure should vary linearly in phase with time. Conversely, structures generated directly by the stream-disc interaction should remain at fixed phases (regardless of the mass ratio of the binary).

6.3.4 Fate of Stream Material

Time-dependent models for accretion discs in (dwarf nova) systems vulnerable to thermal instability-driven outbursts generally add mass to the disc from the stream either in the outermost computational zone (e.g. Pringle, Verbunt & Wade 1986), or else with a narrow gaussian profile at the outer edge (e.g. Cannizzo 1993). Neither is likely to be a good representation of the physical situation if a significant fraction of the

Figure 6.7: Destination of stream mass (in arbitrary units) as a function of radius.

stream mass overflows the disc rim and circularises at smaller radii. To examine this possibility, Figure 6.7 shows the destination of stream material as a function of radius in the disc, for simulation LMXB1, where the disc is circular and the complicating effects of an eccentric disc are not present. The distribution is bimodal, with most of the mass being deposited and circularising at the outer disc rim, but with a significant fraction ($\sim 1/3$) ending up at much smaller radii. The outer peak is caused by the dense inner core of the stream, which on impact with the disc becomes buried in the outer edge, while the inner peak (near the stream circularisation radius) is formed from the stream gas that overflows the disc rim.

This result must be treated with some caution however, as the current simulations do not have sufficient resolution to investigate, for example, any surface instabilities that might entrain the overflowing stream gas more efficiently and thus keep it at larger radii. Calculations with a higher resolution and better treatment of the thermal properties of the gas will be required to investigate this possibility. The general picture from these simulations, however, is that neither mass addition exclusively at the outer edge nor mass addition primarily at the circularization radius is likely to prove a good approximation. Rather, the surface density increment is bimodal with roughly equal amplitudes at the two radii, and this is likely to alter the detailed behaviour seen in time-dependent disc instability models.

Figure 6.8: Rate of heating from shocks as a function of phase for annuli in the disc (simulation LMXB1). The panels run from the innermost annulus at upper left, to the outermost at bottom right. The disc edge is at $R \approx 0.9$ in these units.

6.3.5 Location of energy dissipation

Even in isothermal simulations such as these, artificial viscosity is used in the momentum equation to generate shocks and prevent particles streaming freely through each other. In the physical disc, these shocks would lead to strong heating of the gas, and create bright spots on the disc surface. The strength of this dissipation can be estimated by calculating the shock heating that would occur in the simulation if the gas had an adiabatic ($\gamma = 5/3$) equation of state, while the flow pattern remained as previously described.

Figure 6.8 shows the energy dissipation estimated in this way as a function of phase, for annuli that cover the radial extent of the disc. For the annuli at smaller radii,

the background level of dissipation is uniformly greater because of the increased viscous dissipation that is unconnected with shocks. Excesses over this level represent areas where bright spots might be expected to occur. As expected, the strongest dissipation is found in the outermost annulus, at the location where the stream strikes the disc. However there is also strong shock heating occurring in the innermost ring, at the location where the overflowing stream gas collides again with the disc (at phase $\phi \sim 0.6$). A smaller fraction of stream material reaches this radius, but being deeper in the potential well the total shock heating is similar. No prominent features are seen in the two intermediate annuli.

The width of the features seen in Figure 6.8 represents only the azimuthal extent of the regions where shock heating would occur, the actual size of the bright spots produced as the shocked gas cools will undoubtedly be much larger and may cover a sizeable fraction of the disc circumference (Rozyczka & Schwarzenberg-Czerny 1987). The calculations suggest that a second bright spot should be formed at the roughly diametrically opposed phase where the overflowing gas returns to the disc plane. This inner bright spot is of comparable luminosity to that formed directly by the stream-disc impact, though relative to the background emission at the smaller radius it is, of course, much weaker. It would thus be most easily seen in systems with low viscosity (e.g. dwarf novae with long recurrence times), and could provide valuable clues to the degree of stream overflow occurring in these systems.

6.4 Summary and Discussion

This Chapter has presented three dimensional SPH calculations of the stream-disc interaction. The main conclusion to be drawn from these simulations is that significant amounts of stream material are able to overflow or bounce off the edge of the disc, and flow over the disc surface towards smaller radii. This creates a peak in the column density towards the primary at a phase of around 0.8, and is a likely cause of the absorption dips observed at around this phase in some nearly edge-on low-mass X-ray binaries (see e.g. review by White, Nagase, & Parmar 1995). If this is the case, the absorbing material is located (in radial distance) intermediate between the disc edge and the stream circularization radius. At the highest angles of elevation above the disc surface ($\theta \gtrsim 10^\circ$), no significant absorbing column is seen at any other phases. Recent EUVE observations of U Gem in outburst (Long et al. 1996) show an absorption dip (at phase ~ 0.75) caused by material a few scale heights above the disc surface, in good agreement with the results of this study. ASCA observations show that the dips persist in quiescence (Szkody et al. 1996).

This result differs from that of Hirose, Osaki & Minishige (1991), who in addition to predicting absorption at phase 0.8 also found absorption at phase 0.2 in their models (although as they did not compute column densities from their simplified calculation it is unclear whether both those features would be visible at large θ). Significant absorption is observed at around phase 0.1–0.2 for lower angles of elevation above the disc plane, and

this seems to be primarily due to the eccentricity induced in the disc by the gravity of the companion. It may be noted that in low mass ratio systems absorption features generated by the eccentric disc structure should precess with the disc, and thus can be separated from those induced by the stream-disc interaction, which remain at a fixed phase (~ 0.8) regardless of the mass ratio. Therefore, in systems where two absorption features are seen, a straightforward observational test to determine their origin is possible, by monitoring for a prolonged period the phases of maximum absorption.

The presence of gas that is not in hydrostatic equilibrium flowing over the disc raises a number of intriguing possibilities. If exposed to an X-ray power-law spectrum from the central source, it may be prone to a two-phase instability and break up into dense clouds surrounded by a hot diffuse medium (Krolik, McKee & Tarter 1981; Frank, King & Lasota 1987). Such a picture might explain the very short-timescale variations seen in some dipping X-ray sources. Less speculatively, the wide range of radii over which mass from the stream circularises in these simulations, implies that significant changes might be expected in the behaviour predicted from time-dependent thermal disc instability models. In particular, during quiescence, the quasi-ballistic flow over the disc might dominate inflow caused by viscosity in the outer disc, and this would affect predictions for the behaviour of the disc radius. Significant stream overflow implies that less material with low specific angular momentum will be added at the outer edge of the disc, and hence less contraction of the disc radius during quiescence would be expected. If the degree of overflow were large (as might occur if the outer disc were cold relative to the mass-donating star), then substantive differences in the surface density profile during quiescence would also occur. This could lead, for example, to thermal instabilities triggered at intermediate disc radii, and other, detailed, differences to standard models.

For systems that undergo outbursts, the presence of overflowing stream gas provides a possible observational probe of the disc radius. As the disc expands, the phase of maximum absorption is expected to increase (closer to the phase of eclipse) as a consequence both of the position and angle at which the accretion stream reaches the disc. More subtle effects might also occur due to the varying temperature of the outer disc over the course of an outburst cycle. A hotter disc is thicker, and this should reduce the amount of stream material able to overflow the rim and thereby reduce the depth of the absorption. A thicker disc might of course absorb radiation from the primary directly, but this effect would be axisymmetric and thus distinguishable from that caused by high $|z|$ stream gas. Simultaneously *more* energy would be dissipated in the bright spot at the disc rim, so that the bright spot luminosity would increase as the outburst commenced. There is some observational evidence that this brightening does occur (Livio 1994).

In their attempt to model the visual light curve of the eclipsing supersoft X-ray source CAL 87, Schandl, Meyer-Hofmeister, & Meyer (1996), found that they had to assume the presence of an optically thick 'spray' of material around the disc. They conjectured that such a spray might form by the disc-stream interaction. An examination of Figure 6.2 reveals that a configuration similar to that assumed by Schandl et al. (1996) is indeed obtained from these simulations.

The analysis of the simulations that is presented here has concentrated on absorption features seen in the X-ray and EUV wavebands. Important information is also available in the optical, especially from the analysis of time-resolved spectra using doppler tomography (Marsh & Horne 1988). Many systems have now been mapped using this technique (e.g. Kaitchuck et al. 1994), and in some cases the path of the accretion stream can be clearly traced. A future comparison of synthetic doppler maps generated from simulations of the type presented here with these data appears to provide a fruitful direction in which research into stream-disc interactions can continue.

Bibliography

- Adams F.C., Emerson J.P., Fuller G.A., 1990, ApJ, 357, 606
- Adams F.C., Shu F.H., 1986, ApJ, 308, 836
- Alcalá J.M., 1994, Ph.D. Thesis, Ruprecht-Karls-Universität, Heidelberg
- Alcalá J.M. et al, 1996, A&A, submitted
- Appenzeller I., Dearborn D.S.P., 1984, ApJ, 278, 689
- Armitage P.J., 1995, MNRAS, 274, 1242
- Balbus S.A., Hawley J.F., 1991, ApJ, 376, 214
- Balbus S.A., Hawley J.F., 1992, ApJ, 400, 610
- Baliunas S.L., 1988, in Dupree A.K., Lago M.T.V.T., eds, *Formation and Evolution of Low Mass Stars*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, p. 319
- Basri G., Marcy G.W., Valenti J.A., 1992, ApJ, 390, 622
- Bate M., 1995, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Cambridge, p. 43
- Bate M., 1996, in preparation
- Beckwith S.V.W., Sargent A.I., Chini R., Gusten R., 1990, AJ, 99, 924
- Bell K.R., Lin D.N.C., 1994, ApJ, 427, 987
- Benz W., 1990, in *The Numerical Modeling of Nonlinear Stellar Pulsations*, ed. J.R. Buchler, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, p. 269
- Bertout C., 1989, ARAA, 27, 351
- Bertout C., Basri G., Bouvier J., 1988, ApJ, 330, 350
- Bouvier J., 1991, in *Angular Momentum Evolution of Young Stars*, Catalano S. & Stauffer J.R., eds, NATO ASI Series C340, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, p. 41
- Bouvier J., Cabrit S., Fernández M., Martin E.L., Matthews J.M., 1993, A&A, 272, 176

- Bouvier J., Covino E., Kovo O., Martin E.L., Matthews J.M., Terranegra L., Beck S.C., 1995, *A&A*, 299, 89
- Brandenburg A., Nordlund A., Stein R.F., Torkelsson U., 1995, *ApJ*, 446, 741
- Bruch A., 1992, *A&A*, 266, 237
- Cameron A.C., Campbell C.G., 1993, *A&A*, 274, 309
- Cameron A.C., Campbell C.G., Quaintrell H., 1995, *A&A*, 298, 133
- Campbell C.G., 1992, *Geophys. Astrophys. Fluid Dyn.*, 63, 179
- Cannizzo J.K., 1993, *ApJ*, 419, 318
- Clarke C.J., 1996, in *Evolutionary Processes in Binary Stars*, eds R.A.M.J. Wijers, M.B. Davies & C.A. Tout, Kluwer Academic Publishers, p. 31
- Clarke C.J., Armitage P.J., Smith K.W., Pringle J.E., 1995, *MNRAS*, 273, 639
- Clarke C.J., Lin D.N.C., Pringle J.E., 1990, *MNRAS*, 242, 439
- Clarke C.J., Pringle J.E., 1993, *MNRAS*, 261, 190
- Davies M.B., 1995, *MNRAS*, 276, 887
- Davies M.B., Ruffert M., Benz W., Müller E., 1993, *A&A*, 272, 430
- Dgani R., Livio M., Soker N., 1989, *ApJ*, 336, 350
- Duquennoy A., Mayor M., 1991, *A&A*, 248, 485
- Edwards S. et al., 1993, *AJ*, 106, 372
- Edwards S., 1995, *Rev. Mex. As. Ap. (Conference Series)*, 1, 309
- Edwards S., Hartigan P., Ghandour L., Andrulis C., 1994, *AJ*, 108, 1056
- Faulkner J., Lin D.N.C., Papaloizou J., 1983, *MNRAS*, 205, 359
- Feigelson E.D., 1996, *ApJ*, in press
- Frank J., King A.R., Lasota J.P., 1987, *A&A*, 178, 137
- Frank J., King A.R., Raine D., 1992, in *Accretion Power in Astrophysics*, 2nd edition, Cambridge, p. 67
- Feigelson E.D., Welty A.D., Imhoff C.L., Hall J.C., Etzel P.B., Phillips R.B., Lonsdale C.J., 1994, *ApJ*, 432, 373
- Ghez A.M., 1996, in *Evolutionary Processes in Binary Stars*, eds R.A.M.J. Wijers, M.B. Davies & C.A. Tout, Kluwer Academic Publishers, p. 1

- Ghosh P., 1995, MNRAS, 272, 763
- Ghosh P., Lamb F.K., 1979, ApJ, 232, 259
- Gilliland R.L., 1986, ApJ, 300, 339
- Gomez M., Hartmann L., Kenyon S.J., Hewett R., 1993, AJ, 105, 1927
- Guenther E.W., Emerson J.P., 1995, in Siebenmorgen R., Käuffl H.U., eds, ESO Proceedings, in *The role of dust in the formation of stars*, in press
- Guenther E.W., Emerson J.P., 1996, A&A, 309, 777
- Gullbring E., 1994, A&A, 287, 131
- Hall S.M., Clarke C.J., Pringle J.E., 1996, MNRAS, 278, 303
- Hartigan P., Edwards S., Ghandour L., 1995, ApJ, 452, 736
- Hartmann L., 1991, in *The Physics of Star Formation and Early Stellar Evolution*, eds C.J. Lada & N.D. Kylafis, Kluwer Academic Publishers, p. 623
- Hartmann L., 1994, in *Theory of Accretion Disks-2*, eds Duschl W.J., Frank J., Meyer F., Meyer-Hofmeister E., Tscharnuter W.M., eds, NATO ASI Series C417, Kluwer Academic Publishers, p. 19
- Hartmann L., Hewett R., Calvet N., 1994, ApJ, 426, 669
- Hawley J.F., Balbus S.A., 1991, ApJ, 376, 223
- Hawley J.F., Balbus S.A. 1992, ApJ, 400, 595
- Hawley J.F., Gammie C.F., Balbus S.A., 1995, ApJ, 440, 742
- Hellier C., Livio M., 1994, ApJ, 424, L57
- Herbst W., Herbst D.K., Grossman E.J., Weinstein D., 1994, AJ, 108, 1906
- Hirose M., Osaki Y., Minishige S., 1991, PASJ, 43, 809
- Horne K., 1985, MNRAS, 213, 129
- Horne K., 1994, in *Theory of Accretion Disks 2*, eds F. Meyer, W. J. Duschl, E. Meyer-Hofmeister, J. Frank, & W. Tscharnuter (Dordrecht: Kluwer), p. 77
- Ichikawa S., Osaki Y., 1992, PASJ, 44, 15
- Ichikawa S., Osaki Y., 1994, in *Theory of Accretion Disks 2*, eds F. Meyer, W. J. Duschl, E. Meyer-Hofmeister, J. Frank, & W. Tscharnuter (Dordrecht: Kluwer), p. 169
- Johns-Krull C.M., 1996, A&A, 306, 803

- Joy A.H., 1945, ApJ, 102, 168
- Johnstone R.M., Penston M.V., 1987, MNRAS, 227, 797
- Kaitchuck R.H., Schlegel E.M., Honeycutt R.K., Horne K., Marsh T.M., White J.C., II, Mansperger C.S., 1994, ApJS, 93, 519
- Kawazoe E., Mineshige S., 1993, PASJ, 45, 715
- Kenyon S.J., 1995, Rev. Mex. As. Ap. (Conference Series), 1, 237
- Kenyon S.J., Hartmann L., 1987, ApJ, 323, 714
- Kenyon S.J., Hartmann L., 1995, ApJS, 101, 117
- Kenyon S.J., Yi I., Hartmann L., 1996, ApJ, 462, 439
- Keppens R., MacGregor K.B., Charbonneau P., 1995, A&A, 294, 469
- Koerner D.W., Sargent A.I., 1995, AJ, 109, 2138
- Königl A., 1991, ApJ, 370, L39
- Krolik J.H., McKee C.F., Tarter C.B., 1981, ApJ, 249, 422
- Lanzafame G., Belvedere G., Molteni D., 1994a, MNRAS, 258, 152
- Lanzafame G., Belvedere G., Molteni D., 1994b, MNRAS, 267, 312
- Lin D.N.C., Papaloizou J., 1979, MNRAS, 186, 799
- Lin D.N.C., Papaloizou J., Faulkner J., 1985, MNRAS, 257, 633
- Lin D.N.C., Pringle J.E., 1976, in *Structure and Evolution of Close Binary Systems*, ed. P. Eggleton, D Reidel, Dordrecht, p. 237
- Livio M., 1993, in *Accretion Disks in Compact Stellar Systems*, ed. J.C. Wheeler (Singapore: World Scientific), p. 243
- Livio M., 1994, in *Interacting Binaries*, Saas-Fee Advanced Course 22, eds. H. Nusser & A. Orr, Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, p. 135
- Livio M., Pringle J.E., 1992, MNRAS, 259, 23P
- Livio M., Soker N., Dgani R., 1986, ApJ, 305, 267
- Long K.S., Mauche C.W., Raymond J.C., Szkody P., Mattei J.A., 1996, ApJ, in press
- Lovelace R.V.E., Romanova M.M., Bisnovatyi-Kogan G.S., 1995, MNRAS, 275, 244
- Lubow S.H., 1989, ApJ, 340, 1064
- Lubow S.H., 1991, ApJ, 381, 268

- Lubow S.H., Artymowicz P., 1996, in *Evolutionary Processes in Binary Stars*, eds R.A.M.J. Wijers, M.B. Davies & C.A. Tout, Kluwer Academic Publishers, p. 53
- Lubow S.H., Shu F.H., 1975, *ApJ*, 198, 383
- Lubow S.H., Shu F.H., 1976, *ApJ*, 207, L53
- Lynden-Bell D., Boily C., 1994, *MNRAS*, 267, 146
- Lynden-Bell D., Pringle J.E., 1974, *MNRAS*, 168, 603
- Marsh T.R., Horne K., 1988, *MNRAS*, 235, 269
- Martin S.C., 1996, *ApJ*, in press
- Mason K.O., 1989, in *Proc. 23rd ESLAB Symp. on Two-Topics in X-Ray Astronomy*, ESA SP-296, p. 113
- McCaughrean M.J., O'Dell C.R., 1996, *AJ*, 111, 1977
- Meyer F., Meyer-Hofmeister E., 1994, *A&A*, 288, 175
- Meyer-Hofmeister E., Vogt N., Meyer F., 1996, preprint
- Mineshige S., 1988, *A&A*, 190, 72
- Monaghan J.J., 1992, *ARA&A*, 30, 543
- Montmerle T., 1992, *Mem. Soc. Astron. It.*, 63, 663
- Montmerle T., Casanova S., 1995, *Rev. Mex. As. Ap. (Conference Series)*, 1, 329
- Murray J.R., 1996, *MNRAS*, 279, 402
- Neuhäuser R., Sterzik M.F., Torres G., Martin E.L., 1995, *A&A*, 299, L13
- O'Neal D., Feigelson E.D., Mathieu R.D., Myers P.C., 1990, *AJ*, 100, 1610
- Nousek J.A., Baluta C.J., Corbet R.H.D., Mukai K., Osborne J.P., Ishida M., 1994, *ApJ*, 436, L19
- Ogilvie G.I., Pringle J.E., 1996, *MNRAS*, 279, 152
- Osterloh M., Beckwith S.V.W., 1995, *ApJ*, 439, 228
- Osterloh M., Thommes E., Kania U., 1996, *A&A*, in press
- Ostriker E.C., Shu F.H., 1995, *ApJ*, 447, 813
- Paczyński B., 1977, *ApJ*, 216, 822
- Papaloizou J., Lin D.N.C., 1995, *ARAA*, 33, 505

- Papaloizou J., Pringle J.E., 1977, MNRAS, 181, 441
- Pearson K.J., King A.R., 1995, MNRAS, 276, 1303
- Phillips R.B., Lonsdale C.J., Feigelson E.D., 1991, ApJ, 382, 261
- Phillips R.B., Lonsdale C.J., Feigelson E.D., Deeney B.D., 1996, AJ, 111, 918
- Pols O., Tout C.A., Eggleton P.P., Han Z.W., MNRAS, 274, 964
- Popham R., 1996, ApJ, in press
- Potter, D., 1973, *Computational Physics*, Wiley, London
- Preibisch Th., Zinnecker H., Schmitt J.H.M.M., 1993, A&A, 279, L33
- Pringle J.E., 1981, ARA&A, 19, 137
- Pringle J.E., Verbunt F., Wade R.A., 1986, MNRAS, 221, 169
- Pye J.P., Hodgkin S.T., Stern R.A., Stauffer J.R., MNRAS, 266, 798
- Rozyczka M., Schwarzenberg-Czerny A., 1987, Acta Astron., 37, 141
- Sargent A.I., 1996, in *Discs and Outflows around Young Stars*, eds S.V.W. Beckwith, A. Natta & J. Staude, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, in press
- Schandl S., Meyer-Hofmeister E., Meyer F., 1996, A&A, submitted
- Shakura N.I., Sunyaev R.A., 1973, A&A, 24, 337
- Shore S.N., 1994, in *Interacting Binaries*, Saas-Fee Advanced Course 22, eds. H. Nussebaumer & A. Orr, Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, p. 1
- Shu F.H., 1992, in *The Physics of Astrophysics: II Dynamics*, University Science Books, Mill Valley, p. 82
- Smith K.W., Lewis G.F., Bonnell I.A., 1995, MNRAS, 276, L5
- Smith K.W., Bonnell I.A., Lewis G.F., 1995, MNRAS, 276, 263
- Smith M.D., 1994, A&A, 287, 523
- Stapelfeldt K.R., et al., 1994, Bull. American Astron. Soc., 185, #48.02
- Stern R.A., Schmitt J.H.M.M., Kahabka P.T., 1995, ApJ, 448, 683
- Sterzik M.F., Alcalá J.M., Neuhäuser R., Schmitt J.H.M.M., 1995, A&A, 297, 418
- Stone J.M., Norman M.L., 1994, ApJ, 433, 746
- Strom S.E., 1995, Rev. Mex. As. Ap. (Conference Series), 1, 317

- Szkody P., Long K.S., Sion E.M., Raymond J.C., 1996, ApJ, in press
- Tanaka Y., et al., 1995, Nature, 375, 659
- Tassoul J-L., Tassoul M., 1992, ApJ, 395, 259
- Terquem C., Papaloizou J.C.B., 1996, MNRAS, 279, 767
- Tout C.A., Pringle J.E., 1992, MNRAS, 256, 269
- Tout C.A., Pringle J.E., 1992, MNRAS, 259, 604
- Tout C.A., Pringle J.E., 1996, MNRAS, submitted
- van den Heuvel E.P.J., 1994, in *Interacting Binaries*, Saas-Fee Advanced Course 22, eds. H. Nussbaumer & A. Orr, Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, p. 263
- Vrba F.J., Chugainov P.F., Bruce Weaver W.M., Stauffer J.S., 1993, AJ, 106, 1608
- Walter F.M., Brown A., Mathieu R.D., Myers P.C., Vrba F.J., 1988, AJ, 96, 297
- Wang Y.-M., 1995, ApJ, 449, L153
- Warren J.K., Sirk M.M., Vallergera J.V., 1995, ApJ, 445, 909
- White N.E., Holt S.S., 1982, ApJ, 257, 318
- White N.E., Arnaud K., Day C.S.R., Ebisawa K., Gotthelf E.V., Mukai K., Soong Y., Yaqoob T., Antunes A., 1994, PASJ, 46, L97
- White N.E., Nagase F., Parmar A.N., 1995, in *X-Ray Binaries*, eds. W.H.G. Lewin, J. van Paralijs, E.P.J. van den Heuvel (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press), p. 1
- Whitehurst R., 1988a, MNRAS, 232, 35
- Whitehurst R., 1988b, MNRAS, 233, 529
- Wolk S.J., Walter F.M., 1996, AJ, in press
- Wood J.H., Horne K., Berriman G., Wade R.A., 1989, ApJ, 341, 974
- Wood J.H., Horne K., Berriman G., Wade R.A., O'Donoghue D., 1986, MNRAS, 219, 629
- Yi I., 1994, ApJ, 428, 760
- Zycki P., Krolick J.H., Zdziarski A.A., Kallman T.R., 1994, ApJ, 437, 597

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